

Improving supply chain management through the implementation of social sustainability in the agricultural sector. A case of Cameroon

By

Molonge Uriel Ndely

A thesis submitted to the University of the west of Scotland in part fulfilment of the requirement for the degree of Doctor of Business Administration

In May 2022

Supervised

by

Dr. Teslim Bukoye

Abstract

Unattended social issues in the agricultural supply chain might result in unwanted consequences. The successful implementation of social sustainability initiatives is essential for the agricultural supply chain to sustain long-term growth and profitability. Grounded in the stakeholder resource-based view and the strategic contingency theory, the purpose of this qualitative multi case study was to explore the strategic implementation of social sustainability on improving supply chain management on the agriculture sector of a lower-middle income country and to develop and validate a framework for implementing improvement on social sustainability in supply chain management. Twenty-three semi-structured interviews were conducted from five purposefully selected agribusiness companies which have strategically considered sustainability in their operations and there is community awareness of their sustainability activities. Data analysis of the interviews and documents using Yin's five-phase analysis led to the configuration of various strategic approaches to implement social sustainability on improving supply chain management. A recommendation is that companies in the agriculture sector should reengineer their strategies to business situations while taking into consideration resource needs of different stakeholders. The implications for a positive social sustainability improvement include enhanced levels of professionalism demanded by market actors, the development of innovative capabilities and boost of economic opportunities for the agribusiness companies.

Declaration of Originality.

I certify that all material in this thesis that is not my work has been attributed to the originator and that no material has previously been submitted in whole or in part and approved for the award of any degree or professional qualification by this or any other University.

Acknowledgment

I would begin by thanking the Almighty God for the strength and fortitude without which it could have been impossible to journey to completion.

An incredibly special thanks to my lead supervisor, Dr. Teslim Bukoye for his endless support from the very start of this thesis. He has provided professional guidance throughout my DBA. His pushfulness for consistency in quality highly inspired me achieving this project. Thanks to my assessors, Dr. Tewelde Berhane and Dr. Smithson Steve. I appreciate your support, comments, and motivation.

I thank all managers from the manufacturing companies that took part in this study for their time and corporation throughout the study.

An incredibly special thanks to my loving family whose support words are not enough to describe my dear parents (Mr. and Mrs. Molonge), my brothers (Kinge and Ndive), sisters (Nanyongo, Namondo, Dr. Nalovah, and Eposi), my in-law (Mweke), my special one (Evenye Doris) and my friend Gladys Mossengi. I deeply appreciate your ceaseless prayers, support, and trust in me all through till the end.

Finally, I thank every other person not mentioned here for your support and encouragement.

Contents

Abstract	2
Declaration of Originality	3
Acknowledgment	4
Contents	5
Abbreviations	11
Chapter One	13
1.1 Introduction	13
1.2 Background of the Study	16
1.3 Problem Statement	18
1.4 Research Questions, Aims and Objectives	18
1.4.1 Research Questions	18
1.4.2 The Aim of this Research	19
1.4.3 The Objectives of this Research	19
1.5 Significance of the Study	20
1.6 Overview of the Research Methodology	21
1.7 Thesis Structure	22
Chapter Two – Literature Review	24
2.0 Introduction to Literature Review	24
Part one – Conceptual Underpinning	24
2.1.1 Supply Chain Management	24
2.1.2 Supply Chain Sustainability (SCS)	28
2.1.2.1 The Triple Bottom Line (TBL)	31
2.1.2.2 Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM)	35
2.1.3 Social sustainability	39
a. Definition of social sustainability	39
b. Social Dimensions	42
c. Sources of Analysis of the Social Dimension	45
d. Social Supply Chain Entities	46
2.1.3.1 Drivers of Social Sustainability in Supply Chain Management	47
2.1.3.2 Principles for Managing Social Sustainability	50
2.1.3.3 Barriers/challenges to Social Sustainability	53
2.1.3.4 Solutions to address the barriers for social sustainability in supply chain management	56
2.1.3.5 Benefits of implementing Social Sustainability in supply chain management	57

2.1.4 The conceptual framework	61
2.1.5 Theoretical Underpinning	63
2.1.5.1 Stakeholder Resource Base View (SRBV)	65
2.1.5.2 Contingency Theory	68
2.1.6 Potential Corporate Social Responsibility	69
Part Two – Contextual Underpinning	72
2.2.1.1 Overview of Cameroon	72
2.2.1.2 Foundation of the Country’s Long-term Development	73
2.2.1.3 The Objectives of the Long-Term Developmental Vision	74
2.2.2 The Agribusiness Supply Chain Management	78
2.2.3 Cameroon Agribusiness Environment	81
2.3 Summary	85
Chapter Three - Research Methodology	86
3.1 Introduction	86
3.2 Philosophical Underpinning	86
3.2.1 Ontology and Epistemology	86
3.2.2. Major Ontological and Epistemological Stances	87
3.2.2.1 Positivism	89
3.2.2.2 Interpretivism	89
3.2.3 Critical Realism	92
3.2.4 Philosophical Considerations of SCM	93
3.2.5 Philosophical Stance for This Research	93
3.3 Research Design	95
3.3.1 Research Methods	95
3.3.1.1 Methodological Approach – Qualitative	97
3.4 Research Strategy	98
3.4.1 Research Strategy: Case Study	99
3.4.1.1 Justification of Case Study as a Research Strategy for This Study	100
3.4.2 Instrument Development	103
3.4.2.1 Unit of Analysis	103
3.4.2.2 Sampling	104
3.4.2.2.1 Criteria for Case Selection	104
3.4.2.3 Main Case Studies	107
3.4.2.4 The Case Study Protocol	109

3.5 Data Gathering	110
3.5.1 Instruments for Data Gathering	110
3.5.1.1 Semi-Structured Interviews.....	111
3.5.1.2 Documents.....	112
3.5.2 Data Gathering Technique	112
3.6 Data Analysis	114
a. Compiling	115
b. Disassembling	116
c. Reassembling	116
d. Interpretation	117
e. Concluding	118
3.6.1 Achieving Data Analysis for this Research	118
3.7 Data management	119
3.8 Quality Criteria and Dissemination	121
a. Dependability	121
b. Credibility	122
c. Transferability	122
d. Confirmability	123
3.9 Ethical Consideration	125
3.9.1 Informed Consent	125
3.9.2 Anonymity and Confidentiality	126
3.10 Summary	126
Chapter Four – Findings	128
4.1 Introduction	128
4.2 Presentation of the findings	128
4.3 Research question 1 – What is the current trend of social sustainability in supply chain management in developing countries?	130
4.4 Research question 2 – What are the drivers, principles, and barriers to social sustainability and how do these contribute to the operational performance of the entire agricultural supply chain in Cameroon?	133
4.4.1a Social Dimensions	133
4.4.1b Correlation to the literature	138
4.4.2a Drivers for Social Sustainability	140
4.4.2b Correlation to the literature	140
4.4.3a Social Relationship Levels	141

4.4.3b Correlation to the literature	142
4.4.4a Principles for Engaging the Social Sustainability Initiatives.....	142
4.4.4b Correlation with the Literation	143
4.4.5 Challenge/Barriers to Social Sustainability Adoption.....	144
4.4.5.1 Inadequate Resources and Adaptive Capabilities	144
4.4.5.2 Inadequate Understanding and Knowledge of the Importance of Social Sustainability.....	145
4.4.5.3 Inadequate Basic Infrastructures and Amenities	145
4.4.5.4 Intermediaries and Third Parties	146
4.5.5 Culture	146
4.5.6 Corporate Social Responsibility Projects Not Effective.....	147
4.5.5 Benefits of Social Sustainability Adoption.....	147
4.4.6 Way forward.....	151
4.5 Research question 3 – How are the social sustainability initiatives implemented and managed in the agricultural supply chain with respect to Cameroon?	153
4.6 Findings Relative to the Adopted Theories	156
4.7 Summary.....	158
Chapter Five - Discussion and Framework Development.....	160
5.1 Introduction.....	160
5.2 Objective 1	160
5.3 Objective 2	160
5.4 Objective 3	161
5.4.1 Extrinsically Driven social initiatives/collaboration.	163
5.4.2 Intrinsically driven social initiatives/collaboration.	165
5.4.3 Extrinsically driven social initiatives/formalisation.	166
5.4.4 Intrinsically driven social initiatives/formalisation.	168
5.4.5 Extrinsically driven social initiatives/ formalisation and collaboration.	169
5.4.6 Intrinsically driven social initiatives/formalisation and collaboration.	170
5.5 Objective 4	172
5.5.1 Supplier.....	172
5.5.2 Focal firm.....	173
5.5.3 Customer.....	175
5.6 Objective 5	177
5.6.1 Developing a Framework for Integrating social Sustainability into Cameroon Agricultural supply chain.....	177

5.6.1.1 Challenges/Barriers	180
5.6.1.2 Propose Social Sustainability Framework Measures for the Agricultural Supply Chain	182
5.6.1.2.1 Stakeholder Engagement	182
5.6.1.2.2 Integration of Sustainability into Corporate Policy	183
5.6.1.2.3 Collaboration with Host Communities	184
5.6.1.2.4 Education and Awareness Programme	186
5.6.1.2.5 Lean and Agile Social Supply Chain Measures	187
5.6.1.2.6 Transparency	189
5.6.1.2.7 Wealth Creation Programmes.....	189
5.6.2 Framework Validation	190
5.6.2.1 Validation of the Framework	194
5.7 Performance Indicators for Social Sustainability	196
5.8 Summary.....	201
6.1 introduction	202
6.2 Meeting the Aim and Objectives of this Thesis.....	202
6.3 Research Implications	205
6.3.1. Implications to Theory	205
6.3.2 Implication to practice.....	208
6.4 Limitations and Recommendations for Further Research	210
6.5 Summary.....	211
References.....	212
Appendices.....	249
Appendix A – Case Study Protocol	249
Appendix B - Interview Guide for Case Organisations.....	254
Appendix C - Social Initiatives.....	258
Appendix E – Framework Feedback Sheet	265
Appendix F - Participant's information sheet	267
Appendix G – Drivers for internal and external social sustainability initiatives	269
Appendix H – literature review table.....	271

List of Tables

Table 1 Validated Social Dimensions	44
Table 2 Drivers for extrinsic and intrinsic motivated social initiatives within supply chains.	49
Table 3 Mechanisms for Implementing Social Sustainability	52
Table 4 Barriers to Social Sustainability	55
Table 5 Performance benefits to social sustainability.....	59
Table 6 Key Indicators.....	72
Table 7 Tentative Stages of the Country’s Long-Term Development Towards its Vision	75
Table 8 Network of Basic Assumptions Characterising the Subjectivist-Objectivist Debate Within Social Science	88
Table 9 Demographic Data of Respondents	128
Table 10 Dimensions of Social Sustainability	134
Table 11 Social Initiatives driver, implementation criteria and the social relationship levels.	139
Table 12 Benefits of social sustainability initiatives.	147
Table 13 summarising the findings.....	158
Table 14 Quotes from each type of social sustainability initiative.....	162
Table 15 Model for implementing social sustainability into supply chains.	165
Table 16 Feedback Showing the Perception of Practitioners on the Proposed Framework ..	194
Table 17 Metrics for Social Sustainability Framework in the Agricultural Sector	197
Table 18 meets the aim and objectives of this research.....	202

Figures

Figure 1. Triple Bottom Line (Elkington, 1994).....	31
Figure 2 Sustainable Supply Chain Management (Carter and Rogers, 2008)	38
Figure 3 conceptual framework	62
Figure 4 Food and Agribusiness Supply Shain (adapted from Tsolakis et al. (2014).	79
Figure 5 Agricultural GDP contribution in Cameroon	82
Figure 6 EU Agri-food IMPORTS from Cameroon by product category	83
Figure 7 Structure of EU Agri-food trade with Cameroon, 2012 – 2022	83
Figure 8 The Five-Stage Research Process Model (Adapted from Seuring, 2008).....	102
Figure 9 existing trends of social sustainability.....	130
Figure 10 Social Sustainability Initiatives	153
Figure 12 Current State of Challenges in the Cameroonian Manufacturing Industry	182
Figure 13 Social Sustainability Framework for the Cameroonian Agribusiness Companies (V1).....	186
Figure 14 Social Sustainability Framework for the Cameroonian Manufacturing Sector (V2).	192

Abbreviations

ANOR – Standards and Quality Agency (L’agence des Normes et de la Qualite)

CERES – Coalition for Environmentally Responsible Economics Society

CSR – Corporate social responsibility

FSSC 2200 – Food Safety Management System

GESP – Growth Employment Strategy Paper

GRI – Global Reporting Initiatives

GPD – Gross domestic product

HIPC – Heavily Indebted Poor Country Initiative

ISO – International Organisation for Standardisation

LMICs – Lower- and middle-income countries

MDG – Millennium Development Goals

MINEPAT – Ministry of Economy, Planning and Regional Development

NDS30 – National Development Strategy 2020 – 2030

NIC – Newly industrialized country

QMS – Quality Management System

PRSP – Poverty Reduction Strategy Paper

PSR - Purchasing social Responsibility.

SAPs – Structural Adjustments Programmes

SCG – Supply Chain governance

SCM – Supply chain management

SC – Supply Chain

SS – Social sustainability

SSC – Sustainable supply chain

SSCM – Sustainable supply chain management

SSSCM – Socially sustainable supply chain management

SMART – Specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and timebound

SSM – Sustainable Supply Management

TBL – Triple bottom line

UN – United Nations

UNCSD - United Nations Commission on Sustainable Development

UNEP – United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP)

Chapter One

1.1 Introduction

Modern-day businesses are characterised by bringing their commercial activities nearer to the designated markets and the production of goods and services from every direction to satisfy customers' demands in a timely and well-structured manner. This supposed the need for a system that enabled the coordination across all activities involved in a process known as the concept of supply chain (Wisner et al., 2016). Over the years supply chains have emerged from the traditional buying and selling of goods and services to a well-designed and organised exchange of goods and services through a system that encompasses the sourcing of raw materials for the production of goods and services, transportation of raw materials to production sites, the production process, quality checks, the distribution and storage to warehouses, and delivering the goods to end-users promptly and sometimes the unused parts or after a life of the products (Hugos, 2018).

To ensure the efficient and effective flow of supply chain activities, services and everyone involved in the process constitutes supply chain management (SCM). Supply chain management is defined as: “the systematic, strategic coordination of the traditional business functions and the tactics across these business functions within a particular company and across businesses within the supply chain, to improve the long-term performance of the individual companies and the supply chain as a whole” (Mentzer et al., 2001).

In recent times, organisations are expected by stakeholders and the wider society to efficiently manage supply chains beyond the aspects of time delivery, cost minimisation, quality, customer satisfaction, and financial growth to further consider the environmental and social impacts of their activities on people and society (Mani et al., 2018). This brings into focus the apparent necessity for integrating sustainability into supply chains. Sustainability asserts the

incorporation of economic, environmental, and social considerations into the activities and processes of firms (Elkington, 2002). Sustainable Supply Chain management is the integration of sustainability thinking including environmental, economic, and social dimensions into a firm supply chain to mitigate issues of poor brand perception, and economic loss and to enhance overall supply chain performance (Mani and Gunasekaran, 2018; Fernando et al., 2022). Thus, sustainability and sustainable supply chain management are centered on the triple bottom line (TBL) concept.

Sustainability initiatives have been extensively adopted by organisations in their supply chains and are considered a crucial aspect for long-term survival, as well as providing an operational and strategic advantage in highly competitive business environments (Claro and Esteves 2021; Morais and Barbieri, 2022). Despite this substantial relevance of sustainability in supply chain management, academics, industry, and policymakers have overlooked and without explicit incorporation of the social dimension of sustainability relative to the economic and environmental dimensions into business operations and supply chain activities (Ashby et al., 2012; Dubey et al., 2017; Tang, 2018; Fernando et al., 2022; Morais and Silvestre, 2022). Many organisations are continuously taking into consideration the social effects of their supply chain activities, and this is evidenced by the increasing number of organizations with certified ISO on social sustainability standards and the adoption of CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) strategies to encourage a more positively impacting supply chain (Ciliberti et al., 2009; Agyemang et al., 2020).

Sustainability in supply chain management is not limited to a particular industry or sector as organisation worldwide are expected to and under intense stakeholders pressures, increased competition at the supply chain level, variations in customer demand patterns to manage their supply chains and profit-making activities in a manner not only meeting the needs of their

stakeholders but to also take responsibility of the social impacts of the activities to people and society beyond internal organisational boundaries extending to distant supply chain partners (Marshall et al., 2015; Mani and Gunasekaran, 2018).

The agricultural sector plays a key role in the development of many countries and acts as a major contributor to economic growth and social development (Janker and Mann, 2020). This is because agriculture is one of the most important sectors for global production and consumption to tackle food security and is a key supplier of raw materials to many industries/sectors (Agyemang et al., 2020). Despite its prominent role in economic growth and contribution to social development, the agricultural sector faces many social sustainability concerns including human rights, work conditions, food quality and safety, supply chain transparency, ethical issues, health and wellbeing, etc., (Mangla et al.2018). Scholars have argued that properly managed social issues have the potential to enhance supply chain performance (Yawar and Seuring, 2017).

These social sustainability issues that characterize the agricultural sector are more evident in distant supply chains particularly those operating in Lower-Middle Income Countries (LMIC). The alarming rate of social sustainability issues has been a centre of discussion by many researchers, policymakers, the media, NGOs, and affected stakeholders, and managers are expected to effectively take measures in the form of implementing and managing sustainable initiatives in supply chains. However, not much work has been done on these supply chains to manage social sustainability. This research examines the implementation of social sustainability in the supply chain in the agricultural sector of a lower-middle-income country to proffer implementable improvements through a socially sustainable SCM framework that will improve the efficiency and performance of the sector on social sustainability in supply chain management.

1.2 Background of the Study

This research work is borne out of the need to understand the strategic implementation activities of agricultural companies on social sustainability initiatives on improving supply chain management from the perspective of Lower-Middle Income Countries (LMICs). The agricultural supply chain faces many sustainability challenges due to the growing demand for global consumption and production. Notwithstanding its significant role in economic growth and social development.

Social sustainability in SCM is the management of social issues in organisations supply chain including internal operations, upstream, downstream, and the community within which the supply chain operates to ensure the long-term development of the organisation (Carter and Rogers, 2008). Social sustainability in the literature overlaps with corporate social responsibility (Mani et al., 2016a). This research considers social sustainability as a major sustainability dimension for organisations and goes beyond the conception that social sustainability is still “a mere philanthropic activity” and supports the assertion that properly managed social sustainability issues have the potential to enhance supply chain performance (Yawar and Seuring, 2017).

Social sustainability in SCM has been especially challenging to organisations in developing economies particularly those in LMICs. The social sustainability issues faced by these organisations may be unique and different from those in developed economies (Mani et al., 2016; Morais and Silvestre, 2022). The extant literature shows a substantial variation between these two contexts in terms of the characterisation of the drivers, barriers, mechanisms, and outcomes of social sustainability in SCM (Jia et al., 2018). These differences are even echoed in how the concept has been predominantly shaped by scholarly work with little attention on analysing specific social sustainability issues and initiatives from the developing economic context, such as poverty concerns related to farmers' income, which are generally considered

as the base of the pyramid issues (Khalid et al. 2015). This supposes a problem where most global supply chains operate through LMICs, but the available social sustainability methods fail to address the relevant social impact issues (Golicic et al., 2019). As such, there is a need for more empirical investigations to understand the dynamics of LMICs (Mani et al., 2018; Sánchez-Flores et al., 2020). Also, to consider different actors, industries, and sizes of firms on social sustainability implementation in supply chains (Silvestre, 2015) to identify trends and pathways to achieve sustainability goals listed under the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). We argue that this is even more imperative for the agricultural sector in LMICs, which receives far less attention.

Alongside this empirical shortage, a limited number of studies in developing countries have considered the use of theoretical contributions to advance understanding of the implementation of the social sustainability framework in supply chains (Mani et al., 2018; Morais and Barbieri, 2022). Notable extant studies have focused on multinational companies' perspectives of implementing practices and standards on social sustainability (Ehrgott et al., 2011; Zorzini et al., 2015) and recently on their suppliers (Huq and Stevenson, 2018). Thus, there seems to be little knowledge of how and to what extent locally-based organizations implement social sustainability practices in their supply chains. The theoretical lenses of Stakeholders Resource Base Views (SRBV) and Strategic Contingency Theory) were used in this research study to explore the implementation of social sustainability in LMICs.

1.3 Problem Statement

As businesses extend the reach of their supply chains to become more responsive, efficient and to sustain competitive advantage, they are increasingly subject to many types of disruptions and catastrophes, with little or no predictability, and with an increasing frequency and high impact (Suresh et al., 2020). Usually, business that suffer a supply chain disruption, experienced 27 percent decline in operating revenue, 13 percent fall in sales revenue, and a 16 percent decrease in return on assets (Baghersad and Zobel, 2021). The general business problem was that poorly manage social issues triggered the growing demand for supply chains to improve social standards, along with strong pressure to avoid substantial economic losses and public backlash has put social sustainability at the centre of supply chain management. The specific problem is that some local companies in the agricultural supply chain lack understanding on the strategic implementation of social sustainability initiatives to improve supply chain performance in LIMCs.

1.4 Research Questions, Aims and Objectives

1.4.1 Research Questions

1. What is the current trend of social sustainability in supply chain management in developing countries?
2. What are the drivers, principles, and barriers to social sustainability and how do these contribute to the operational performance of the entire agricultural supply chain in Cameroon?
3. How are the social sustainability initiatives implemented and managed in the agricultural supply chain with respect to Cameroon?

1.4.2 The Aim of this Research

The research explores the strategic implementation of social sustainability in improving supply chain management in the agriculture sector of a lower-middle-income country and develops and validates a framework for implementing improvement on social sustainability in supply chain management.

The research work differs from previous research as it focuses on the locally based supply chain in the agricultural sector of an LMIC's social sustainability SCM practices and examines the strategic implementation of social sustainability initiatives to enhance supply chain performance.

1.4.3 The Objectives of this Research

1. To critically examine the existing trends of social sustainability in supply chain management in developing countries.
2. Identifying the drivers, principles, and barriers to social sustainability in supply chain management practices in the Cameroonian agricultural sector.
3. To critically examine the implementation and management of social sustainability initiatives in the agricultural supply chain in Cameroon.
4. To analyse the benefits of social sustainability on the entire supply chain.
5. The development and validation of a framework to evaluate and enhance the agricultural sectors' social sustainability SCM efforts in Cameroon.

1.5 Significance of the Study

Researchers and practitioners have developed an interest in achieving supply chain resilience and have become a top priority as organisations contemplate how to anticipate and mitigate disruptions that will surely occur in the constantly evolving business environment. Organisations must develop tools to support the identification and implementation of strategies to achieve this objective (Cohen, 2022). Agribusiness companies/managers need to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of existing tools and devise customized strategies for developing countries to address concerns of social development and to mitigate risk related to financial loss, reputational damage, and stakeholder trust in their supply chains.

The Cameroon government in its bold vision of becoming a NIC (Newly Industrialised Country) by 2035, has effected fundamental socio-economic structural changes to promote endogenous and inclusive development while preserving opportunities for future generations. The government places emphasis on the agricultural sector as the main engine of development with the vision's objective to have a competitive and productive agricultural sector that can sustain growth, ameliorate the social situation, and help to integrate the country into the international scheme while accounting for 23 percent of the countries GDP. This outcome has committed the World Bank group's portfolio to roughly 3 billion dollars. This study will help enhance the agricultural sector's position toward achieving the country's SDGs as it develops various approaches to strategically implement social sustainability with the implication of sustaining growth and improving the social situation in the sector.

Also, there have been calls on LMICs to address sustainability issues in SCM practices where social issues have become a major concern (Mani et al., 2018; Fernando et al., 2022). This will help to understand social sustainability in SCM perspectives to generalize the findings for

theory and practices in Cameroon (Mani and Gunasekaran, 2018; Morais and Silvestre, 2022; Sánchez-Flores et al., 2020).

The study will guide practitioners on the necessary ways to integrate social sustainability into their strategies to be better than their competitors and mitigate risks associated with financial loss, reputational damage and stakeholders' trust. This research explores this important phenomenon in the Cameroonian agricultural sector. Also, the alarming rate of social sustainability issues at various levels is putting corporations under pressure to develop schemes that integrate social sustainability aspects in managing their supply chain. Thus, this research develops a framework that integrates the parameters to improve social sustainability in SCM.

1.6 Overview of the Research Methodology

The study adopts an exploratory multi-case study research design. This is necessary for the investigation because research on social sustainability is underexplored, and its construct is still to be clearly defined and delineated (Yin, 2009; Aberdeen, 2013). The case research method is essential for in-depth analysis of complex real-life issues and to enable a thorough understanding of the phenomenon under investigation (Eisenhardt and Graebner, 2007; Yin, 2009; Hollweck, 2016). This is recommended for social sustainability investigation based on its complex and multifaceted perspectives as well as in the development of conceptual models (Brandenburg et al., 2014; Seuring, 2008). Also, multiple-case research allows the investigator to gain in-depth insight into a phenomenon and a better understanding of the “locally grounded causality” compared to single-case research reducing the researchers' bias (Eisenhardt and Graebner, 2007). A total of 23 Semi-structured interviews were performed to collect data (Yin, 2018). The semi-structured interviews were essential in ensuring internal validity as responses were assessed as comparable across all interviewees. This allowed for flexibility during

interviews and probed the participants for details discussions of sensitive issues while remaining within the limits of social sustainability. Interviews were transcribed and coded using the qualitative data analysis software NVivo10. Case selection was carefully done and considered the nature of the research, as well as following the logic of literal and/or theoretical replication (Yin, 2013). To avoid bias in case selection, purposefully varied case situations need to be linked (Yin, 2009). Moreover, Benbasat et al. (1987) emphasis the need for organisational characteristics for case selection when investigating organisational phenomena. Once each interview was achieved, a summary detailing the main point specified by each respondent was prepared. Afterward, the interview for each was examined closely with archival data to identify themes before cross-case analysis with other cases. For reliability and validity, the researcher used participants who represent various positions demonstrating an understanding of the subject of interest. Coupled with that, respondents were provided copies of their transcribed interviews and findings to get feedback ensuring the representativeness and validity of the data (Yin, 2003).

1.7 Thesis Structure

This thesis is made up of 6 chapters presented as follows: Chapter 1 introduces the study by providing background, SMART questions, the aim of the study, objectives, rationale, and structure of the thesis. Chapter 2 examines the literature by dividing the chapter into two parts. Part 1 focused on the body of knowledge on sustainability, SSCM specifically on social sustainability. Part 2 describes the context of why the study was selected. Chapter 3 presents the various philosophical and methodological choices and gives a justification for adopting the exploratory multi-case study research design for the investigation and the qualitative data collection. Chapter 4 gives an account of the analysis and present the findings. Chapter 5

examines the results to address the research question which were raised in the introductory chapter. Chapter 6 summarises the main findings and elaborates on the contributions of this research to the body of knowledge and practice followed by the research limitations and recommendations for future research.

Chapter Two – Literature Review

2.0 Introduction to Literature Review

This chapter is divided into two parts. Part 1 discourses on the body of knowledge on supply chain management, supply chain sustainability, the Tripple Bottom Line, a specific focus on social sustainability in SCM, relevant theories, the conceptual framework, and the potential corporate social responsibility. Part 2 describes the context and why it was selected for the study.

Part one – Conceptual Underpinning

2.1.1 Supply Chain Management

Operating in today's business environment necessitates companies to become much more involved with their upstream, midstream, and downstream partners (Ahi and Searcy 2012). With globalisation expanding the market boundaries and increased competition, companies are subjected to be good at several things to satisfy customers' demands at their desired price. Businesses must take into consideration “where materials come from; how supplier's products are designed, produced, transported; and customer value to the product” (Wisner et al., 2016). This might be attributed to the fact that businesses nowadays compete as a supply chain rather than an independent entity (Lambert et al., (1998). Over three decades now, many businesses have become aware of the advantages associated with a well-managed supply chain. The business increases the practice of horizontal and vertical integration to minimise the cost and management challenges of such diverse business units (Hugos, 2018). Businesses especially agricultural entities focus more on core capabilities through creating strategic partnerships with their supply chain actors in the value chain (Wisner et al., 2016). This collaborative style of

doing business (SCM) in purchasing, producing, and distributing goods and services has become the new dawn for companies to stay successful.

Supply chain management is an essential instrument for the success of many agricultural enterprises through the efficient utilization of resources (Stadtler et al., 2015). The growing interest for companies to work collaboratively is driven by several factors such as the rapid change in information and communication technologies (Gunasekaran and Ngai, 2011). This facilitates globalisation which increases firms' competition, customer demands with specific needs, revenue growth, managing relationships, improving overall performance, and sustainability concerns (Pagell and Wu, 2009; Stevens and Johnson, 2016).

To capture the understanding of SCM, it is necessary to define what a supply chain is.

Lambert et al. (1998) defined supply chain as:

“The alignment of firms that bring products or services to market.”

To Chopra and Meindl (2015):

“a supply chain consists of all stages involved, directly or indirectly, in fulfilling a customer request. The supply chain not only includes the manufacturer and suppliers, but also transporters, warehouses, retailers, and customers themselves.”

“A supply chain is a network of facilities and distribution options that performs the functions of procurement of materials, the transformation of these materials into intermediate and finished products, and the distribution of these finished products to customers.” (Ganeshan and Harrison, 1995).

The above definitions portray the things influencing the activities of the supply chain to achieve the desired results. Gibson et al. (2005) stated that “the discipline of supply chain

management is going through a maturation process of reaching consensus agreement on what is included, and what is not included”. The scholars in their survey trying to understand the perception of the role of supply chain management as purely strategic or activity-focused, found out that a greater percentage of the participants perceived the role of SCM to be a mix of strategy and activity while a smaller percent considered it to be either strategic or activity focused. In the same direction, Ganeshan and Harrison (2002) considered the understanding of SCM from strategic and operational perspectives.

The Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals (CSCMP) defines supply chain management as:

“As the planning and management of all activities involved in sourcing and procurement, conversion, and all logistics management activities. Importantly, it also includes coordination and collaborations with channel partners, which can be suppliers, intermediaries, third-party service providers, and customers”.

The Association for Operations Management (APICS) defines SCM as:

“The design, planning, execution, control, and monitoring of supply chain activities to create net value, building a competitive infrastructure, leveraging worldwide logistics, synchronizing supply with demands, and measuring performance globally”.

Mentzer et al. (2001) defined SCM as:

“Supply chain management is the systematic, strategic coordination of the traditional business functions and the tactics across these business functions within a particular company and across businesses within the supply chain, to improve the long-term performance of the individual companies and the supply chain as a whole”.

Others such as Hervani et al. (2005)

“SCM is the coordination and management of a complex network of activities involved in delivering a finished product to the end-user or customer”.

La Londe and Masters (1994)

“The strategy of applying integrated logistics management to all the elements of a supply chain”.

Logistics and SCM are often used interchangeably to infer the same thing. Logistics is limited within the boundaries of a single organisation while SCM goes beyond all activities of logistic management (planning of sourcing and procurement, distribution, maintenance, and inventory management). SMCs also include networks of all the companies engaged in coordinating activities to deliver a product or service to the market (Cooper et al., (1997). Cooper et al., (1997) described SCM as *“the integration of business processes from end-user through original suppliers that provide products, services and information that add value for customers”*. Stadtler (2004) and Hugos (2018) followed the same view. All definitions aim to strategize the coordination of goods- and services-related activities among supply chain functions for higher efficiency, product quality, and customer value at the lowest possible cost while improving the overall performance of the organisations.

Given the challenges in improving performance, the collaborative relationship between upstream and downstream partners is inevitable to facilitate the dynamic flow of material, capital, and information within and across the diverse business units. Linton et al. (2007) stated that a *“critical evaluation of supply chains is necessary for businesses to fully comprehend the emerging values of sustainability and benefit therein as more businesses are now concentrating on optimal operations along the entire supply chain and not just on a specific aspect of the business”*. With globalisation, many production plants continue to

expand their base beyond their state boundaries to create customer value and increase the profit margin (Seuring and Muller, 2008). This globalised nature of production, sourcing, distribution, storage, and consumption beyond firms' boundaries makes it challenging for proper control, monitoring, and accountability of the impacts born from firms and their supply chain (Kong and Mont 2012). There is a growing concern for the environmental and social impact of firms and their supply chains. A growing number of consumers and stakeholders are demanding firms and their supply chains act in an ethically and socially responsible manner (Ashby et al., 2012; Wisner et al., 2016). This includes "attention to how the firms are hiring and training employees, how they are harvesting plants and other materials, how their activities impact the environment, and what sort of sustainability policies are being utilized" (Wisner et al., 2016). Firms are held responsible for the unsustainable practices of their supply chains especially lead firms (La Londe and Master 1994). Sustainability has become a key element in managing supply chains as this requires organizations to become more transparent in terms of disclosing their sources of supply, focusing on greener and humanising their supply chains (Sarkis et al. 2011 and Linton et al. 2007).

2.1.2 Supply Chain Sustainability (SCS)

While sustainability has become a parameter of interest across the globe, supply chain sustainability remains a difficult concept to explain (Cooper and Stanley, 2015). These variations are often likened to policies, stakeholders, and by the willingness of organisations to adopt practices that support supply chain sustainability (MIT CTL and CSCMP, 2020).

Over the last decades, studies on sustainability have shown that businesses are increasingly incorporating sustainability practices into their SCM strategies. The term "sustainability" can

be traced back to the early 18th century in which it was referred to the “the practice of never harvesting more than the forest can regenerate”. With the emergence of ecology as a scientific discipline, the concept of sustainability was redefined as “the ability of an ecosystem to maintain its essential purposes and functions over time” (MIT CTL and CSCMP, 2020). In 1987 sustainability gained increasing popularity with the issuing of the “Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our Common Future: The Concept of Sustainable Growth” known as the Brundtland Commissions Report. The issues defined sustainability as “the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (Brundtland, 1987). The definition places emphasis on “needs” versus “limitations”, which is critical in the sustainability debate.

Although the reality of business sustainability is incontestable, the early conceptualisation of business sustainability is subject to reductive interpretations that are the interchangeable use of “sustainability” and “environmental” sustainability (Martins and Pato, 2019). Integrating sustainability concerns into supply chain management in literature can be traced back to the term “Green supply chain management” (GrSCM). Srivastava (2007) defined GrSCM as “integrating environmental thinking into supply-chain management, including product design, material sourcing, and selection, manufacturing processes, delivery of the final product to the consumers as well as end-of-life management of the product after its useful life”. Despite been the most prevalent definition of GrSCM, other scholars, reflected on what the different ways of “integrating environmental thinking into supply-chain management” means (Ahi and Searcy, 2013). They all showed that economic results (the “needs”) are limited by, or at the very least have to take into account the environmental impact aspect (the “limitations”).

A more critical focus in the understanding of the concept of business sustainability in the supply chain came under the term “triple bottom line” (see 2.2.1). In “Cannibals with Forks: The Triple Bottom Line of 21st Century Business”, integrating the 3Ps to imply “people, planet

and profits” Elkington highlighted that organisation should not limit their focus only to the traditional financial profit and loss, but should also take into consideration the social and the environmental bottom lines (Elkington, 1997). The “first - people's bottom line - measures the level of social responsibility of the organisation, whereas the second - planet's bottom line - records the environmental impact of its operations. This three-pillar perspective became a synonym of a more comprehensive approach to business sustainability”. Business sustainability in supply chains goes beyond the interacting relationship of these three pillars to address areas of improvement or bring changes to the entire system. Linton et al. (2007) commented: “Sustainability in supply chain management has the prospective capability to affect future government policy, current production operations, and identify new business models”. Svensson (2007) traced the relationship between supply chains and sustainability to features such as actors, activities, resources, and interfaces; like interaction, coordination, cooperation, and competition. Winter and Knemeyer (2011) support this view by emphasizing the existence of the relationship between sustainability and supply chain management as activities of sustainability traverse organisational growth, profitability, relationships, and environmental consideration. This inter-relationship between sustainability and SCM has not always been recognised in some disciplines since earlier studies on supply chain and sustainability did not put much emphasis on the subject matter (Carter and Easton, 2011).

Scholars like Carter and Jennings (2004) found the integration of this isolated concept under the holistic term “Corporate Social Responsibility” (see section 2.6). These were identified as the aspects of sustainability on SCM as logistic social responsibility (LSR) and purchasing social responsibility (PSR). The main characteristics of CSR found in different initiatives include voluntary activities, managing external factors, stakeholder management, alignment of social and economic responsibilities, considering practices and values, and extending CSR activities beyond philanthropy to instrumentality (Carroll, 2016).

Integrating sustainability into supply chain management will avoid being considered an add-on where all future studies on SCM are SSCM studies. Considering the relevance of sustainability to become a core part of SCM, organizations should add sustainability to SCM or redefine SCM completely. Sustainability in SCM reforms many supply chains as organizations continue to integrate it into their business activities.

2.1.2.1 The Triple Bottom Line (TBL)

Elkington in 1994, framed the TBL and incorporated profit, planet, and people as contributing parameters to the overall performance of organisational sustainability. The idea behind the TBL is that true sustainability simultaneously balances an organisations' economic, environmental, and social goals (Elkington, 2004, 2013). The following paragraphs review the literature on arguments supporting and disparaging the concept. The consideration of TBL is an appropriate framework for this study.

Figure 1. Triple Bottom Line (Elkington, 1994)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

In their work “a critique of the TBL,” Milne et al. (2007) argued the TBL concept does not promote sustainability and emphasised the definitional issues of sustainability. They strongly opposed the TBL being used interchangeably with sustainability. It seems that organisations confuse the reporting practices of the TBL despite being an essential condition for sustainability.

Milne et al. (2013) argued on the uncertainties created by the concept, the aspects of the definition, and variations in the measures for integration thereby justifying the TBL concept to be “fuzzy” and can be interpreted differently. That is another reason why the concept is suited for this research using a case-based approach on differing organizations with different strategies.

Another concern with the TBL is that it has a reporting background i.e., “bottom line” and most critics have been directed to its conception as a reporting tool and lack of rigour. For example, Norman and Macdonald (2004) stressed that the issues of measurement and the aggregation of non-financial impacts in reports is a big challenge i.e., “*if you can't measure it, you can't manage it*” and because companies can “*cherry pick*” what to report (Milne and Gray, 2013). According to Kolk (2003), such reporting challenges make sustainability a mere “*window-dressing*”. To others, TBL is used as a tool to enhance legitimacy in responding to pressure from stakeholders (Sridhar, 2012). Organisation come to disclose nothing more than basic information about each bottom line without integration (Isil and Hernke, 2017). Social responsibility and ethical business practices are important aspects of corporate governance and any attempt enabling them to be more transparent to stakeholders is welcomed. Therefore, any apparent and effective measures of social sustainability are considered to be important for the development of solid supply chains (Norman and Macdonald, 2004).

They further argued it is difficult to come up with an appropriate methodology for reaching a definite social bottom line based on fundamental philosophical grounds. This is attributed primarily to weighting social impacts which are difficult to measure. Also, reaching a consensus for accepted standards in the same way as accounting could not be reached because of the complex nature and subjectivity involved. Because it is inevitable to assign a monetary value to social and environmental aspects (Norman and Macdonald, 2004). He further argued that firms should pay attention to these facts rather than add them to the main bottom line. Therefore, they consider the TBL to be: “a *good old-fashioned single bottom line plus vague commitments to social and environmental concerns*” enabling organisations to shy away from commitments. Pointing to the fact that there is no yearly data to compare rivals with no standards in assessing the progress. Thus, the triple bottom-line reporting simply allows companies to pick what to report that might be of interest to stakeholders. This can be modified yearly to reflect compatibility and paint a good picture for stakeholders. This is a major challenge for the concept with little or no improvements in the past 20 years. Therefore, environmental, and social accounting are still considered to be “*embryonic*”. Elkington (1994) commented on this as “*the metrics are still evolving*” (p.72). which still appears to be the case today.

Notwithstanding the critics of no social bottom-line metrics, different aspects have been developed to measure social impact using a set of standard indicators in a relatively objective way. These can be measures audited, reported, and benchmarked. They provide some defense to counter the arguments against the TBL. However, this study considers the TBL as an approach used by organisation for addressing sustainability taking into consideration financial gains, environmental integrity, and social equity in organisational strategies (Milne and Gray, 2013). That is to a larger part encompasses both shareholders with their as compared to a reporting tool.

Freeman (1984) argued it is not enough to concentrate on a single bottom without a consideration of other stakeholder's interests. However, the TBL is an essential way to understand sustainability, but there are no metrics that can quantify the prepositions. However, analysis can be done to identify and merge related and important aspects.

The significance behind this topic is that focusing on financial gains will only lead to short-term success (Dylick and Hockerts, 2002). While sustainability requires a focus on all three dimensions to meet long-term success. Though it is always not advisable to investigate the dimensions in isolation when something is a contributing factor, it is important to investigate each dimension separately where applicable. To 'catch up' with the economic and environmental dimensions, the social dimension must be investigated in isolation and later reunited with the other dimensions (Zorzini et al., 2015). This is backed by the fact that the social aspect has been overlooked and requires more focus necessitating a separate investigation.

Assessing social impacts helps to enhance the social performance of corporations. A good socially performing corporation always enjoys long-term profitability (Norman and MacDonald, 2004). Corporations are obliged to disclose their social performance stakeholders and demonstrate transparently how well they have performed in certain areas. TBL Advocates argued that environmental and social performance can be evaluated objectively and the outcomes can be used to enhance ecological and social performance. With this additional reporting on social and environmental dimensions, organizations are sure to expect improved financial bottom line in the long term. Even though the TBL has been greatly criticized, critics have yet to provide a way forward (Milne et al., 2005). Those critiques about TBL reporting are justified especially when looking for similar data from other organizations. Other aspects should be incorporated into the TBL reporting like evaluating the values and practices of an organization towards attaining its financial, ecological, and social goals. These aspects do not

consider measures for social sustainability, but they are focused on areas that require TBL reporting.

Social and environmental dimensions are not beneficial for profit and they are confusing due to the lack of a quantifiable methodological approach (Norman and MacDonald, 2004). This concludes the proposition that the Global Reporting Initiatives (GRI) framework lacks clarity on the subject matter (Milne et al., 2007). Notwithstanding the critics, there are attempts been made to counter the critics. The TBL provides an appropriate framework for this study as it can be developed within the supply chain management context (for example, developing supplier management initiatives relates to one of the many aspects of the TBL). There is evidence that supports its usefulness for profit and as a theory. it is flexible and provides a good basis for analysis. It is of public interest as it takes into consideration stakeholder interest. Moreover, TBL has been adopted by firms in their reporting and sustainability agenda.

2.1.2.2 Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM)

The literature identifies different definitions that have been used to describe the concept of sustainable supply chain management. One key aspect in these definitions is “sustainable development” in SCM. Thus, sustainability is highly significant within the supply chain as its processes can influence positively or negatively the three integrated dimensions (3Ps) of sustainability. Based on its significance, Pagell and Wu (2010) commented that: “To be truly sustainable, a supply chain would produce a profit over an extended period while preserving natural or social systems”. However, some supply chains in the sustainable aspect perform far better as compared to others irrespective of the industry. This argument therefore supports the assertions that business could survive over an extended period.

Seuring and Müller (2008) defined SSCM as:

“The management of material, information and capital flows as well as cooperation among companies along the supply chain while taking goals from all three dimensions of sustainable development, i.e., economic, environmental and social, into account which are derived from customer and stakeholder requirements.”

Despite the increased popularity of the above definition in SSCM, Ahi and Searcy (2013) advanced this definition following their evaluation of 12 SSCM definitions resulting in a newly proposed definition. Their definition integrates the concept of procurement and supports development in the long run.

Ahi and Searcy (2013) define SSCM as:

“The creation of coordinated supply chains through the voluntary integration of economic, environmental, and social considerations with key inter-organizational business systems designed to efficiently and effectively manage the material, information, and capital flows associated with the procurement, production, and distribution of products or services to meet stakeholder requirements and improve the profitability, competitiveness, and resilience of the organisation over the short- and long-term”.

This definition is an advancement of SSCM as it stresses the need to integrate a long-term focus, an aspect mentioned by only four (thirty-three percent) of prior definitions of SSCM (Pagell and Wu, 2010). Carter and Easton (2011) further identified strategy, risk management, transparency, and organisational culture as four enabling aspects of SSCM included in these definitions besides the 3Ps. According to Elkington, corporate sustainability should “not just focus on the economic value that they can add, but also on the environmental and social value that they add – or destroy” Elkinton (2013). Thus, Carter and Rogers (2008) defined SSCM as:

“The strategic, transparent integration and achievement of an organization’s social, environmental, and economic goals in the systemic coordination of key inter-organizational business processes for improving the long-term economic performance of the individual company and its supply chain”.

Krause et al. (2009) in an editorial review revealed that an organisations sustainability progress is relative to its suppliers’ network (Elkington,1994). The integration of sustainability with supply chain management extends far beyond the start of raw material processing to final delivery to end users. It includes the initial process of product design to the entire product life cycle to avoid ecological impacts during and after product use to eliminate waste and resource depletion (Linton et al., 2007). Thus, Hassini *et al.* (2012) defined SSCM as *“the management of supply chain operations, resources, information, and funds to maximise the supply chain profitability while minimising the environmental impacts and maximising the social well-being”*. Environmental sustainability practices include green products and process design, the adoption of environmental materials and pollution control, the adoption of green procurement practices, the circular economy, and shouldering higher levels of environmental responsibility (Heydari et al., 2020; Klassen, 2001), Govindan et al., 2021). SSCM involves the management of all activities of the supply chain and also includes the reverse supply chain (Ashby et al. 2012). Described as *“the process where a producer accepts previously shipped manufactured parts or products for remanufacturing, recycling or proper disposition”* (Sarkis et al., (2013). Social sustainability overlaps with corporate social responsibility (CSR) and addresses the well-being of human beings and society through the management of social resources (Sarkis et al., 2010); poverty alleviation, respecting justice, human rights, and employee welfare and work transparency (Krause et al., 2009). Carroll (1991) developed the pyramid of CSR – a hierarchy of economic, legal, ethical, and other voluntary activities and responsibilities for organisations to support stakeholders and the society in which they operate.

Conceptualising sustainability with the TBL allows for assessing social sustainability independently or as an integrated part of sustainability. This is essential because research on economic and environmental sustainability largely dominates scientific research on social dimensions (Huq et al., 2016; Mani et al., 2016; Fernando et al., 2022; Morais and Silvestre, 2022).

Figure 2 Sustainable Supply Chain Management (Carter and Rogers, 2008)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

The SSCM framework by Carter and Easton (2011) emphasised strategy, risk management, transparency, and organisational culture to be enablers of SSCM. Strategy because sustainability supply chain management initiatives take into consideration corporate sustainability in strategies. Transparency allows for traceability and visibility along the entire

operations of the supply chain. Risk and culture are crucial for enhancing organisational reputation.

The intersection of environmental and social aspects in Figure 2.2 was labeled “good” to imply such endeavours are socially irresponsible unless integrated into an organisation’s overall objectives (Carter and Easton, 2011). However, the three dimensions were given equal significance in developing the SSCM framework, but the social dimension has not gained popularity relative to the environmental and economic dimensions that have been more investigated. Thus, research on this thesis is trying to be built around the social sustainability dimension.

2.1.3 Social sustainability

a. Definition of social sustainability

While social sustainability remains a major sustainability dimension, the SCM field continues to show an increasing interest in investigating social issues in different industry areas, geographic regions, and technologies (Golicic et al., 2019). Unsurprisingly, the literature has not provided a standard definition for social sustainability in SCM (Nakamba et al., 2017). Nonetheless, a body of knowledge is developing attempting to describe what constitutes social sustainability in SCM from several perspectives (Yawar and Seuring, 2015; Golicic et al., 2019). For instance, Sarkis et al. (2010) consider social sustainability from the standpoint of social resources as “the management of social resources including people’s skills, and abilities, institutions, relationships, and social values”.

Awaysheh and Klassen (2010) understood from the perspective of management practices addressing both negative and positive aspects related to social sustainability that “Management practices that affect how a firm contributes to the development of human potential or protects

people from harm, thereby capturing both positive and negative aspects, respectively”. Croom et al. (2018) categorised these management practices into two: (a) Basic practices refer to workers' safety, welfare, and health in SCM and (b) advanced practices redesign the supply chain and focus on the product-related and process-related aspects that are beneficial to the different stakeholders involved. In addition, Klassen and Vereecke (2012) mentioned “social management capabilities” that “social sustainability encompasses three levels of stakeholders (who), focusing on the evolving set of social concerns for which the firm has influence in the supply chain (which issues), and involving management capabilities that respond to these concerns by mitigating risk or enhancing customer value (how).”

Others have considered the concept of stakeholders in defining social sustainability extending beyond the supply chain boundaries. For example, Chardine-Baumann and Botta-Genoulaz (2014) “social conditions of work (employment, respect for social dialogue, health, and safety, development of human resources); human rights (child and forced labour, freedom of association, discrimination); social commitment (involvement in the local community, education, culture and technological development, job creation, health care, social investment); customer issues (marketing and information, health and safety, protection of privacy, access to essential services); and business practices (fight against corruption, fair trade, and promotion of social responsibility in the sphere of influence)”. Wood (1991) as: “The product and process aspects of firms the impact human safety, welfare, and wellness”. Freeman (1984) identified three levels of stakeholders concerning social sustainability issues. First at the internal levels for the firm’s operation (workforce diversity and safety management), second at the inter-firm levels concerned with external interactions directly linked to the firm based on strong economic relations (buying firms, suppliers, consumers, and end-users), and thirdly those with less strong economic relation (society, regulators, and NGOs) (Klassen and Vereecke, 2012). Hence, the role played by stakeholders cannot be denied

in influencing organisations toward the management of social sustainability behaviour (Sodhi, 2015).

Also, social sustainability in SCM can be understood from a dual perspective both at the individual and the organisation levels (Winter and Knemyer, 2013). Marshall et al. (2015) extends this dual perspective to process-facing and market-facing approaches. Shibin et al. (2018) suggested the concept of “frugal innovation” in defining social sustainability in the supply chain. Meanwhile Ivory and Brooks (2018) proposed “the strategic agility capabilities of sensitivity, collective commitment, and resource fluidity”. More recently, a study by Golicic et al. (2019) on the global understanding of the meaning of social sustainability in supply chain management should take into consideration “the different levels of economic development, but also within the levels as well. Culture, community, and whether basic human needs are met all weigh into the perspectives of what this concept is and should entail; a broad, contingent approach”.

From these definitions, it can be pointed out that social sustainability in the supply chain entails management practices, capabilities, stakeholders, and resources geared towards human potential and welfare within and extend beyond supply chain boundaries to include communities while taking into consideration economic situations and cultures using a broad contingent approach.

However, this supposes the complexity surrounding the concept as a standard definition is yet to be reached. This complexity is further advanced according to Matos and Silvestre (2013) by its ambiguity, multidimensionality, and the conflicting interests of several variables like stakeholders. It is also argued that most of the definitions assumed perspectives from developed economies that do not fit into this society (developing economies) that sustain them nor represent the nature of the global supply chain (Sánchez-Flores et al., 2020). These

societies are characterised by environmental uncertainties, business complexity, and growing social concerns. Thus, when practices from developed economies are adopted in these countries without an understanding of the context it only becomes more challenging (Golicic et al., 2019; Sánchez-Flores et al., 2020; Morais and Silvestre, 2022). Notwithstanding the material circumstances surrounding the concept, the social sustainability issues appear to be immaterial and therefore quantitatively, challenging to evaluate (Lehtonen, 2004).

b. Social Dimensions

The literature reveals increased research on social sustainability dimensions. A study by Bubicz et al. (2019) found that studies are focused on four social aspects developed from the UN Global Reporting Initiative Framework (GRI) which include: labour conditions, human rights, society, and product responsibility across the supply chain. Others have argued the lack of universally validated social aspects (Mani et al., 2015, Nakamba et al., 2017, Golicic et al., 2019). The measures of social sustainability supply chain practices are highly “contextual, time-dependent, dynamic, and emergent” (Yawar and Seuring, 2015). Several scholars have followed this perspective for example, Awayshe and Klassen (2010) developed a framework for the assessment of supplier socially responsible practices. Their study was conducted from industries across the North American economies (US and Canada) to capture social aspects of human rights, labour practices, and codes of conduct. Others like Shafiq et al. (2014) developed a similar framework on social sustainability aspects on the multiple dimensions of socially responsible practices conducted across industries in Canada. The work of Marshal et al. (2015) on framework measurement of environmental and social supply chain management practices identified social dimensions of (equity, safety, health and welfare, philanthropy, ethics, and human rights).

Within the developing economic context, for example, Mani et al., (2016a) framed a practitioner framework to measure social sustainability covering the entire supply chain. Their framework identified six dimensions of social sustainability that are: “equity, ethics, health and welfare, human rights, philanthropy, and safety”. Lu et al. (2012) in their study on social supplier development, identified measures such as ethical codes of conduct, employees, investors, community, and suppliers as social measures. Others for example, Jorgensen (2007) used the life cycle assessment, to categorise social sustainability into four groups which aligned with the GRI proposed to categorise that is: “human rights, work practices and decent work conditions, society, and product-related responsibility”. In their review to identify studies in SCM that focused on the subject, Yawar and Seuring (2015), identified various groups of social sustainability that are: “working conditions; child labour; human rights; health and safety; development of minorities; inclusion of disabled or marginalized persons; and gender”. Similar studies have identified safety, wages, and labour practices (Mani et al., 2015).

It is evident from the review that there is a lack of valid social sustainability construct in SCM in LMICs particularly those of Africa. The absence of social aspects construct in LMICs geographic context is not surprising in the literature due to few empirical studies in the context (Denu et al., 2023). Scholars have attributed this to (for example) Mani et al. (2015) managers within the context of LMICs lack adequate knowledge and understanding of the social dimension not to mention its measures and how it can be implemented and managed. To others such as Ashby et al. (2012), Mani et al. (2016), and Jia et al. (2018), social sustainability investigations from LMICs are still at the nascent stage and underexplored due to clarity in concept and specific dimensions of social sustainability, particularly evident in manufacturing and operations supply chains.

Recent studies show social aspect of poverty alleviation is emphasised in LMICs (see Table 2.1). This supposes many organisations especially from LMICs have started considering

elements of human wellness or considered poverty alleviation as a priority in their supply chains.

Table 1 Validated Social Dimensions.

Authors	Title	Context	Social Dimensions
Awaysheh and Klassen (2010)	The impact of supply chain structure on the use of supplier socially responsible practices	North America (developed economy)	Human rights Labour practices Codes of conduct Social audits
Lu et al. (2012)	Socially responsible supplier development: construct development and measurement validation	Emerging economy manufacturing industry (China)	Codes of ethics, employees, investors, community, and suppliers
Mani et al. (2016)	Supply chain social sustainability for developing nations: Evidence from India	Emerging economy manufacturing industry (India)	Human rights, equity, health and welfare, safety, ethics, and Philanthropy

Denu et al. (2023)	Social sustainability performance: development and validation measures in the context of emerging African economies	Lower middle-income country in the African manufacturing and service industry (Ghana)	Community, equity, poverty alleviation, human rights, ethics, regulatory enforcement, and employees
--------------------	---	---	---

Other studies like the work of Hajjar et al (20219), found organisations are also given priority to ameliorate rural livelihoods. While poverty is considered a global challenge to achieving sustainable development goals, it has also led to social exclusion and inequality especially in developing countries (Hall et al., 2011).

c. Sources of Analysis of the Social Dimension

The literature on the analysis of the social dimension suggests different approaches have been used. The most used approaches include frameworks development (Mani et al., 2016; Denu et al., 2023); development of CRS practices; SSCM - identification of social indicators; sustainability reports and standards; Social Life Cycle Assessment; Social Footprints (Bubicz et al., 2019). This might suggest a major challenge as this shows there is a lack of consensus amongst researchers on the best approach used for assessing the social dimension as there is no specific approach to assess the social dimension.

The sustainability supply chain management concept has been well integrated towards addressing sustainability issues in supply chains, the literature argues such analysis only considers part of the supply chain entities or that these practices are yet to be incorporated by

firms in both their internal and external operations (Barbosa-Povoa et al., 2018). Scholars have emphasized social responsibility to be a major driver towards achieving economic performance in the long run when explored within the context of CRS practices, CRS must be viewed from a holistic perspective highlighting the significance of embedding these practices in the whole organisation including extended parts of the organisation (Perry et al., 2015; Hsueh, 2014). The social life cycle assessment has been used as a methodology to assess and report on the positive and negative social impacts in the product life cycle (Jorgensen, 2007). Other approaches like social footprints are also explored to identify social dimensions.

d. Social Supply Chain Entities

To the integration of social sustainability analysis in the supply chain, the literature suggested different entities across the supply chain have been included to analyse social sustainability in the supply chain that is “all forward supply chain entities (supplier-producer-consumer); supplier, production/service provider; consumer; and Reverse logistic (Govindan et al., 2020; Bubicz et al., 2019). The lead firm is also included and described as the entity that manages the whole supply chain and can be a supplier, producer, or service provider. The literature emphasizes the lead firms' management of social sustainability in the supply chain, the social aspect of supplier selection and responsible purchasing have been addressed upstream (Ehrgott et al., 2011; Sarkis et al., 2012; Mani et al., 2017).

The literature also mentioned social aspects in reverse logistics entities. For instance, in their developed model for measuring performance indicators of reverse logistics social responsibility using the TBL, Nikolaou et al., (2013), the authors considered social dimensions of labour practices, human rights, product responsibility, and society. The authors further are reverse logistic when considering has been done so isolation rather than an integrated part of the supply chain whereas the entire supply chain should shoulder the

responsibility. Researchers have stated integrating both forward and reverse logistics in supply chain management research (Suduarto et al., 2016). This is a necessary advancement as close collaboration between supply chain partners is important to be sustainable (Bubicz et al., 2019). Though the consumer level is emphasised in the literature, more research is needed in the area, particularly in developing countries where limited work has been done.

2.1.3.1 Drivers of Social Sustainability in Supply Chain Management

Drivers are considered an important aspect that urges companies to go after certain goals. In supply chains, drivers are major indicators enabling organisations to commit resources towards sustainability initiatives to pursue more sustainable business practices. Silvestre (2016) emphasised: “It is important to understand the reason why supply chains implement sustainability initiatives and pursue more sustainable business practices in terms of the main drivers behind these actions. Understanding this “why” question is critical for the development and practices of supply chain management”.

Extensive literature has been developed on the drivers for the implementation of social sustainability practices in SCM from different perspectives (Nakamba et al., 2017; Govindan et al., 2021). Mani and Gunasekaran (2018) argued that the adoption of social sustainability practices in supply chains is influenced by two factors. On the one hand, companies believe that keeping a good stakeholder relationship (stakeholder management capabilities) might increase economic gains. On the other hand, companies turn to pursue these practices in confirmation of norms and stakeholders’ expectations (government and other external stakeholders) on how operations should be performed. Both motivations are crucial for competitive advantage and differentiation and others have considered the drivers to an internal – external perspectives. Yin (2017) and Morais and Silvestre (2018) constituted internal drivers

to include ethical corporate culture, top management commitment, and external drivers to (increase profits, competitive edge, market share, and normative social pressure).

Reviews by Morali and Searcy (2013), Nakamba et al. (2017) Kumar and Rahman (2017) found stakeholder pressure is the most highlighted driver in the literature. Other drivers include customer pressure, competitive pressure, and the commitment of top management, civil society organizations, employees, and the government. The role stakeholders play in social sustainability has been greatly documented by research. Stakeholder pressure is considered a major driver that might push organizations to adopt social sustainability practices (Mani et al., 2015; Mani and Gunasekaran, 2018; Fernando et al., 2022). The role played by internal stakeholders in influencing social sustainability adoption is emphasized in different studies. (Gimenez and Tachizawa, 2012). Ehrgott et al. (2011) showed how purchasing managers influence the adoption of social standards by suppliers. Similarly, Huq et al. (2014) highlighted the competitive pressure for skilled labour shortages influences companies in the Bangladeshi Garment industry to adopt social standards to avoid employing migration to other sectors. Zorzini et al. (2015) found top management's moral values along with the company's ethical culture are important drivers and assert an organization's commitment to a sustainability culture as part of its competitive strategy influences the adoption of sustainability practices (Marshall et al., 2015).

Similar studies have revealed external pressure from stakeholders drives the adoption of social standards such as trade unions and the media (Write and Brown, 2013), customers and competitive pressure (Mani et al., 2015), pressure from the local community (Nakamba et al., 2017), and institutional pressure (Yin, 2017). A study by Huq et Stevenson (2018), found that institutional pressure might not always lead to the adoption of social standards, others found government pressure to be a significant driver (Govinda et al., 2021). Recently, Mani and Gunasekaran (2018) proposed customer pressure, regulatory compliance, corporate culture,

and external pressure from stakeholders as the four main forces influencing the adoption of social sustainability practices in supply chains. Further studies have found incentive actions (for instance tax incentives and profit sharing) Kumar and Rahma (2017), resource and information sharing, audition, and monitoring suppliers, and strong partnership joint developmental plans (Govindan et al., 2021).

Additionally, recent studies have revealed that the integration of systematic practices that may involve remodelling organisations processes and operations such as the integration of innovative strategies that are lean and agile enables the adoption of social sustainability standards (Mann et al. 2017; Nath and Agrawal, 2020).

In the literature, although scholars have made significant efforts on what influences social sustainability practices, Nakamba et al., (2017) and Köksal et al. (2017), it is evident that regulatory forces are important drivers in developed and emerging economies. However, the relationships between social sustainability adoption and cultural values and normative forces are more significant in developed countries where the sustainability culture is well-developed in the societies (Marshall et al. 2015; Nakamba et al., 2017). This might suggest a need to explore these factors in developing economies, particularly those in Africa.

Table 2 Drivers for extrinsic and intrinsic motivated social initiatives within supply chains

Drivers	Description	Studies
<i>Extrinsically Motivated Initiatives (i.e., driven by financial rewards of social sustainability)</i>		
Competition	Focal company launches social initiative in the supply chain because competitors are undertaking social/sustainable initiatives	Dubey et al., (2016)
Market	Focal company launches social initiative in the supply chain because of pressure from customers willing to buy socially responsible/sustainable goods and services.	Klassen and Vereecke, (2012), Marshall et al., (2015) Sancha et al., (2016)

Regulations	Focal company launches social initiative in the supply chain because of changing laws and regulations	Marshall et al., (2015), Dubey et al., (2016)
Reputation and competitive advantage	Focal company launches social initiative in the supply chain to achieve enhanced reputation through marketing campaigns and the search for competitive advantage	Klassen and Vereecke, (2012), Grosvold et al., (2014)
Secondary stakeholders	Focal company launches social initiative in the supply chain because of pressure from secondary stakeholders (e.g., media, NGOs, financial institutions)	Awaysheh and Klassen (2010); Hall and Matos (2010); Yawar and Seuring, (2015)
<i>Intrinsically Motivated Initiatives (i.e., driven by ethical considerations and values)”</i>		
Ethics and Values	Focal company launches social initiative in the supply chain because of decision-makers’ ethical standards and/or organizational values	Beske and Seuring, (2014), Silvestre, (2015a), Dubey et al., (2016)

2.1.3.2 Principles for Managing Social Sustainability.

These are formal and informal practices designed to ensure control over the outcome of actions executed by others (Monks and Minow, 2004). In the supply chain context, these practices suppose managers oversee the selection, comparison, and monitoring of suppliers (Sodhi et Tang, 2017). Yawar and Seuring (2015) in their review of supply chain and corporate social responsibility, classified responsible supply chain strategies into communication, compliance, and supplier development to manage social issues. The literature also emphasises the use of codes of conduct, social standards, social reporting, inspection, and auditing as important tools for managing social issues in the supply chain (Ciliberti et al., 2009; Lu et al., 2012; Klassen and Vereecke, 2012; Sancha et al., 2015; Mani et al., 2017). Scholars have discussed the

implementation of social standards for instance Ciliberti et al. (2009) in their work on the Italian SMEs showed how the use of social standards such as SA8000 (the global social accounting standards) is essential to develop and ameliorate social aspects of labour condition and human right and further argued these standards to strengthen the relationship amongst supply chain members if not limited to the lead firms only. About auditing, it has been argued to improve labour conditions and remuneration (Kortelainen, 2008). Sancha et al. (2015) found inspection to mount pressure on suppliers to improve working conditions and minimising work accidents.

Gimenez and Sierra (2013) suppose these approaches are designed to enhance supply chain social sustainability performance in managing relationships with suppliers. Bonatto et al. (2021) suggest managing relationships within and across the supply chain aims to maintain an equitable and profitable balance between business and authority on a long-term basis. However, the effectiveness of this different approach in SSCM is not certain (Sodhi and Tang, 2017). Managing social sustainability in the supply chain might involve suppliers' rewards and sanctions for adherence to social sustainability standards. A study by Porteous et al. (2015) revealed that supplier incentives through training and increased business opportunities compared to sanctions improve supplier violation and reduce focal operating costs. A similar study by Sancha et al. (2016) reported that “while assessment of suppliers improves the buyer’s social performance, collaboration with suppliers enhances the supplier’s social performance”. Further studies by Formentini and Taticchi (2016) group social sustainability managing principles into collaboration and formalisation practices.

Notwithstanding the insight into principles for managing (formalised mechanisms and the significance of collaborative approaches) social sustainability in supply chains, limited research has been conducted on addressing the levels of implementation of such codes and standards (Nakamba et al., 2017). However, their scope and mode of implementation differ

greatly (Morais and Silvestre, 2018). A crucial aspect is that of examining the effectiveness of these principles in different social and economic contexts (Sodhi and Tang, 2017).

Table 3 Mechanisms for Implementing Social Sustainability

Governance Mechanisms	Description	Authors
Integration Activities and Internal Governance	These mechanisms include top management support; Use of codes of conduct / ethics, guides, and internal policies; establishment of objectives, action plans and management systems; incentive systems and rewards for internal members; systematic analysis of the supply chain and classification of suppliers; adherence to international initiatives (e.g., Global Compact);	Carter and Jennings (2004); Cilibertietal. (2008) Pagell and Wu (2009); Formentini and Taticchi (2016)
Screening/ selection of future suppliers	Definition of minimum standards required; Process defined for supplier selection	Carter and Jennings (2004) Vachon and Klassen (2006); Leire and Mont (2010); Ehrgott et al. (2010)
Incentive actions for improvement	Establishment of consequences for noncompliance; Contracts with reward system; Encouraging competition based on sustainable criteria	Vachon and Klassen (2006); Gimenez and Sierra (2013); Formentini and Taticchi (2016)
Assessment	Activities related to supplier assessment, such as application of questionnaires or company visit.	Gimenez and Sierra (2013); Sancha, Gimenez and Sierra (2016)
Monitoring	It seeks to guarantee hiring expectations, with audits or certification by an independent third party. It reports on success and the way in which agreed practices are being implemented.	Leire and Mont (2010); Grosvold, Hojmosse and Roehrich (2014); Marshall et al. (2015)
Collaboration	Better coordination with customers, suppliers, and stakeholders to jointly improve results. May involve membership	Gimenez and Sierra (2013); Marshall et al. (2015); Sancha, Gimenez and Sierra (2016)

	/ collaboration with NGOs; Collective initiatives (sectoral)	
Development	Training and education; Joint development; Follow-up activities; Supplier diversity; Knowledge and shared assets; Knowledge transfer; Local Suppliers	Ciliberti et al. (2008); Gimenez and Sierra (2013); Formentini and Taticchi (2016)

Adapted Akhavan and Beckmann (2017), Formentini and Taticchi (2016) and Gimenez and Sierra (2013)

2.1.3.3 Barriers/challenges to Social Sustainability

Even though social sustainability is emphasized to be an important element for SSCM, it has been argued to be inadequately understood and complex (Silvestre, 2016). A lot of companies still struggling with challenges to implement and manage social sustainability in their supply chains (Khan et al., 2021). These challenges/barriers are often seen as internal and external to firms. They are described as factors that hinder firms from implementing and achieving social sustainability practices in the supply chains (Govindan et al., 2021). The literature emphasises financial concerns such as pressure on cost reduction (internal) and the demand for low-priced products (external) as a barrier to social sustainability (Walker and Jones, 2012). Others have argued the lack of financial support from the government, availability of support grants, and access to bank loans are significant barriers (Zorzini et al., 2015). The lack of stakeholders' interest including pressure from labour associations and shareholders (Mani et al., 2016), customer requirement (Hussain et al., 2018), investor pressure (Wilhelm et al., 2016) lack of interest from skilled policy entrepreneurs (Davies et al., 2019; Marshall et al., 2015) and no commitment from top management are also emphasized in the literature. The absence of strict laws and regulations provides an easy escape for social supply chain practices (Panigrahi et

al., 2019; Mani et al., 2016). Panigrahi and Nune (2018) highlighted that “the lack of employment stability, lack of health and safety measures, poor community economic benefits, lack of scope of improvement in products’ characteristics, inadequate infrastructure development, and lack of skilled human resources are important barriers to adoption of sustainability practices”. Inadequate knowledge, awareness, and engagement in social sustainability (Mani et al., 2016; Hussain et al., 2018); the non-consideration of moral values and ethical principles, inadequate information technology application (Movahedipour et al., 2017); cultural differences, bribery, and corruption (Huq et al., 2014); inadequate training and education (Zorzini et al., 2015); the absence of competitive pressure (Mani et al., 2016; Khan et al., 2021)

Firms failing to become socially sustainable often comes with plenty of negative effects affecting the entire supply (Sodhi and Tang, 2018). Similarly, the inadequately addressed social sustainability issues in supply chains could result in losing important social resources like individuals’ talents and capabilities, stakeholders' support, relationships, and social values (Hannibal and Kauppi, 2019). To others, poorly managed social issues can negatively impact the business environment between the lead organization, stakeholders, and communities across the geographic spread of the supply chain (Bubicz et al., 2019).

The literature suggests barriers/challenges to the implementation of social sustainability in supply chain management are emergent context-dependent and even based on the sector (Nakamba et al., 2017). Research by Hall et al. (2012) revealed that some sectors are socially exclusive due to the extensive training and capabilities required while others are socially inclusive but lack the necessary resources and financial incentives.

Table 4 Barriers to Social Sustainability

Author	Title	Context	Identified Barriers
Walker and Jones (2012)	Sustainable supply chain management across the UK private sector	Developed economy (UK) multi-industry	Lack of commitment of top management, Lack of competitive pressure, Demand for lower priced products, Resource limitation, Cost pressure, Organisational reluctance, Lack of knowledge and Size of the organisation
Huq et al., (2014)	Social sustainability in developing country suppliers an exploratory study in the readymade garments industry of Bangladesh	Developing economy Bangladesh garment industry	Mock compliance, bribery and corruption, lack of law enforcement and regulations, cost reduction, cultural mismatch,
Mani et al., (2016)	Impediments to Social Sustainability Adoption in the Supply Chain: An ISM and MICMAC Analysis in Indian Manufacturing Industries	Emerging economy (India) manufacturing industries	Lack of regulatory compliance, lack of awareness of social sustainability, lack of pressure from trade unions, lack of pressure by stakeholders, lack of customer requirements, lack of pressure from social organisations, lack of zeal on the part of the skillful policy entrepreneurs, lack of social concern, and inadequate competitive pressure,
Nakamba et al., (2017)	How does social sustainability feature in studies of supply chain management? A review and research agenda	Systematic literature review	Lack of government enforcement and regulation, financial limitations, lack of investor pressure, and the lack of industrial obligations
Panigrahi and Nune (2018)	A stakeholders' perspective on barriers to adopt sustainable practices in MSME supply chain: Issues and	Emerging economy Indian textile industry	Lack of employment stability, lack of health and safety measures, poor community economic benefits lack of stricter government rules and regulations, lack of skill full human resource, lack of awareness and inadequate infrastructural development.

	challenges in the textile sector		
--	----------------------------------	--	--

2.1.3.4 Solutions to address the barriers for social sustainability in supply chain management.

These solutions are suggested to help avoid the impacts of the barriers while facilitating the implementation of social sustainability initiatives. The literature identifies several solutions, for instance, awareness of social sustainability practices. Externally, firms can create awareness by establishing and employing social norms and directives to enhance the knowledge and commitment to social sustainability practices (Ahmadi et., 2017), couple that firms focus on creating public awareness of social performance (Davis et al., 2019), more to that, firms established strong relationships with external stakeholder (government, communities, NGOs) to enhance transparency (Mani and Gunasekaran, 2018) and to also develop feedback channels with these actors to engage them directly or indirectly in the social initiatives (Khan et al., 2021). Internally, Mani and Gunasekaran (2018) emphasis personnel awareness. Huq et al. (2014) insist on a strong commitment by top management embodied in the corporate policy. Also, firms should design, develop, and plan efficient social sustainability training programs for employees and upstream partners (Morais and Silvestre, 2018). Other solutions mentioned are aspects of “developing cultural cohesion and cooperation among the internal actors and employees’ autonomy to engage in social actions in their environment” (Huq and Klassen, 2016; Hannibal and Kauppi, 2019).

From a strategic perspective, the literature highlights necessary measures to ensure strategic coordination with the supply chain entities (Sodhi and Tang, 2018). Strategic coordination measures are necessary to synchronise decision-making and ensure the various entities are on the same page toward social sustainability targets. This will entail cross-functional collaborations among departments and with entities across the supply chain (Ahmadi, 2017).

Also, advanced levels of strategic coordination with suppliers are necessary to collaborate and support different social initiatives across the spread of the supply chain (Sodhi and Tang, 2018). The literature also asserts that “transparency-based workflow or open-door policy” with supply chain partners provides a conducive atmosphere for social sustainability commitment (Wilhelm et al.2016). Finally, a careful supplier selection and assessment of social commitment allow for social awareness among supply chain partners (Yawar and Seuring, 2018).

Recent studies suggest the implementation of advanced technologies (internet of things) for social sustainability as an extension of its use in environmental SCM to mitigate social sustainability-related risk (Khan et al., 2021).

2.1.3.5 Benefits of implementing Social Sustainability in supply chain management.

Outcome refers to performance, the significance of sustainability practices, and their importance to organizational performance. That is, the main goal that supply chain partners seek to achieve when implementing social sustainability in SCM practices is to manage all kinds of risks associated with the supply chain (Yawar and Seuring, 2015).

Many studies have investigated the benefits resulting from social sustainability initiatives in SCM (Pullman et al.,2009; Klassen and Vereeke, 2012; Mani et al., 2018). However, some depict leaders in the sustainability agenda as integrating sustainability as a key strategic objective by many companies to enhance overall corporate performance. Others show no impact between a well-defined and articulated corporate sustainability strategy and performance (Croom et al., 2018).

Integrating social sustainability practices in SCM might lead to better product quality, and enhancement in skills and compensation (Pullman et al., 2009). Further, costs can be reduced

(Carter, 2005), which might result in improved corporate social performance, better brand reputation, and other strategic benefits (Mani et al., 2016a) for the lead firm. Research has focused particularly on the positive or negative impact between social practices and financial performance (Nakamba et al., 2017). Pullman et al. (2009) asserts such positive outcomes may improve quality performance, which in turn improves cost performance. But such financial benefits are not certain in the short and mid-term when investing in social sustainability practices (Wang and Sarkis, 2013; Marshall et al., 2016).

In contrast, research on the negative outcomes of investing in social sustainability initiatives argues that investing in social practices increases costs such as skills enhancement (Pullman et al., 2009). These results aligned with Gimenez et al. (2012) who found that enhancing employee working conditions led to increasing costs in manufacturing. Whereas these studies reveal mixed findings on social practices and performance outcomes, nevertheless, other studies showed no effect of investing in social practices on performance benefits (Holloos et al., 2012).

However, assessing performance using social sustainability is a real challenge compared to environmental and economic sustainability using the analytical tools used for assessing economic and environmental performance are not easily integrated into social sustainability (Govindan et al., 2021) which is often attributed to the complexity of social practices and the lack of unified indicators applicable in supply chains in addition to the subjectivity of social sustainability in nature (Zorzini et al., 2015). Different metrics have been used in the literature to assess social performance (Sakis et al., 2010). For instance, Tamara et al. (2017) proposed three indicators that are “generic, suppliers-specific, and industry-specific” to assess social sustainability performance. Chen and Kitsis (2017) proposed performance indicators to assess social sustainability performance under two broad categories: human capital and societal capital. These two broad categories cover social indicators related to employees, the

community, and customers. This might suggest integrating social sustainability initiatives in SCM is beneficial to both upstream and downstream supply chains.

Notwithstanding the mixed results on the outcomes of social sustainability, Nakamba et al. (2017) suggested that empirical investigations be conducted on what specific social practices impact corporate financial performance however, taking into consideration non-financial performance indicators to show social practices impact not only financial and non-financial measures but also economically valued outcomes. Couple that, Roca and Searcy (2012) suggested that linking operations with social practices has the potential to deliver a wide range of benefits across business processes. Therefore, despite the challenges to measuring outcomes from social practices, organizations are still aiming for economic benefits and social improvement when investing in social sustainability practices in supply chains.

Table 5 Performance benefits to social sustainability

Author	Title	Performance	Context
Pullman et al. (2009)	Food for thought: social vs environmental sustainability practices and performance outcomes	Improvement in product quality	Food and beverage companies U.S. A
Klassen and Vereecke (2012)	Social issues in supply chains: Capabilities link responsibility, risk (opportunity), and performance	Improvement in social and economic (reduction in cost, increase in market share) performance	Multinational companies
Yand and Zang (2017)	The impact of sustainable supplier management practices on buyer-supplier performance: An	Improve buyer-supplier relationships and their performances lead to stronger competitive advantage.	Chinese manufacturing

	empirical study in China		
Mani et al. (2018)	Enhancing supply chain performance through supplier social sustainability: An emerging economy perspective	Improvement in both buyer and supplier social performance and the overall supply chain performance	Indian manufacturing
Mani and Gunasekaran (2018)	Four forces of supply chain social sustainability adoption in emerging economies	Improvement in operational and social performances of both buyers and suppliers. It also helps to improve brand image in terms of social responsibility.	India and Portuguese firms
Croom et al. (2018)	Impact of social sustainability orientation and supply chain practices on operational performance	Advanced social sustainability practices improve operational performance which is significantly moderated by long-term orientation. Basic social sustainability practices do not improve operational performance.	United States-based companies
Jajja et al. (2020)	The indirect effect of social responsibility standards on organizational performance in apparel supply chains: A developing country perspective.	Improvement in organizational social behavior which in turn positively impacts operational and quality performance.	Apparel companies in Pakistan

2.1.4 The conceptual framework

The purpose of this research is to explore the strategic implementation of social sustainability in improving supply chain management in the agriculture sector of a lower-middle-income country and to develop and validate a framework for implementing improvement on social sustainability in supply chain management. Further, the research seeks to identify motivators, enablers, barriers, and distinct dimensions of social sustainability in the agribusiness supply chain as well as its benefits on performance.

The literature highlights several drivers, social issues, practices, and barriers to social sustainability in SCs (supply chains). Drivers are supposed to influence the adoption and implementation of social sustainability initiatives while barriers hinder the adoption and implementation of such initiatives especially in developing countries. As such, focal firms and their supply chain partners are pressured by the different stakeholder groups (stakeholders theory) to address social issues in their supply chains. In response to the various stakeholder's pressure, they implement social sustainability practices using resource-based view perspectives which promote organisational learning, and trust and support long-term relationships among the actors and stakeholders in the supply chain. These practices are then reflected in terms of improved social sustainability indicators and supply chain performance via the avoidance of social sustainability risks. To improve social sustainability in the agricultural supply chain efforts to establish a relationship among drivers, barriers, social issues, principles for engaging, social level, and performance have been proposed through the conceptual model developed (fig 2.1.4)

To understand how firms in the Cameroon agricultural sector implement social sustainability in the supply chain, the research argues that articulating these three aspects – Driver, principles for engagement, and relationship levels (i.e., suppliers, consumers, and/or society) based on the business situation (contingency perspectives) – is central in describing and analysing how

social sustainability issues are implemented and managed, how such initiatives are managed at various stages in the supply chain, the relationship levels focal companies engage when operationalizing such initiatives and the possible interconnections between these three dimensions (Mani et al., 2015; Morais and Silvestre, 2018).

Figure 3 conceptual framework

Theoretical frame

- SRBV theory
- Contingency theory

2.1.5 Theoretical Underpinning

The literature mentions the potential for the use of organisational theory to advance research studies on SSCM. This has been mentioned by researchers with no theoretical lenses for SSCM investigation (Carter and Easton, 2011; Morais and Biabieri, 2021; Palazzo and Vollero, 2021). Ketchen and Hult, (2007) suggest the opportunity to employ them that has not yet been realised. Also, others have criticised the slow pace of integrating theories into SSCM studies (Carter and Easton, 2011). However, the efforts for the introduction of such theoretical frameworks in SSCM are still gaining momentum (Gold et al., 2009). For others, SSCM is still emerging, and this provides an extensive opportunity for studies to bridge the gap between theory and practice (Touboulic and Walker, 2015). Couple that, the SSCM field has drawn from several organisational theories (Carter and Easton, 2011).

Despite efforts integrating theories on SSCM investigations, most of the literature has been applied more widely in environmental research. To become more mainstream in organisations, social sustainability investigations need to adopt similar theoretical lenses in understanding organisational behaviour via the use of organisational theories (Touboulic and Walker, 2015). Moxham and Kauppi (2014) defined organisational theory as “a management insight that can help explain or describe organisational behaviours, designs, or structures”. Font et al. (2008) stated that SSCM was drawn from various theories with the principal objective that firms must engage in their supply chain with upstream producers and downstream consumers.

Researchers such as Carter and Easton (2011); Sarkis et al (2011), pointed out that, the literature has attracted popular theories from different disciplines on sustainable SCM investigations and called on researchers to use other lenses could generate new insight in the field. Sarkis et al. (2011), Morali and Searcy (2012), and Touboulic and Walker (2015) identified various theories in sustainable supply chain management. Sarkis et al. (2011) point out nine different theories relating to Sustainable supply chain management including

complexity theory, ecological modernization theory, institutional theory, resource-based view (RBV), resource dependency theory (RDT), Stakeholder theory, social network theory and transactional cost economy. Other theories include agency theory, critical success theory, contingency theory, rough set theory, and system theory (Nakamba et al., 2017). For example, building on the resource dependency theory (RDT) Klassen and Vereecke (2012), show how firms promote the development of internal and external collaboration to gain control over resources that minimize their dependence and over resources that maximize the dependence of other firms themselves. They further assert that such collaborative efforts not only help mitigate social risk in supply chains when addressing social issues but also create new opportunities and enhance the sustainability performance of firms. Similarly, Walker and Jones (2012) using the contingency theory develop different approaches used by firms to SSCM and to analyse factors influencing SSCM. Ehr Gott et al., (2010) using stakeholder theory examines how pressure from stakeholders (purchasing managers) determines the extent to which firms consider social aspects in the selection of emerging market suppliers. Further, they examine the link between socially sustainable supplier selection on firms' capabilities, market reputation, and supply chain management. A Few studies have used more than one theory in their studies, Pagell et al., (2010) used the resource-based view and transactional cost economy and found that the two theories provide conflicting explanations for the evolving use of the purchasing portfolios in SSCM, but that stakeholder theory can be used to reconcile both perspectives. Mani and Gunasekaran (2018) using stakeholder theory and institutional perspectives demonstrate how pressure from the different stakeholders acts as the principal driving force of firms in determining the extent to which firms consider supply chain social sustainability in emerging countries and further investigate the adoption of social sustainability to supplier's social performance, operational performance, and social reputation of the focal firms. Further studies building on the RBV theory such as Carter and Jennings (2004) through purchasing social

responsibility (PSR) and Sodhi (2015) through stakeholder resource-based view (SRBV) show the significance of developing and harvesting stakeholders' resources for the competitive advantage of the focal firm (Mani et al., 2018).

2.1.5.1 Stakeholder Resource Base View (SRBV)

A stakeholder is “any group or individuals who can affect or is affected by the achievement of an organization's objectives” (Freeman, 1884). Stakeholder theory supposes that firms produce externalities that affect many parties (stakeholders) which are constituents beyond the direct representatives or shareholders. Donaldson and Preston (1995) considered three theoretical approaches to stakeholders including a descriptive approach which defines the basis for stakeholders' claims and concerns; an instrumental approach sets a balance between corporate finance and stakeholders' interests; and the normative approach or the ethical stakeholder theory it places stakeholders' interest ahead of financial gains that is according to the authors “the interests of all stakeholders are of intrinsic value. That is, each group of stakeholders merits consideration for its own sake and not merely because of its ability to further the interests of some other group, such as the shareowners.”

Clarkson (1995) identified five groups of stakeholders for firms (shareholders, employees, customers, suppliers, and communities) and firms should consider the legitimacy, power of influence, and urgency of the claim of each stakeholder when making decisions. Stakeholders are classified based on the degree of influence each party has on the firm. “Primary stakeholders are actors who directly influence the company (e.g., suppliers, employees, community residents, and customers); similarly, secondary stakeholders can affect the firms through influence on the primary stakeholders (e.g., nongovernmental organizations). The public stakeholder group includes government and communities that provide infrastructure to

markets whose regulations and laws must be obeyed” (Agle et al., 2008). All these stakeholders are significant in exerting pressure on the sustainable behaviour of firms (Sarkis et al., 2011). These stakeholders are grouped into three main driving forces influencing social sustainability implementation that is normative (industry and history), cultural (norms, ethical values, and tradition), and regulatory (government and other secondary stakeholders) (Huq et al., 2014; Gaur and Mani, 2018; Nguyen et al., 2021). Studies by Mani and Gunasekaran (2018) and Köksal et al. (2018) revealed that regulatory forces significantly influence social sustainability in the entire supply chain, particularly in developing economies. Meanwhile, social sustainability adoption and the aspect of cultural values and normative forces have a well-established relationship in developed economies where the sustainability culture is strongly rooted (Nakamba et al., 2017).

Ehrgott et al., (2011) used the stakeholder theory to demonstrate how different stakeholders’ pressures including government, customer, middle management, mimetic, coercive, and normative influence supply chain social sustainability adoption and help them to achieve social legitimacy. Branco and Rodrigues (2006) argued that engaging stakeholders is pushed by the potential to achieve long-term benefits which can be material or immaterial. This is further justified by Donaldson and Preston (1995) who showed through instrumental perspectives that a strong relationship between stakeholder management and the firm's performance. Stakeholder theory has been used to investigate firms’ drivers/motivations towards social sustainability efforts and the role played by the different stakeholders in influencing firms to act in a social sustainability manner (Sancha et al., 2015; Mani and Gunasekaran, 2018). Thus, this research investigates the influence of different stakeholders on improving social sustainability in the agricultural supply chain in Cameroon through the stakeholder theory (instrumental form).

Further building on the resource base view (RBV) of firms that supposes the possession of resources that are rare and cannot be easily copied gives them a competitive edge over others (Barney, 1991). Through purchasing social responsibility, Carter and Jennings (2004) showed how firms develop such resources to gain a competitive advantage over rivals in the upstream supply chain. Similarly, Mani et al (2016a) used the SRBV proposed by Sodhi (2015) in the entire supply chain to address social sustainability issues such as equity, safety and health, product responsibility, human rights, and philanthropy throughout the supply chain. This supposes a learning process to improve social sustainability might take time and cost significantly, but such learning can have a considerable beneficial influence on supplier performance, operating cost reduction, and relationship management (Klassen and Vereecke 2012). Such supply chains can easily avoid unwanted consequences and build stronger trust with stakeholders (Morali and Searcy, 2013).

Building on Sodhi (2015) SRBV is conceptualised from the stakeholder's theory and resource-based view theory, which supposes in operations, there is a diverse group of stakeholders with unique resources, capabilities, and tasks, aiming toward the optimum use of resources within a specific time frame which is important to consider both competitive advantage and dynamic capability taking into consideration risk and uncertainty. This research further considers how firms manage these stakeholders with inimitable resources to achieve their corporate social sustainability objectives. Touboulic and Walker (2015) and Sodhi (2015) mentioned that theoretical perspectives from other disciplines impact the way SSCM has been conceptualized. There has been a highlight on researching the relationship amongst resources, performance, and power of firms. Notably, researchers focus on identifying competitive advantage sources through deploying natural environmental and social dilemmas within the structure of business capacity which fits with the current sustainable development focus.

2.1.5.2 Contingency Theory

The contingency theory of organisational analysis is of the view that organisations dynamically seek to fit with changing contextual variables in that different situations require different practices. A significant consideration is that of identifying those variables that can generally influence firms' structure and practices and the predictable outcomes caused by differences in these variables (Donaldson, 2001). This approach emphasises that the nature and structure of organisations can take many forms and can be linked to several contingencies. In operations management and SCM literature, researchers have used contingencies to analyse contextual variables and their influence on organisations choice of practice to performance variables (Sodhi and Tang, 2017). Sousa and Voss (2008) categorise contingency variables into four including national context and culture, firm size, strategic context, and other organisational context variables amongst which research on SSCM has either focused on specific industries, countries, or both. Tachizawa and Wong's (2014) review of the framework of approaches and contingency to the management of sustainability in supply chains highlighted four main factors: power, material criticality, dependence, distance, and knowledge resources have been the most renowned.

Contingency theory argues that different situations require different practices, contributing in a way that identifies a set of variables that influence organizations. Further aver that there is no one-size-fits-all approach to managing companies taking into consideration the different internal characteristics and external environments (Morais and Barbieri, 2022). Golicic et al. (2019) used a contingency approach to show how unique stakeholders and business environment shape their understanding of social sustainability within each supply chain. The authors stated, "that the optimal course of action is contingent upon the situation". Similarly, Walker and Jones (2012) developed a typology of approaches to sustainable SCM, based on internal and external enablers and barriers. Companies were classified as internal focusers,

reserved players, external responders, and agenda setters. Using the contingency view of strategic management this research develops a typology of approaches based on the driver/motivation, principle for engaging, and the social-relational level on the extent to which firms in the Cameroon agricultural supply chain implement social sustainability.

2.1.6 Potential Corporate Social Responsibility

The concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has been well studied in the literature and considered to be broad beyond the limits of supply chains to encompass the firms' overall treatment of human beings and the environment (Andersen and Skjoett-Larsen, 2009). However, a consensus is yet to be reached on its definition and the general CSR practices (Crane et al., 2009). This has been partly attributed to the extent of its operationality. Other difficulties are related to companies' differences in size, products, profitability, resources, and societal impacts. Not forgetting the different concepts used interchangeably to describe CSR – sustainable development (Brundtland, 1987), corporate citizenship, sustainable entrepreneurship, the triple bottom line (Carroll, 1991), and business ethics (Marrewijk, 2003). Studies such as the work of Montiel (2008), Marrewijk (2003), and Dahlsrud (2008) attempt to characterise the different perspectives used to define CSR. For example, the shareholders' approach “the social responsibility of business is to increase its profits” (Friedman, 1970), and the stakeholders' approach to CSR requires “consideration of issues beyond the narrow economic, technical, and legal requirements of the company”. The societal approach of CSR states that “companies are responsible to society as a whole, of which they are an integral part” that is they obtain their license to operate from the public to “serve constructively the needs of society – to the satisfaction of society” (cited in Crane et al., 2008). Others describe CSR as “the responsibility of companies for their impact on society to integrate social, environmental,

ethical, human rights and consumer concerns into their business operations and core strategies” (Confederation, 2012). Similarly, ISO 26000—the global Standard for social responsibility characterizes social responsibility as “an organisation’s responsibility for the impact of its decisions and activities on society and the environment, through transparent and ethical behaviour” (International Organization for Standardization 2010). Such thinking is directed towards sustainable development as the main goal of the organisation. This aligns with the World Commission on Environment and Development which places intra and intergenerational equity at the forefront. Dyllick and Hockerts (2002) characterised corporate sustainability as “meeting the needs of a company’s direct and indirect stakeholders, without compromising its ability to meet the needs of future stakeholders as well. To achieve this goal, companies need to maintain their economic, social, and environmental capital base”, which directly refers to triple-bottom-line thinking (Elkington, 1998).

The current literature suggests CSR and sustainability share environmental and social aspects. That is, both concepts are converging even though they have their paradigmatic differences (Montiel, 2008). In the past environmental concerns were considered under the social dimension in CSR studies while in corporate sustainability, the social dimension is considered an important dimension of sustainability (Shalchian et al., 2015). In recent times, firms must address sustainability issues (economic gains, social equity, and environmental integrity) in all their operations and activities before they can be considered sustainable or socially responsible. Thus, aspects of CSR that incorporate economic growth, people/society, and the ecology and corporate sustainability of the triple bottom line (TBL) that is profit, planet, and people dimension are more alike. Both are directed toward balancing the triple bottom-line elements to achieve long-term sustainability and social responsibility. Thus, CSR and sustainability aim to balance economic gains, social equity, and environmental integrity, notwithstanding how they are conceptualized as environmental issues under social concerns or as the third

dimension of sustainability. CSR and sustainability are found to further converge to how investigators operationalize their constructs to measure social and environmental performance as well as on variables measuring CSR and sustainability. Variables for CSR include “ethics policy, philanthropic contributions, stakeholder relationships (investors, shareholders, customers, suppliers, employees, and the community), urban development, minority support programs, health and safety initiatives, pollution abatement programs, and conserving natural resources. Sustainability variables include employee eco-initiatives, voluntary environmental restoration, eco-design practices, and systematically reducing waste and emissions from operations from an environmental dimension. However, other sustainability measures also capture economic and social dimensions, such as government relationships, stakeholder interests, health and safety, and community development”. This supposes that TBL measures and variables of sustainability mimic those of the tridimensionality CSR vision (Montiel, 2008; Dahlsrud, 2008). Thus, sustainable companies consider stakeholder interests and become involved with their local communities.

Part Two – Contextual Underpinning

2.2.1.1 Overview of Cameroon

Cameroon is a central African country located along the Atlantic Ocean with a population of 26.5 million (2021). Cameroon is classified under the lower-middle-income countries (LMIC) with a per capita GDP of \$1,507 in 2019. The official working languages are English and French. Because of the country's rich natural endowment and diversified culture, Cameroon is often called "Africa in miniature" (i.e., a bit of everything found in every other country can be found in Cameroon). Despite efforts by the government and foreign bodies to eliminate poverty to a considerable level and human development, close to 50% of the population lives below \$3.20 a day. Cameroon has currently only met one of the Millennium Development Goals (MDG2: net school enrolment). In 2020, Transparency International ranked Cameroon 149 out of 180 countries per the corruption perception index. Corruption remains a key obstacle to wider economic growth in the country (BTI, 2022).

Table 6 Key Indicators

Indication	Score
Population	26.5 million
Population growth rate	2.6% p. a
Life expectancy	59.3 years
Urban population	57.6%
HDI	0.563
HDI rank of 189	153
UN Education Index	0.547
Poverty	47%
GDP p.c., PPP	\$ 3773

Sources (as of December 2021): The World Bank, World Development Indicators 2021 | UNDP, Human Development Report 2020. Footnotes: (1) Average annual growth rate. (2) Percentage of population living below \$3.20 a day at 2011 international prices

After a prolonged period of peace and stability, in recent years Cameroon has been struggling to sustain this peace and stability following secessionist insurgency from the English-speaking parts of the country in 2017 while in the Far Northern part of the country, there has been serious terrorist attacks from Boko Haram. Over 600 lives have been lost including 400 civilians and 200 uniform officers, and over half a million internally displaced persons (BTI, 2022).

To effect visible structural changes in the Cameroonian public, the outcome of an extensive consultative talk with different stakeholder groups brought in a bold vision for the country's long-term development aimed toward economic growth and poverty alleviation while committing to the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) (GESP, 2010). The Growth Employment Strategy Paper (GESP) emphasis the agricultural sector as the engine of development with the objective of the vision centred to have a competitive and productive agro-industrial sector that can sustain growth, ameliorate the social situation, and help to integrate the country into the international scheme while accounting for 23% of the country's GDP.

2.2.1.2 Foundation of the Country's Long-term Development

Following the prolonged economic crisis in the 1980s, Cameroon was engaged in an economic revival plan through the help of its developmental partners. For this to be successful, Cameroon was subjected to a period of structural adjustment programs (SAPs) to stabilize its economy. As such the country's medium and long-term initiatives were discontinued. In 2006, Cameroon researched the satisfactory point on the implementation of the SAPs and was admitted into the Heavily Indebted Poor Country Initiative (HIPC) and this followed the cancellation of a

considerable amount of the country's debt. The debt cancellation enabled the government in 2003 to produce a Poverty Reduction Strategy Paper (PRSP). However, results from the population and household census in 2007 on poverty reduction were unsatisfactory. This outcome allowed for the revision of the poverty reduction strategy paper in 2009 and a long-term sustainable development plan was adopted (for a period of 25 years) with the GESP used as the main instrument for achieving phase one of the long-term vision (2010 – 2019) and the second instrument the National Development Strategy (NDS30) running from (2020 – 2030) with an agenda to align with the SDGs, stabilize planning timelines and as well as adjournments on executing the growth employment strategy paper (MINEPAT, 2021).

2.2.1.3 The Objectives of the Long-Term Developmental Vision

To achieve the country's long-term developmental plan, MINEPAT through the NDS30 emphasis that: *“the intention is to engage in a structural transformation of the economy by effecting fundamental socio-economic structural changes to promote endogenous and inclusive development while preserving opportunities for future generations”*. The goal of this structural transformation is to lead the country toward attaining the status of a Newly Industrialized Country. Thus, an industrialized strategy has been adopted as the focus of NDS30 with four main objectives that are “to Reduce poverty to an acceptable social level; become a middle-income country; attain the status of a Newly Industrialized Country; and strengthen national unity and consolidate the democratic process” (MINEPAT, 2021).

The NDS30, also demonstrates how the government plans on achieving these objectives in identifying targets to assess the progress of the long-term vision:

- To ensure economic growth i.e., wealth creation and structural adjustments to facilitate industrialization, the purpose will be to “increase the annual growth rate from 4.6% to

8.1% on average between 2020 and 2030; to increase growth of the secondary sector (excluding oil) beyond 8% on average; to reduce trade balance deficit from 8.8% of GDP in 2018 to less than 3% in 2030” (MINEPAT 2021). This objective will address SDGs 8 (decent work and economic growth), 9 (industry innovation and infrastructure), 11 (sustainable cities and communities), and 12 (responsible consumption and production).

- To ensure significant improvement in living conditions i.e., availability of basic social services, and reduce poverty and unemployment to an accepted social level, NDS30 targets to “reduce the rate of poverty from 37.5% in 2014 to less than 25% in 2030; curb underemployment from 77% in 2014 to less than 50% in 2030; increase Human Capital Index from 0.39 in 2018 to 0.55 as well as Human Development Index from 0.52 in 2016 to 0.70 in 2030” (MINEPAT, 2021). This will address SDGs 1 to 7 and 10 (no poverty, zero hunger, good health and well-being, quality education, gender equality, clean water and sanitation, affordable and clean energy, and reduced inequality).
- To significantly integrate measures to protect the environment and to mitigate risks related to climate change i.e., economic growth that comes along with sustainable and inclusive development (MINEPAT, 2021). This will address SDGs 13 (climate action), 14 (life below water), and 15 (life on land)
- To ensure governance in achieving the long-term goal i.e., affect the necessary changes to drive institutional practices and to accelerate the process of decentralization (MINEPAT, 2021). This will address SDGs 16 (peace, justice, and strong institutions) and 17 (partnership for the goals).

Table 7 Tentative Stages of the Country’s Long-Term Development Towards its Vision

	2010 – 2019	2020 - 2027	2028 - 2035
	Key Objective – modernizing the economy and accelerating growth	Key Objective – becoming a middle-income country (per capita income between \$ 3706 and \$11 455, 2007 value)	Key Objective: becoming newly industrialized and emerging country (with the secondary sector accounting for more than 40% of GDP)
Economic Growth	Specific objectives: 1. Increasing Cameroon’s overall economic productivity significantly to address urgent sector crises (food, energy, financial, employment crisis) 2. Raising the investment rate significantly to attain a two-digit economic growth 3. Bringing the poverty rate to less than 25% 4. Improving the business climate, as well as public and corporate governance	Specific objectives: 1. Consolidating growth and ensuring its sustainability 2. Extending income redistribution 3. Intensifying environmental protection and climate change	Specific objectives: 1. Ensuring quality growth 2. Bringing the manufacturing value added close to 25% of the GDP and manufactured products value to more than 50 percent of exports 3. Strengthening exchange and outward-looking policies 4. Bringing the minimal poverty rate to less than 10% while raising life expectancy at birth to more than 60 years
	PILLAR I: Increasing productivity and accelerating growth. 1.1 Increasing investment in infrastructure (energy, roads and bridges, ports, telecommunications, and water) 1.2 Modernising the production system. 1.3 Enhancing human resource investment efficiency. 1.4 Mobilising funds and putting the financial	PILLAR I: Maintaining strong growth and diversifying economic activities. 1.1 Developing new infrastructure. • Notably technology-intensive infrastructure 1.2 Intensifying farm mechanization and developing irrigation 1.3 Intensifying industrial processing of local products, notably through:	PILLAR I: Increasing growth and economic industrialization. 1.1 Increasing infrastructure to consolidate Cameroon’s role as a regional transport hub. 1.2 Strengthening the integration of the country’s economic base. • vertical integration of sectors • horizontal integration of branches 1.3 Pursuing regional economic integration.

	<p>system at the service of development.</p> <p>1.5 Consolidating regional integration and diversifying exchange.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agro industries • Aluminium and steel industries • building industry • oil-derived product industries <p>1.4 Building the capacity of the education, training and research system</p> <p>1.5 Increasing the share of non-oil exports.</p> <p>1.6 Accelerating financial market development.</p> <p>1.7 Strengthening regional integration and international insertion</p>	<p>1.4 Strengthening and diversifying international exchanges.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • intensifying commodity trade • intensifying service trade, notably tourism <p>1.5 Strengthening human resources.</p> <p>1.6 Strengthening the capacity of the financial system to mobilize external resources indispensable for the funding of overall domestic demand, namely investments</p>
Social Development	<p>PILLAR 2: Promoting employment and increasing income.</p> <p>2.1 Addressing SMEs problems within the framework of the job creation strategy: realizing the SMEs development master plan (facilitating the establishment of SMEs)</p> <p>2.2 Providing incentives for job creation.</p> <p>2.3 Reviving income policies and redistribution mechanism</p> <p>2.4 Strengthening Social Development.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving access to quality social services nationwide • Promoting the management, social inclusion and 	<p>PILLAR 2: Extending income redistribution policy and strengthening regional development</p> <p>2.1 Strengthening SMIs/SMEs development.</p> <p>2.2 Maintaining incentives for decent job creation.</p> <p>2.3 Increasing social infrastructure.</p> <p>2.4 Expanding the social security system.</p> <p>2.5 Strengthening mechanisms for the fight against social exclusion.</p>	<p>PILLAR 2: Consolidating income redistribution and social inclusion.</p> <p>2.1 Consolidating SMIs/SMEs development.</p> <p>2.2 Consolidating incentives for decent job creation.</p> <p>2.3 Strengthening redistribution mechanisms.</p> <p>2.4 Expanding and consolidating social security and protection.</p> <p>2.5 Pursuing the fight against social exclusion and strengthening gender equality.</p>

	integration of women, the youth, and the vulnerable in economic channels.		
Governance	<p>Pillar 3: Promoting a sound business climate, good governance, and strengthening the strategic management of the country.</p> <p>3.1 Good governance and business climate 3.2 Strategic management of the country</p>	<p>Pillar 3: Consolidating the business climate and governance, protecting the environment, and intensifying climate change control.</p> <p>3.1 Consolidating governance and the business climate</p>	<p>Pillar 3: Maintaining the business climate and governance, furthering decentralization.</p> <p>3.1 Maintaining governance. 3.2 Furthering decentralization 3.3 Strengthening the business climate</p>
Strengthen national unity and consolidate the democratic process	<p>Pillar 4: Consolidating national integration and the democratic process.</p> <p>4.1 Enhancing solidarity and national unity.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • intensifying sensitization and the fight against identity confinement • promoting the development of Cameroon’s culture as a whole • introducing national languages in school curricula • ensuring equitable representation of all segments of society • strengthening solidarity in the decentralization process <p>4.2 Consolidating the democratic process.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increasing transparency in the electoral process, and the institution’s credibility • ensuring and strengthening the respect of individual and association freedoms • promoting the development of civil society • promoting a high turnout in elections • strengthening the State’s authority and credibility of the judicial system • promoting gender parity in the electoral process 		

Adapted from the National Development Strategy 2020 – 2030 (MINEPAT, 2021)

2.2.2 The Agribusiness Supply Chain Management

The concept of agriculture has existed for thousands of years (Khandelwal and al., 2021).

However, it is only in the last two decades that the agroindustry started considering SCM as a major concept for its competitiveness and sustained growth (Tsolakis et al., 2014). The

Food and agribusiness SCM suppose the management of supply, production, customer

demands, and distribution. As many businesses nowadays see the need to compete as a supply chain rather than independent entities (Lambert et al., (1998), due to the rapid change in information and communication technologies (Gunasekaran and Ngai, 2011) increase, globalisation and firms' competitiveness, government safety regulations, the evolving nature of customer demands, forecast revenue growth, managing relationships and the desire to improve overall performance (Stevens and Johnson, 2016), the growing interest on environmental and ethical practices (Pagell and Wu, 2009). The food and agribusiness supply chains have not been left behind to integrate these aspects (Bendinelli et al., 2020).

The food and agribusiness supply chain is complex with two main components: “farm outputs for direct demand and farm-based intermediate products for final demand” (Chandrasekaran and Raghuram. 2014). The sector comprises a set of activities often referred to as “farm to fork” with several actors that is input providers, farm output market, processing, and retailers (Tsolakis et al., 2014). Every actor in the agribusiness supply chain adds a unique value to the final product supported by logistical, financial, and technical services further supported by physical material and product flows, financial flows, information flows, process flows, energy, and natural resources flows. These activities, services, and flows are linked into a complex structure involving various stages (supply production, post-harvest, storage, processing, distribution and end users) and stakeholders (farmers, consumers, agricultural suppliers, food processors/manufacturers and distributors, (NGOs), national and international agricultural bodies, government, related allied institutions, traders (exporters/importers), wholesalers and consumers etc. (Tsolakis et al. 2014; Khandelwal and al. 2021), each of these stakeholders has its unique role to play either in the agribusiness field (private stakeholders) or governance (public stakeholders) (Bachev, 2012).

Figure 4 Food and Agribusiness Supply Shain (adapted from Tsolakis et al. (2014).

As the agribusiness supply chain continues to dynamically evolve to reflect the changing needs of the wider agribusiness environment along with new market trends and a reliable input supply sector, the agribusiness supply chain plays a crucial role in economic transformation and development of food-producing, industrial, and export agriculture sector and the provision of employment and revenue. For instance, investment in agribusiness is estimated to rise to US\$1 trillion in 2030 compared to US\$313 billion in 2010 in sub-Saharan triggered by rising urbanisation in the region (World Bank, 2016). The increase is expected to boost economic growth and transformation in the region. Thus, integrating sustainability into the food and agribusiness supply chain is a necessity.

Food and agribusiness supply chains are also expected to be flexible enough to accommodate the intermediaries while at the same time coping with contemporary issues: stakeholder pressure (on environmental, economic, and social concerns), issues of quality, security,

information asymmetry, and high energy consumption (Zhu et al., 2018). Others include lack of smallholder engagement, lagging industrialization, and management inadequacy and the different components working in silos are issues that need to be addressed and are essential to achieve sustainability in the agricultural sector (Luthra et al., 2018). Thus, in recent times, the food and agribusiness supply chains are required to be sustainable. Luo et al. (2018) found that the food and agribusiness supply chain is closely related to sustainability as it deals with the social aspects of sustainability such as rural development, food safety and security, traceability, and social responsibility. Nonetheless, the current literature shows a growing interest in sustainability studies in the sector (Beske et al., 2014) on single issues like traceability, uncertainty, and risk management with a particular focus on environmental concerns and economic impacts (Yadav et al., 2022). This might suggest the need for further studies to gain more insight into the social dimension of sustainability and the integration of holistic aspects into the food and agribusiness supply chain (Zhu et al., 2018).

2.2.3 Cameroon Agribusiness Environment

The Growth Employment Strategy Paper (GESP, 2010) emphasizes the agricultural sector as the engine of growth, economic diversification, and resilience to external shocks and one of the main pillars for structural transformation in Cameroon. The agricultural sector employs 46 percent of the active population, accounts for close to 50 percent of its export revenue, and provides 22 percent of the country's non-oil gross domestic product (Ndjidda, 2023) see (table 2.2.3.1) On the country's GDP evolution. The agricultural sector in Cameroon consists of different actors including smallholders, cooperatives, larger enterprises, finance organisations, etc engaged in the production of a variety of products which can either be raw materials, semifinished and finished products such as rice, corn, banana-plantain, palm oil, cassava, cacao-coffee, and cotton etc (MINEPAT, 2021). The agricultural market in Cameroon is estimated at USD 11.26 billion in 2023 and is expected to reach USD 13.57 billion by 2028,

growing at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 3.80 percent during the forecast period (Mordor, 2023). The main export destinations for its agricultural products include the Economic and Monetary Community of Central Africa (CEMAC) where Cameroon is considered the bread baker in the region, Nigeria, the European Union, China, and North America (MINEPAT, 2021). See figure 2.2.3.1 and table 2.2.3.2 On EU agrifood imports from Cameroon in percentage per million euros.

Figure 5 Agricultural GDP contribution in Cameroon

(Source: world Bank, 2023)

Notwithstanding this essential role played by the sector towards the economic and social contribution. The sector remains below expectations in terms of poverty reduction and food security. The agriculture sector is characterised by a decrease in capital investment, grants, and government subsidies due to a fixed agricultural policy with an average of 4.5 percent of the state budget allocated each year (MINEPAT, 2016). Thus, agricultural products and foodstuffs per capita fell from 23 percent to 13 percent because of increased population growth (Chitchui, 2019).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 6 EU Agri-food IMPORTS from Cameroon by product category

(Source: EUROSTAT, 2023)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 7 Structure of EU Agri-food trade with Cameroon, 2012 – 2022

(Source: EUROSTAT, 2023)

In this context, Cameroon has adopted different policies and actions plans for instance, in 2005, adopted the rural sector development strategy aimed to; “ensure food security and self-sufficiency of households and the nation, contribute to economic growth and in particular, the growth of foreign trade and employment, increase the incomes of rural producers, improve the quality of life of the rural populations, and ensure the best use and sustainable management of the natural capital base for production” (Chia et al., 2019). In 2014, it adopted the National Agriculture Development Plan (NADP) aimed towards improving the competitive performance of the agribusiness supply chain both in the subregional and international markets while achieving the country’s long-term sustainable development goals as indicated in its National Development Strategy (NDS30) (Ndjidda, 2023).

Several external partners are also involved such as the World Bank, European Union, and other bilateral/multilateral partners. From 2010 to 2020 a total of nearly CFAF3,0000 billion has been received as development aid from external partners and close to CFAF 9,000 billion is estimated to have been located for agriculture development (Ndjidda, 2023). These supports are aimed towards transformative integrated investments such as infrastructures to facilitate production and modernize the agribusiness; “diversifying agricultural production; strengthening existing value chains and the structural transformation process; supporting the agricultural plan compact; and promoting sustainable agriculture processing methods” (Country strategy paper (CSP) 2023-2028). This aligns with the country’s vision to have a competitive and productive agricultural sector that can sustain growth (decent work and economic growth, responsible production and consumption, etc) and ameliorate the social situation(reduce poverty, zero hunger, good health and wellbeing, quality education, gender equality, clean water and sanitation, affordable and clean energy, reduced inequality, and inclusive development) and help to integrate the country into the international scheme (MINEPAT, 2021).

2.3 Summary

In this chapter, the literature on SCM, the TBL, and SSCM was reviewed. The chapter examined social sustainability supply chain management in detail including the dimensions, motivations, barriers, principles for engaging social practices, and the potential benefits of implementing social sustainability practices across the supply chain. The review further explored the relevant theories. The reason for the research context was reviewed. The review revealed an opportunistic window for companies to be more resilient to social sustainability-related risk to explore the implementation of social sustainability in the agricultural supply chain and the possible implication to enhance social and operation performance by adopting the developed conceptual framework. The following chapter elaborates on the philosophical and methodological considerations to explore this opportunity.

Chapter Three - Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to assess the rationale behind the research strategy, design, and methodological choices in addressing the study questions and objectives.

3.2 Philosophical Underpinning

The usefulness of philosophical underpinnings has been highly emphasized in business and management studies (Easterby-Smith et al., 2008). In social sciences, research philosophy refers to developing knowledge and the nature of that knowledge in the social world. It involves significant considerations of how different social actors view the social world. They argued that two central concepts (ontology and epistemology) greatly impact the quality of scientific investigations and are pivotal in research design. However, understanding philosophical issues in research guides the researchers understanding in explaining which design will or will not work, as well as adapting research designs to different subjects. However, scholars argue for the importance of considering the different assumptions of social inquiry to distinguish the different philosophies (Symon and Cassell, 2012; Easterby-Smith et al. 2008).

3.2.1 Ontology and Epistemology

In social science, ontology and epistemology are two fundamental concepts essential in deciding the research methods and methodology. Ontology is about the very essence of reality or the nature of reality that is “the science or study of being”. It deals with the essence of phenomena and the nature of their existence (Symon and Cassell, 2012). It is concerned with whether or not the interested phenomena exist independent from our perception and actions – or is what we see and consider real, instead, an outcome of these acts of perceptions and actions.

Epistemology on the other hand is the grounds of knowledge. It is concerned with how we gain scientific knowledge (Symon and Cassell, 2012). Epistemology allows for the philosophical underpinning of different methodologies. It helps to clarify if a particular claim can be considered knowledge or just an assumption, providing a framework and justification for what can be considered knowledge and the essential criteria for such knowledge to follow.

3.2.2. Major Ontological and Epistemological Stances

Philosophers have yet to agree on the different views on conducting social science investigations. For instance, Easterby-Smith et al. (2008) identified two main opposing views on how to conduct social science research: positivism and social constructionism. Other researchers have taken a continuum view of two opposing extremes: objectivist and subjectivist towards the philosophical perspectives (Morgan and Smircich, 1980). Philosophers like Blaikie (1993) to Ontological assumptions, divided approaches to social science research into two: (a) The realist, perceives reality to be ordered and independent of how we think about the social world. (b) The constructivist, assumes reality to be an outcome born from the thoughts and actions of social actors. For instance, it is an “intersubjective world of cultural objects, meanings, and social institutions” (Blaikie, 1993). While it is argued that there may be multi-realities challenging to the researcher, Blaikie (1993) suggests the choice should be either: realist or constructivist from an ontological standpoint. For epistemology, it should be inside or outside. Between the two extremes, critical realism is considered a better alternative (Fleetwood, 2005). Using Morgan and Smircich (1980) model, the following paragraph highlights the philosophical stances and the choice of research methods for this study.

Table 8 Network of Basic Assumptions Characterising the Subjectivist-Objectivist Debate Within Social Science

Subjective Approaches

Objectivist Approaches

to Social Science

to Social Science

Items	1	2	3	4	5	6
Core ontological assumption (Reality)	Reality as a projection of human imagination	Reality as a social construct	Reality as a realm of symbolic discuss	Reality as a contextual field of information	Reality as a concrete process	Reality as a concrete structure
The assumption about human nature	Man, as pure spirit, consciousness, being	Man, as a social constructor the symbol of the creator	Man, as an actor the symbol of the user	Man, as an information processor	Man, as an adaptor	Man, as a responder
Basic epistemological stance (knowledge)	To obtain phenomenological insight, revelation	To understand how social reality is created	To understand patterns of symbolic discourse	To map contest	To study systems, processes, change	To construct a positive science
Some favourite metaphors	Transcendental	Language game, accomplishment, text	Theatre culture	Cybernetic	Organism	Machine
Research methods	Exploration of pure subjectivity	Hermeneutic	Symbolic analysis	Contextual analysis of gestation	Historical analysis	Lab experiments, survey

Source: adapted from Morgan and Smircich, (1980)

3.2.2.1 Positivism

The ontology on the extreme right (column 6) view reality as a concrete structure that supports an epistemological stand of positivism which supposes reality to be the objective truth and external to social actors. Epistemologically, knowledge can be discovered through observable and measurable facts and regularities. Any reference to subjectivity or intangibility is considered meaningless (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019; Morgan and Smircich, 1980). Positivist focuses on concrete verifiable facts, supports knowledge in an objective way relative to the precise nature of laws, phenomena and regularities (Morgan and Smircich, 1980). Positivism follows a hypothetic-deduction approach and adopts a formal means of reasoning.

3.2.2.2 Interpretivism

The left of the table (column 1 to 3) presents the subjectivist approach (interpretative school). Ontologically, interpretivist sees the world as an extension of human imagination and subjective experiences emerging from social processes (Burrell and Morgan 2017). Interpretivist assumes reality to be socially constructed and explicitly subjectivist with focus on complexity, richness, multiple interpretations, and sense-making of that reality (Saunders et al. 2019; Bryman and Bell. 2015). Interpretivists seeks to create new, richer understandings and interpretations of organisational realities in their social world and context. It attempts to understand the process through which social actors through their own subjective and intersubjective interactions gives meaning to the social world (Orlikowski and Baroudi, 1991). Interpretivists take into consideration language, culture, and history to understand the organisational and social world (Saunders et al., 2019). The Different epistemological stances in the interpretivist school places slightly differences how to achieve this in practice: phenomenology, Hermeneutics and Ethnography.

3.2.2.2.1 Phenomenology

Column 1 of table 4.1, ontologically views the world as a projection of human imagination and supports an epistemological stance of phenomenology (Saunders et al., 2019). Phenomenologist uses participants social behaviour, context, and close analysis of “live experience” to gain deeper understanding on how participant creates meaning through embodied perceptions (Stark and Trinidad, 2007; Saunders et al. 2019). Also, phenomenologist uses subjective experience to generate knowledge, and this relies on the investigators own capability to interpret how individuals perceive the social world from within themselves (Morgan and Smircich, 1980).

3.2.2.2.2 Hermeneutics

Column 2 of table 4.1 considers reality to be socially constructed and supports an epistemological stance of hermeneutics (Saunders et al., 2019). It seeks to examine the processes through which reality is created and conventionally its emphasis the descriptions of text, symbols, stories, and images (Stewart and Philipsen, 1984; Winch, 2002). In contemporary hermeneutics, the meanings of these words have been expanded. The term “text” includes “organisational practices and institutions, economic and social structures, culture and cultural artefacts, and so on” (Prasad, 2015). Couple to that, researchers using hermeneutics to investigate organisational phenomenon needs to consider history and context of the organisation. In addition, hermeneutic is a process of self-reflexive and self-critical. Thus, researcher needs to continually question themselves and their own prejudices when using hermeneutics.

3.2.2.2.3 *Ethnography*

Column 3 of table 4.1 view reality “as a realm of symbolic discourse” and supports an epistemology of ethnography. Ethnography seeks to gain insights on the nature and pattern of the symbols through social reality is created (Morgan and Smircich, 1980). Ethnography supposes studies that profoundly investigate into organisational and inter-organisational phenomena (Carter and Rogers, 2008). The significance for the adoption of ethnographic investigations on sustainable supply chain management by researchers was mentioned by Carter and Rogers (2008) who suggested spending full-time onsite observing supply chain operations of companies will enable the investigator gain deep insight on corporate beliefs and influences for initiating SCM. Anderson (1994) after observing the usefulness and contribution of ethnographic investigation into organisations, asserted ethnography to be a complex and subtle practice.

Table 3.2 Comparison of philosophical positions positivism and interpretivism

	Positivism	Interpretivism
Ontology	Reality is real and apprehensible, external and independent. One true reality (universalism) Granular (things) Ordered	Reality is complex, rich socially constructed through culture and language. Multiple meanings, interpretations, realities. The flux of processes, experiences, and practices.
Epistemology	Scientific method Observable and measurable facts. Law-like generalisations. Numbers. Causal explanation and prediction as a contribution. Objectivists: findings are true.	Theories and concepts are too simplistic. Focus on narratives, stories, perceptions, and interpretations. New understandings and worldviews as contributions. Subjectivist: created findings
Axiology	Value-free research	Value-bound research.

	The researcher is detached, neutral, and independent of what is researched. The researcher maintains an objective stance	Researchers are part of what is researched, subjective. Researcher interpretations key to contribution Researcher reflexive.
Methods	Typically, deductive, highly structured, large samples, measurement, typically quantitative methods of analysis, but a range of data can be analysed.	Typically, inductive. Small samples, in-depth investigations, qualitative methods of analysis, but a range of data can be interpreted.

adapted from Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, (2019:144)

3.2.3 Critical Realism

Column 4 and column 5 of table 4.1 support an epistemology of critical realism which sees reality from 3 perspectives: “The real, the actual, and the empirical”. The real assumes that which exists independence of our understanding and experience of it. The actual signifies the events or non-event generated when the real is activated. The empirical indicates what is observed or experienced” (Sayer, 2000). Thus, according to critical realists “although a real world exists, our knowledge of it is socially constructed and the events we experience and wish to explain are causally generated by the structures of the underlying systems” (Mingers, 2003). Critical realism is differentiated from positivism in that, it distinguishes the actual and the real in that the actual does not completely represent the real. Elsewhere, critical realism is recommended as appropriate for operations research that allows operations researchers to take a positivist stance, whilst accepting critics of naive positivism; it incorporated natural and social sciences encompassing the hard and soft approaches; potentially, it fits the reality of operations research as an applied discipline (Mingers,2003).

3.2.4 Philosophical Considerations of SCM

Research in sustainable supply chain management prevailed by the hard and soft branches of the system theory (Naim et al., 2004). However, the literature suggests a dominance of the hard system in supply chain management investigations prevalence by positivism research (Peck, 2005). A structured literature review by Burgess et al. (2006), also found this dominance. They argued that this dominance might restrict the field to a single paradigm, limiting its potential for further development. They further encourage researchers in SCM to use a plurality of paradigms and to incorporate research methods other than the positivist. This suggestion is backed by several researchers promoting the soft system view (also see Voss et al., 2002). Researchers are encouraged to carry out supply chain management investigations in context and to adopt an all-inclusive and interdisciplinary perspective. A review by Ansari and Kant (2017) finds quantitative methods dominate SCM research design investigations but incorporating sustainability elements entails social desirability making it less suited for quantitative research. Thus, qualitative research is ideal as it contributes to the field due to its richness and focus on gathering and analyzing data.

Seuring and Müller (2008), asserted that SSCM researchers do not often clearly state if a more positivist or a social science-based approach is used to characterised investigation. Based on the assertion above Golicic et al. (2012) proposed that researchers in SSCM should incorporate a more balanced approach that allows for more interpretivist techniques compared to conventional naive positivist techniques in SSCM investigations.

3.2.5 Philosophical Stance for This Research

The research investigates social sustainability in the context of SCM. Social sustainability perspectives provide an analysis of products and process aspects that have a direct or indirect influence on human safety, welfare, and wellness of people. Notable factors related to social

sustainability perspectives include motivations and engagements. Therefore, an interpretative approach suits the investigation based on the exploratory nature of the study's purpose. Social sustainability perspectives suggest either one or more of the following ontological positions is fitted for the investigation: “reality as a projection of human imagination”, “reality as socially constructed” and “reality as a realm of symbolic discourse”.

The ontological assumption of “reality as a projection of human imagination,” assumes a phenomenological philosophy is required (Saunders et al., 2019). Phenomenologist uses participants' social behaviour, context, and close analysis of “live experience”, and are time-consuming to gain a deeper understanding of the social study (Stark and Trinidad, 2007; Saunders et al, 2019). Also, the insight generated from phenomenology rests on multiple subjective experiences (Morgan and Smircich, 1980), which supports methods such as multiple case studies and peer observation.

The ontological assumption for “reality as a realm of symbolic discourse” supposes an ethnographic philosophy that requires extensive research experience (Anderson, 1994). However, since the focus of the investigation is an inter-organisational relationship, adopting an ethnographic approach for the investigation will require the researcher full-time on-site and a long period of observation of the focal companies and their supply chains.

The ontological position of reality as socially constructed is recognized by this investigation and necessitates the adoption of a hermeneutics-based approach. The nature of social sustainability suggests hermeneutics suits research on social sustainability aspects. The development of social sustainability perspectives is a socially constructed, emergent, and complex process (Lauring and Thomsen, 2009; Thomsen and Lauring, 2008). Also, context plays a significant role in social sustainability initiatives. In addition to that, the role of context is emphasized as essential for theory generation and insight into SSCM practice (Blome et al.,

2013). Hermeneutics fits the investigation of social sustainability perspectives as it focuses on analysing the process via which social reality is created (Morgan and Smircich, 1980). Taking into consideration the context and organisational history of the issue being investigated, the main ontological position chosen for the investigation views reality as a social construct, and a hermeneutics-based approach to the inquiry is used for the investigation. In addition to this, the research combines certain elements of phenomenology (didn't intend to explore live and multiple subjective experiences but rather to gain knowledge of how focal firms develop and implement their social sustainability initiatives) and ethnography (data will be collected on-site and observation of the focal firms not to explore the cultural phenomena of focal firms but to explore the various approaches these firms use on social sustainability) due to their benefits for this research.

3.3 Research Design

This is an important guide essential for the researcher in the process of gathering and analysing data, and the significant relationships between the theory and argument that informed the study. It suggests priority is given to a variety of choices in the research process (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Yin (2009) is a careful plan that links field data to the primary research questions and conclusion of a study. A blueprint for the investigator to identify components of the research like what question to research on, the kind of data to gather, and how the data can be analyzed.

3.3.1 Research Methods

The choice of a particular method for a scientific investigation is often based on either the purpose of the investigation, the problem statement for the investigation, or questions to be answered in the investigation (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Philosophers highlight three methods of scientific investigation: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods (Yin, 2009).

Qualitative investigation supposes an interpretive, natural, and holistic way of scientific investigation of a social phenomenon in its natural environment (Creswell, 2013). It is ideal for generating new insight into existing theories as it uses participants' live experiences, attitudes, beliefs, knowledge, and understanding (Saunders et al., 2007).

Quantitative research methods are ideal for testing hypotheses, investigating variables, collecting numerical data, and using statistical analysis to gain insight into the phenomenon by establishing a relationship between dependent and independent variables. A key aspect of quantitative analysis is the establishment of relationships, associations, and trends between variables (Stockemer, 2019). A quantitative analysis approach was not ideal for this research because the research does not test for relationships, associations, or trends among variables using statistical analysis to address the study question.

A mixed methods inquiry supposes the combination of both quantitative and qualitative methodologies that is hypothesis testing using statistical analysis and flexibility of qualitative analysis to investigate a social phenomenon. Mixed method studies adopt open-ended questions to explore the subject of study and numerical analysis to establish correlations and relationships (Archibald and Gerber, 2018). A mixed method was not considered for this study as the research didn't use numerical analysis. The research focused on gaining deep and rich insight into participants' real-life experiences knowledge and understanding of the social phenomena under investigation in addition to the extant literature and corporate documents. The researcher didn't develop a hypothesized model or collect numerical information to explore the implementation of social sustainability in improving supply chain management in the agricultural sector and develop a framework to implement social sustainability in supply chain management. Therefore, adopting a mixed or quantitative approach was less ideal than considering a qualitative approach.

3.3.1.1 Methodological Approach – Qualitative

The study adopts a qualitative research method in the research design to explore the implementation of social sustainability in improving supply chain management. Qualitative design uses a range of methods for gathering data to give a diverse perspective of the phenomenon under investigation (Maxwell, 2013). This method uses open-ended questions via in-depth interviews to explore participant insights on the social phenomenon and company documents to corroborate insight gained from interviews. Miles and Huberman (1984) describe it as a research process where the investigator makes sense by comparing, contrasting, replicating, cataloguing, and classifying the object of study. Saunders et al., (1997) view it as being based on “meanings expressed through words, [the] collection of results in non-standardized data requiring classification into categories, [and the] analysis conducted through the use of conceptualisation”. This approach is distinguished by richness and fulness due to the opportunity to explore participants in their real-life context using the thick description (Creswell, 2013). A thorough abstraction of qualitative data. The usefulness of qualitative methods can be seen in their ability to understand beliefs, meaning, or experiences as opposed to quantitative methods which struggle with such understanding (Wisker, 2001). The research adopts a qualitative approach to explore how companies implement social sustainability in improving their supply chains. The qualitative method was appropriate as it allowed the use of open-ended questions to explore the knowledge of participants to collect rich data from the participants and gain an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon.

Saunders et al. (2007) research Onion is a valuable tool that can guide the researcher ensuring that the required decisions before data collection are made. It involves the decisions that the researchers need to consider involving philosophies, research approach, strategies available for them, choice of methods, and possible timeframe. Using the research onion, this research is cross-sectional, a case study, and an inductive approach using an interpretative philosophy.

3.4 Research Strategy

The research strategy is a general plan for carrying out a logical investigation of a subject of interest (Marshall and Rossman, 1999). Every research strategy comes with its own pros and cons particular to it. Benbasat (1987) commented that: “no strategy is more appropriate than all others for all research purposes”. Yin (2008) emphasis that research strategies should be developed based on: “(a) the kind of questions been asked, (b) the extent of control an investigator has over actual behavioural events and (c) the degree of focus on contemporary or historical events”. Benbasat (1984) attributes the choice to the goals of the researcher. Marshall and Rossman (2010) to the research purpose and Benbasat 1987; Creswell, 2013; Marshall and Rossman (2010) to the nature of research questions. Table 4.3 is used as a guide in choosing a research strategy.

Table 3.3 Choosing appropriate research strategy.

Purpose of the Research	Research Question	Research Strategy	Data Collection Technique
<p>Exploratory To investigate little-understood phenomena. To identify and discover important variables. To generate a hypothesis for further research</p>	<p>What is happening in the social program? What are the salient themes, patterns, and categories in participant meaning? How are these patterns linked to one another?</p>	<p>Case study Field study</p>	<p>Participant observation In-depth interviewing Elite interview</p>
<p>Explanatory To explain the forces causing the phenomenon in question</p>	<p>What events, beliefs, attitudes, and policies are shaping these phenomena?</p>	<p>Multi-site case study History Field study Ethnography</p>	<p>Participant observation In-depth interviewing Survey questionnaire Document’s analysis</p>

To identify plausible and casual networks shaping the phenomenon	How do these forces interact to result in the phenomena?		
Descriptive To document the phenomenon of interest	What are the salient behaviours, events, beliefs, attitudes, structures, and processes occurring in this phenomenon?	Case study Field study Ethnography	Participant observation In-depth interviewing Document analysis Unobtrusive analysis Survey
Predictive To predict the outcomes of the phenomenon. To forecast the events and behaviours resulting in the phenomenon.	What will occur because of these phenomena? Who will be affected? In what ways?	Experiment Quasi-Experiment	Survey Kinesics/Proxemics Content analysis

Adapted from Marshall and Rossman, (1999: 33)

3.4.1 Research Strategy: Case Study

A case study strategy is adopted for this investigation. Yin (2018) described case research “as an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon in depth and within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not evident”. Therefore, a case study research strategy is essential when the scientific inquiry seeks to investigate an organizational social phenomenon with an empirical focus. Coupled with the use of an inductive approach, will enable the development of theory in this area of research.

Some critical factors need to be considered for case study research to be valid Yin (2003) these include: “(1) the case study must be significant to be “exemplary”. That is the selected case or cases must be unusual and of general public interest [whereby] the underlying issues are

nationally important, either in theoretical terms or in policy or practical terms; or both preceding conditions have been met. (2) case study inquiry must be complete, must consider many more variables of interest than data points, relies on multiple sources of evidence, with data needing to converge in a triangulating fashion and must be engaged in a composed manner”.

Case studies are significant for in-depth analysis compared to other methods (Yin, 2008), enabling complete exploration of the situation (Wisker, 2001). Emory and Cooper (1991) also argued case study to be a useful strategy for exploring theory or an enabling source for developing new hypotheses.

In addition to the in-depth analysis for the case study investigator, it also provides a “rich multi-dimensional picture of the situation being studied, illustrating relationships, corporate political issues and other patterns of influence in that particular context”. They are crucial for contemporary issues (social sustainability) as they use real-life contexts in the emerging business and management world (Remenyi et al., 1998).

3.4.1.1 Justification of Case Study as a Research Strategy for This Study

An exploratory multi-case study is the selected choice of research strategy for this study. Exploratory is necessary for the investigation because research on social sustainability is underexplored and its construct is still to be clearly defined and delineated (Yin, 2008). Case studies have been used extensively in complex management practices that are: “an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon in depth and within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not evident” (Yin, 2008; Eisenhardt and Graebner, 2008). This is recommended for social sustainability investigation based on its complex and multifaceted perspectives as well as in the development of conceptual

models (Brandenburg et al., 2014; Seuring, 2008). The flexibility of the case study allows the researcher to have some degree of control over the events enabling data access at any stage using a flexible and standardized data collection procedure and seeking answers to why, what, and who questions in the real-life context of the social phenomena (Seuring 2005, 2008). Also, multiple case study allows the researcher to gain in-depth insight into phenomena and a clear picture of the “locally grounded causality” (Eisenhardt and Graebner, 2008). Offers an extensive framework for data gathering, and increases the generalisability of the data gathering procedure ensuring more convincing data is gathered (Miles and Huberman, 1994). The researcher intends to explore multiple bounded systems used by focal firms to implement social sustainability in improving supply chain management, a multiple case research was appropriate to a single case. The qualitative multiple-case research was ideal for this investigation as it allowed the researcher to identify approaches used by the companies in implementing social sustainability to improve supply chain management performance.

Despite the significance of adopting case studies, they are criticized for their difficulty in generalized from a single case so “either the case needs to be contextualized and carefully described and then others can consider its usefulness in other contexts or can take a range of cases to establish a range of examples or interpretations of a situation” (Wisker, 2001). Thus, this study needs to ensure its transferability to another context. Also, if the study is too generalisable, subsamples will lack representativeness in the research setting. Yin (2003) for instance emphasised that case studies like experiments can be: “generalisable to theoretical propositions and not to populations or universes”. To ensure the generalisability of this study, the study adopts multiple cases to establish a range of examples or interpretations of the social phenomena that is, it follows the logic of literal and theoretical replication.

In addition to the lack of case generalisation, another challenge is the lack of case rigour (Yin, 2003). Eisenhardt (1989) stresses the significance of a rigorous methodology in case study investigations. The designing of precise and measurable constructs is crucial for theory building. Thiruchelvam and Tookey (2011) further emphasised the reliance on analytical inferences rather than statistical inference in case studies. And argued that for analytical inference to be achieved, logical coherence in the research procedure must be consistent and adequately essential for quality in case study research. Seuring (2008) called for the necessity of case research rigour in SSCM. The five-stage case study research rigour process designed by Stuart et al. (2002) is demonstrated in Figure 3.1. In practice, the actual process is elastic and highly iterative allowing the repetition of certain stages during the research (Seuring et al., 2008) considered a major strength for case studies (Yin, 2003).

Figure 8 The Five-Stage Research Process Model (Adapted from Seuring, 2008)

Couples to the research process, theories, and conceptual framework have also been highlighted as vital by researchers. Eisenhardt, (1989) for instance emphasized the familiarity with extant theories in the researcher's domain. Further elaborated that a deep understanding of the literature guides the researcher to connect results back to the literature and unfold them into previous publications, as well as the theoretical contributions made (Easterby-Smith et al., 2008). It guides the researcher on what is known in the field and where to situate the research (Silverman, 2009). Miles and Humberman (1994) assumed a conceptual framework makes the investigator selective. Thus, it saves time during data collection and eases cross-case analysis.

To achieve rigour in this research, a five-stage case research procedure is developed (research questions, instrument development, data collection, data analysis, and dissemination) to ensure logical coherence and consistency in the research. The researcher also explored the extant literature for a thorough understanding of the phenomena that is social sustainability in supply chain management and to guide the focus of the research. Couple that, the research adopts necessary theories to advance management understanding of the concept and finally, a conceptual framework is developed to help achieve analytical inferences and quality in this study.

3.4.2 Instrument Development

3.4.2.1 Unit of Analysis

Defining the unit of analysis is emphasized as the most vital component in case study research (Yin, 2003). The units of analysis are critical for case replication and comparison (Yin, 2013). Seuring (2008) argued that to gain a richer insight into the sustainable supply chain management field, researchers need to clearly define units of analysis and field works on different levels of the supply chain since ecological problems and social equity can happen at any level in the supply chain. By doing this, the investigator defines the research boundaries, and this should be linked to the original research question. Thus, the unit of analysis is considered a main factor influencing the selection criteria. The unit of analysis for this research is large agribusiness companies in Cameroon that have actively engaged in implementing social sustainability initiatives in their supply chains. The researcher conducted semi-structured interviews with informants who have sufficient knowledge and experience on social sustainability and sustainable SCM.²³ interviews we conducted from multiple organisations with informants representing various positions demonstrating the subject of interest.

3.4.2.2 Sampling

Sampling according to Benbasat et al. (1987) is: “the selection of a fraction of the total number of units of interest to decision makers for the ultimate purpose of being able to draw general conclusions about the entire body of units”. Sampling helps to conclude the research objectives and it is unrealistic to survey the entire population. This research adopts purposeful sampling methods essential for selecting the subjects of interest with rich insight. Purposeful sampling is a technique used by researchers to select a fraction of the unit of interest to unveil knowledge, experience, and understanding of a social phenomenon (Shaheen and Pradhan, 2019). Purposeful sampling has often been used in case study investigations to explore the particular interest of a social phenomenon. The technique is particularly useful when the supposed unit of analysis exceeds the number of participants required for the minimum sample size (Eisenhardt, 1989). The objects of study in this research were selected based on knowledge and demonstration of the topic of interest. Adopting purposeful sampling in this research is appropriate when the unit of analysis must meet certain requirements (Campbell et al., 2020). Coupled with that, the consideration of purposeful sampling by researchers to select the unit of analysis should align with the study questions. This research considered the purposeful sampling technique as the most appropriate for this investigation. In addition to purposeful, the researcher also used snowball sampling which involved build-up sampling through a participant most likely to happen as the research unfolded.

3.4.2.2.1 Criteria for Case Selection

The researcher selected appropriate agribusiness companies that demonstrated active engagement on sustainability initiatives in their supply chains and there is community awareness of these initiatives. To make sure this study can be generalised, the researcher

ensured the selected case organisations take the nature of the research study, as well as follow the logic of literal replication (cases are selected to predict similar results) and/or theoretical replication (cases are selected to predict contrasting results but for theoretical reasons) (Yin, 2013). Coupled with that, the selection of multiple cases ensured purposefully varied case situations were linked (Lewis, 1998). Moreover, Benbasat et al., (1987) emphasis the need for organisational characteristics for case selection when investigating organisational phenomena including: “industries, organisational sizes, organisational structures, ownership types, geographic coverage, and degrees of vertical or horizontal integration”. This research considered large locally based companies with supply chain power in the agribusiness sector. While the literature emphasis the need to conduct context-specific research in LMICs on SSCM (Ashby et al., 2012; Yawar and Seuring, 2015), this research was conducted in the context of Cameroon where agribusiness companies demonstrate increasing integration of social sustainability in their supply chains. A total of six carefully selected cases were approached for this research. However, 5 cases were granted access, and 1 case declined the request for privacy reasons.

3.4.2.2.1.1 Number of Cases

While the number of cases remains a necessary consideration for a multi-case study design, Yin (2008) proposed that, since in a multi-case design the logic of replication and not sample size technique is employed, therefore, sampling size technique is not applicable for multi-case design research. Patton (1990) attributes the validity of qualitative studies to the data richness of the selected case organisations and the investigators' analytical abilities. Therefore, the sample is an important factor but not the most relevant criterion for validity in qualitative case study research. However, no specific standard is set for the number of cases, but certain criteria are recommended for instance, Yin (2008) suggested the number of cases should be based on

the kind of results the research wants to achieve. Similarly, Eisenhardt and Graebner (2008) relate the number of cases to the point where saturation is reached. Based on research experience by scholars, the number of cases ranges between 2 to 4 and 10 to 15 as the minimum and maximum ranges (Eisenhardt, 1989; Miles and Huberman, 1994; Perry, 1998). Perry (1998) suggested 3 to 6 case organisations generate 35 to 50 interviews for doctorate research. Taking into consideration the above suggestion, this research adopts 5 organisations and 2 to 6 participants per organisation to generate 23 interviews for this research project. 5 carefully selected and discrete organisations with varying sustainability characteristics were selected for the information richness of the case organisation. The number of cases chosen reflects an accepted range for multi-case study research and facilitates cross-analysis among cases (Yin, 2014). This is essential to ensure the replication of results across the carefully selected case organisations and to analyse theoretical and empirical variables across case organisations (Yin, 2008). However, the purpose for selecting these cases rests on the possibility of observing the concepts (social sustainability) across the different case organisations.

3.4.2.2 Criteria for Interviewee Selection (23)

Research informants are one of the most critical aspects of qualitative investigations. The quality and the outcome of the research results are highly dependent on the data provided by the informants (Yin, 2018). For reliability and accuracy, researchers select informants with deep insight, experience, and understanding of the social phenomena of interest (Patton, 1990). This research ensured that the informants selected reflected the eligibility criteria. In applying this method, the researcher ensured the selected informants with sufficient knowledge and experience on social sustainability and SSCM were identified as appropriate for this research. To eliminate aspects of elite bias, within each case organization, multiple

interviewees were selected from various positions at the strategic, managerial, and operational levels. In addition, as the interviews unfolded most informants were recommended by other informants due to the sufficient knowledge and experience, they possessed on the subject of interest. From the five case organizations, 23 interviews were generated to achieve the research purpose.

3.4.2.3 Main Case Studies

Table.4.4 Characteristics of case study firms

Characteristics	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
Industry	Agro-industrial	Food and Agri-business	Food and Agri-business	Food Processing	Agro-industrial
Size	Large	Large	Large	Large	Large
The geographic focus of Customers	Local and regional level	International	Local and international	Local and international	Local and international
B2B/B2C	B2C & B2B	B2B	B2B & B2C	B2C & B2B	B2C & B2B
Basis of Competition	Quality and Efficiency	Premium, high-quality products	Market segmentation: good value to high-quality	Market segmentation: services and quality	Quality
Type of Manufacturing	Semi-automated and capital intensive	Labour intensive agricultural production	Semi-automated	Semi-automated and capital intensive	Labour intensive and semi-automated

- The Company's names are replaced for privacy reasons.
- Large companies are companies with over 500 employees.

Case 1 a Cameroonian-based company, started in 1948, leading the agro-industrial sector in Cameroon and involved in the production of food beverages as an efficient-modern citizen organization. In addition to food beverages, Case 1 has a diversified product portfolio including packaging solutions, Mineral water, and feed production. The company has over 7000 employees. To sustain its operations and remain competitive, Case 1 has a Quality Management

System (QMS) for continuous improvement and constantly modernizing its management system to ensure its commitment to promoting a culture of quality. To achieve its goals Case 1 is ISO 9001, FSSC 22000, and ANOR certified.

Case 2 is part of a multinational joint venture founded in 1990 that operates globally in the production, sourcing, and exportation of cocoa and coffee beans. Case 2 showcases its sustainable development strategic objectives necessary for its business success are based on its positioning at the start of the supply chain: 1) no poverty, 2) decent work and economic development, 3) zero hunger and sustainable agriculture, 4) access to portable and clean water, 5) quality education, 6) women empowerment and 7) climate action and life on land. It undertakes sustainability initiatives to improve farmers' livelihood, community well-being, and environmental protection. Case 2 constantly conducts supplier capacity-building programs and sustainability certification training.

Case 3 is a food production multinational company that started its operations in Cameroon in 1995 and is one of the largest in the country with over 1900 employees. Case 3 activities are the production, procurement, and export of cocoa and coffee beans, grains, and rice. Case 3 is a major player in addressing Cameroon's food security needs and at the same time achieving positive impacts for farming communities. Case 3 sustainability measures are not for commercial purposes but for improving productivity, through quality, quantity, and stability in supplies. Case 3 recognises transparency and traceability to be critical for minimising social and environmental risk.

Case 4 is a multinational company that started its operations in Cameroon in 1980. The company has about 3500 employees. The company produces food, beverages, and health solutions. Its sustainability initiatives are geared towards creating shared values through commitments to regenerative agriculture, farmers' livelihoods and child labour risks, and the environment with the potential to impact a wide range of interconnected issues.

Case 5 is a multinational company with over 35 years of operation in Cameroon and has over 2000 employees in Cameroon. The company started as a small rubber-producing factory in 1936. Today it produces rubber, palm oil, and seeds. The mission of the company is “to keep improving tropical agriculture in a responsible, sustainable, and innovative way.” The company collaborates and provides training to smallholder plantations and develops an efficient and adapted response to economic development and food security issues taking into consideration environmental protection practices. In return, this approach helps to rebuild local agriculture while addressing economic, social, and environmental concerns.

3.4.2.4 The Case Study Protocol

This is one of the techniques used for addressing issues of “reliability and validity of case-study research data” (Yin, 2003). This is an important tool for multi-case studies. It acts as a quick reminder and checklist during an interview to ensure every aspect considered for the research is covered (Voss et al., 2002). The protocol is particularly helpful in the process of gathering empirical data. Notwithstanding the formal procedures followed in case study research, the empirical data collected from case studies is difficult to decode. Thus, a well-developed plan is required to ensure relevant questions are asked of the informants relating to

the phenomenon under investigation throughout the whole data collection exercise to make sure relevant data are gathered. The protocol for this research can be found in the Appendix A

3.5 Data Gathering

The empirical data for qualitative studies can be collected from a multitude of sources such as interviews, documents, participant observation, archival data, etc., (Yin, 2013). And further emphasised the strengths and weaknesses associated with each source. However, Yin (2008) suggested the use of different sources of data collection for triangulation to enable the development of converging lines of inquiry. Triangulating sources of evidence can have a substantial impact on the development of frameworks or propositions and add value to the study (Barratt et al., 2011). To identify links between strategic focus, evidence for this study was gathered via interviews and documents from the selected case organizations.

3.5.1 Instruments for Data Gathering

These are tools used by the researcher to gather evidential information for research projects. Yin (2013) highlighted the researcher as the first instrument for data gathering who is responsible for developing the research project. In this study, the researcher served as the first data-gathering instrument and used professional recording devices to capture informants' responses during interviews. The researcher used semi-structured interviews and assessed relevant company documents following guidance from the case study protocol. During the interviews, the steps highlighted in the study protocol were observed in conjunction with the interview guide. Seven open-ended semi-structured interview questions were asked (see Appendix A and B) nudging informants to reveal more information about social sustainability through documents like corporate policies and sustainability reports. Before interviews

informed consent was obtained through filling the informed consent forms through emails and onsite. The duration of the interviews was between 40 minutes to 1 hour 30 minutes. The data collected from the interviews was supported by documents from the case organizations.

3.5.1.1 Semi-Structured Interviews

These are some of the primary instruments used by qualitative researchers to gather information and insight from a population in a research study (Yin, 2018). Semi-structured interviews are particularly powerful in obtaining narrative information about participants' views in more depth. Research informants for this study were interviewed by the researcher to gather evidential information to get deep insight and understanding to capture the social phenomenon under investigation. As an instrument for gathering evidential information, semi-structured interviews provide valuable insights into human actions through verbal interaction (Yin, 2013). This research study used semi-structured interviews to collect in-depth evidential data about the research topic. The interviews were complemented with documents from the case organisation to provide in-depth information about the informant's beliefs and inner values. Thus, the use of multiple sources enabled richer data to be collected by the researcher. Yin (2008) suggested the use of different sources of data collection for triangulation to enable the development of converging lines of argument. Triangulating sources of evidence can have a substantial impact on the development of frameworks or propositions and add value to the study findings (Barratt et al., 2011).

To ensure the evidential information gathered and the process used is trustworthy for the credibility of the research results, the researcher ensured members' checking was achieved. That is a summary detailing the study results was sent to participants to review and validate the interpretation of the information gathered once the analysis was completed (Yin, 2018).

As qualitative research involves the use of interviews as an instrument, Yin (2013) warns about various aspects of bias that can be introduced in the research process such as the researcher's subjective judgment can take control and move away from the research purpose or posing questions to respondents that might change the direction of the interviews to validate their expectations rather than capturing the perspectives of the interviewee. To reduce bias, the researcher used the interview guide to set a scope on what data to be collected from the research participants. In addition, the case study protocol was used to enable an efficient and easy flow of the interview process.

3.5.1.2 Documents

Documents are used as a secondary instrument for gathering evidential data to corroborate data collected from semi-structured interviews in this research. The semi-structured interviews for this research were complemented with case organizations' documents to provide in-depth insight into respondents' inner values and beliefs. The researcher required two types of documentary information: 1) contextual documents, which were required to understand the case organization's background information; 2) specific documents, which are directly relevant to the research topic such as policies and procedures on sustainable SCM.

3.5.2 Data Gathering Technique

The empirical data collection for qualitative studies can be collected through a variety of techniques including interviews, documents, participant observation, archival data, site visits, websites, tape recording, etc (Yin, 2013). This is mainly done to guarantee quality and reliable data collection from the respondents. For this study, the researcher used the protocol as a guide starting with a script before and at the end of the interviews, gathering informed consent, and

gradually engaging with the open-ended questions as elaborated in the interview guide for each participant. In conjunction with the semi-structured interviews, the researcher reviewed other sources of information including case organisations' websites, reports, policies, and other important documents of informants. Yin (2018) suggested the use of multiple sources of information to enable triangulation of the data for the development of converging lines of argument. Triangulating sources of information can have a substantial impact on the development of frameworks or propositions and add value to the study (Barratt et al., 2011). The use of standardized data collection techniques which enable multiple sources of data collection is vital for the research to analyze data from different perspectives essential for the validity and credibility of the research results. When aspects of validity and credibility can be achieved in a research study, the study findings are considered to be trustworthy (Yin, 2013).

The main data collection technique for this research study is semi-structured interviews. The choice of semi-structured interviews allows for enough flexibility in approaching different participants and focusing on the unique situation of each case while gaining in-depth insight and understanding of the social phenomenon under investigation (Yin, 2013). Furthermore, the semi-structured interview allows the collection of empirical evidence based on subjective perceptions of how individuals perceive social reality. As a result, issues of bias are likely to be introduced by the researcher or participant during the interview process because of individual opinions. To eliminate issues of bias in this study, the researcher ensured member checking after the interviews and the case study protocol was used as a framework to connect with the participants, pose interview questions, and set the time for review and remarks. This enabled the smooth flow of the process.

Tape recording and footnotes are other important techniques used during the interview process to collect data to ensure the reliability and credibility of the collected data. This technique enables the transcript to be accurate while making sure all information provided by the

respondents is remembered. Audio recording during the interviews allows the researcher to focus on other aspects like observation (gestures, behaviours, body language) more accurately (Yin, 2013). The usefulness of tape recording also enables coding, analysis, and member checking which are vital for data analysis and credibility. Tape recordings and footnotes are how the researchers rechecked and replayed the data collected for credibility.

Documents are often used as a source and a technique for collecting evidential data in qualitative studies (Heesen et al., 2019). Data achieved from interviews is most times qualified with documentary information to improve data credibility, reliability, and dependability. In this study, published case organizations documented were reviewed including, annual reports, company journals on the research topic, website information, and other relevant information that was available online to triangulate interview data. This enabled the data collected from informants to be proven or contested. Reviewing documents and archival data are important sources of evidential information but gaining smooth access and the necessary information may be challenging (Noor, 2008). However, focusing on case organisations' documents only includes inaccurate, incomplete, or inaccessible documents (Heesen et al.,2019).

3.6 Data Analysis

Researchers have argued data analysis is the least explored but the most challenging aspect of case study inquiry (Yin, 2013). Data analysis is the process of transforming raw data collected to unveil its meaning and usefulness to a given project (Lester et al., 2020). It is necessary to break down the process of data analysis into different parts for ease of understanding and transparency of the process to the investigator and readers of the research project. Yin (2013) highlighted five steps for researchers to follow during data analysis (1) compiling, (2) disassembling, (3) reassembling, (4) interpreting, and (5) concluding. This study adopted Yin's

five-step data analysis process while using methodological triangulation. Methodological triangulation involves the use of more than one kind of method to study a phenomenon. It enhances confirmation of the findings, more comprehensive data, increased validity, and enhanced understanding of the phenomenon under investigation (Bekheret et al., 2012). In social science studies, methodological triangulation, coding, and thematic analysis have been used as techniques for data analysis. methodological triangulation has been achieved in the research study at the data collection stage (the use of semi-structured interviews and reviewing documents from the case organizations’).

a. Compiling

The compiling step supposes organizing and managing the data collected towards answering the research questions. Qualitative data often involve large and a large variety of data sets. Bingham (2023), highlights that effectively managing and organizing qualitative data supports the rigor and trustworthiness of the study. Thus, it is necessary to have well-structured organizational practices in place. Following Miles et al. (2020), on the reliance on deductive strategies to help data organization and management. Deductive or a priori coding entails codes developed before data analysis and applying those codes to the data (Miles et al., 2020). Deductive coding is used to organize data into predetermined categories generated from the literature review. Compiling data through deductive coding as purely organisational categories (e.g., the type of data or when it was collected), categorised based on the research purpose or questions, or as categorised based on the concept or theoretical framework. Data in this research was organised through a deductive strategy consisting of a form of organisational coding called “attribute coding” which is the first phase of coding where the transcribed interviews and documentary information were defined into categories to develop an organisational schema using Microsoft Word which could be imported into NVivo (that is the

researcher labeled evidential data using prior codes representing organizational categories to manage the data). This helped to keep track of the data and identify the sources to build trustworthiness. The researcher also carried out memoing during the attribute coding process. Memoing is a process of recording thoughts and notes throughout the research study (Bingham, 2023). Memoing helped the researcher to generate initial impressions and thoughts on the evidential information gathered and the analysis process.

b. Disassembling

The disassembling step involves sorting evidential information into relevant topical categories (Bingham, 2023). To achieve this step, the researcher relied on deductive analysis, a priori topic codes (drivers, measures for improvement, benefits, social dimension, etc.) aligned to the research purpose, research questions, and the framework that was developed and then the researcher carefully examined the data in detail to sort and organise the evidential information. This process is known as Descriptive codes – codes that cover extensive categories of interest characterizing questions/framework aligned with the study purpose (Yin, 2018). The researcher used this process to filter out relevant data memoing decisions on code development and keep a record of ideas to be developed.

c. Reassembling

Once the evidential information was grouped into categories aligned to the study questions and framework, in the earlier steps (one and two), then the reassembling step proceeded. This step is achieved in this study using an inductive analysis strategy. “Inductive analysis involves reading through the data and identifying codes, categories, patterns and themes as they emerge” (Miles et al., 2020). Common to inductive analysis is the process of open/initial coding (the researcher identifies and labels important concepts and patterns in the data) and continuous

comparative method (“the data is coded, compare data with data, codes with codes, and eventually condensed into categories, categories into themes and then themes into findings”). The researcher uploaded the categorised data into NVivo reviewed the evidential information within and across each category and developed codes to describe the data. While constantly comparing newly reviewed evidential information to previous ones to determine if the evidential information can be described to existing codes or if new codes can be created. Memoing in this step, helped the researcher to define code boundaries and identify ideas related to the research question.

d. Interpretation

The fourth step of interpretation is to develop the findings of the analysis. it entails giving meaning to the reassembled evidential information to determine the conclusions and implications of the findings. This step involves identifying patterns, themes, and findings (Bingham, 2023). To begin with, the codes were reviewed to identify patterns that emerged to create themes that are collapsing codes to create a few analytic concepts. Yin (2018) suggested that the use of themes facilitates the interpretation of current studies based on existing ones. Yin further cautioned that studies following the five steps to analyse evidential information, when reflecting on how data gathered relates to information in the literature, the research questions should be taken into consideration. Aligning themes from analysed evidential information to existing studies and the conceptual framework shows rigor in qualitative inquiries (Yin, 2013). As part of the five-step analysis process, the researcher compiled evidential information into categories, later disassembled into research questions and framework, and then reassembled to codes and themes in an iterative process. The goal of interpreting evidential information is to link back the developed themes to the literature and conceptual framework while contributing to knowledge and generating new ideas (Yin, 2013).

This research draws its findings and reports conclusions based on the interpretation of evidential information.

e. Concluding

The final step entails addressing the research questions or achieving the study purpose (Yin, 2018). Qualitative methods of data analysis often develop themes to explain the research findings and situate the themes to the literature and conceptual framework elaborating how the findings confirm or contradict previous studies. This important activity is particularly unique to qualitative researchers. This research study identified key themes by detecting and classifying the reoccurring ideas, phrases, and words drawn from research informants' responses, additional information gathered in member checking sessions, and documentary information from the case organisations. The researcher compared and contrasted the emergent themes to the conceptual framework to explain and publish the findings; and situate the findings in the literature.

3.6.1 Achieving Data Analysis for this Research.

Before starting the actual process of data analysis, provisional themes were developed following the literature review to guide the researcher in the actual coding process. This process ensured the researcher was linked back to the literature while enabling the flexibility to add new themes as they emerged. For example, when analysing supplier benefits as a result of the lead firm strategic implementation of social sustainability initiatives in the supply chain new themes that emerged included increased stakeholder trust, improved level playing field, economic opportunity, organisational learning, and supply chain performance (i.e., open/initial coding process). To ensure the quality of the code, before the initial coding process, the draft

of the open codes was sent to experts and supervisors to assess the coding structure after which coding continued from the transcribed interviews and documents.

Once each interview was completed and transcribed, common statements were identified and grouped into first-order codes. Documents were also coded to contextualize the researchers' understanding of the coded interviews. For instance, document data were essential to capture measurable outcomes and a timeline for the social initiatives from the case organizations. Necessary attention was given to ensure all data were carefully classified into the relevant categories (especially quotes from interviews). The researcher ensured that data relating to drivers of the social sustainability initiatives for example the external drivers and how to validate them as external drivers were classified as risk mitigation and financial gains. These were classified as first-order codes into categories based on the social initiatives which progressively increased in detail. For example, first-order themes such as market demand, competition, regulation, reputation, and competitive advantage, and Secondary stakeholders were later classified into second order as risk mitigation and financial gains and further to third order (external driver). The outcome was a result of theoretical categories correctly presenting the data (see Appendix G).

3.7 Data management

Data management remains a significant aspect of qualitative research and is considered integrally related to data analysis (Yin, 2013). Notwithstanding the frequent use of data management in qualitative inquiries, almost one-third of qualitative inquiries are faced with serious flaws in managing evidential information (Miles and Huberman, 1994). They suggested data management should be a well-documented process. Yin (2013) supports this assertion in developing a well-structured database. And relates the absence of a well-structured database to

be a significant setback in most case study investigations. Considering the huge volume of evidential information gathered, data management is considered an integral part of this research study. The fieldwork generated a substantial amount of evidential information using both hard and software tools like tape recorders, paper files, and electronic files in Microsoft Word and Excel. The physical management of evidential data involves printing, labelling, organizing significant peer review sources, and collecting hard copy evidential information. Once prepared, the information can be electronically uploaded to a computer and stored in folders. The folders included transcribed interviews, voice records, and the necessary case documents. Evidential information was coded anonymously using case organization and participant identifiers, the type of data collected, and the time and date. Structuring and defining the data content with labels and categorise ensures continuity, and credibility and provides a virtual database. This study developed and kept a well-structured database. Microsoft Word was used to organise evidential information collected, the electronic data remained password protected, and necessary back-ups were created using google drive and memory sticks.

NVivo software is an application often used by qualitative researchers to organise evidential data into clusters, categories, and themes. Researchers have used NVivo software to code data, perform structural analysis, retrieve, and compare data, and display data for cross-case analysis and interpretation (Mortelmans, 2019). This research used the NVivo 10 application to categorize collected data, perform structural data analysis, and retrieve, compare, and visualize data for interpretation. First, interview transcripts and case documents were grouped into relevant topical categories and uploaded into the NVivo 10 application to obtain computerized results for data disassembling and reassembling. Secondly, NVivo 10 was used to compare and contrast the results to identify emerging patterns and themes. Finally, the NVivo 10 application was used to group the themes and track the ideas from the findings.

3.8 Quality Criteria and Dissemination

Trustworthiness is considered a major aspect of qualitative research and qualitative researchers need to demonstrate the credibility of their studies (Creswell, 2013). Trustworthiness entails the overall perception of the quality of a research study. It includes aspects associated with the systematic rigor of the research design, the credibility of the researcher, the believability of the findings, and the applicability of the research methods (Rose and Johnson, 2020). Qualitative researchers have sought to improve trustworthiness through validity and reliability. Creswell (2013) “qualitative validity means the researcher checks for the accuracy of findings by employing certain procedure, while qualitative reliability indicates that the researcher’s approach is consistent across different researchers and different projects”. Rose and Johnson (2020) emphasised that “rather than just prescribing what reliability and/or validity should look like, researchers should attend to the overall trustworthiness of qualitative research by more directly addressing issues associated with reliability and/or validity”. Qualitative case study researchers have often adopted four common techniques: dependability, credibility, confirmability, and transferability of the evidential information and results of the inquiry (Yin, 2013). Despite most times a single-event occurrence, issues of reliability and validity should be considered throughout the entire period of the inquiry, as should concerns and expositions about the inquirers' subjectivity and reflexivity (Rose and Johnson, 2020).

a. Dependability

Dependability supposes consistency in data collection, and data analysis that is the whole research process and could be repeated (Rose and Johnson, 2020). To improve the dependability of qualitative inquiries, researchers use methodological triangulation and member checking. To demonstrate how significant research informants support the inquiry, member checking can be integrated as a process of validity where inquirers engage informants’ processes of correcting and reorienting inquirers and the development of qualitative data to

produce more representative analyses of the topic of interest (Rose and Johnson, 2020). Triangulation involves “recognizing multiplicity and simultaneity of cultural frames of reference providing a plurality of techniques to best ensure accurate description and presentation of a given situation” (Rose and Johnson, 2020). This research used member checking and methodological triangulation to enhance the dependability of this inquiry.

b. Credibility

Credibility in qualitative research supposes the extent to which the research results represent the essence of the evidential data and establishes whether the results accurately reflect the interpretation of the evidential information collected from the research participant (Megheirkouni and Moir, 2023). Credibility is considered a qualitative construct equivalent to internal validity. Qualitative researchers have used different strategies to establish rigor in their inquiries such as member checking, prolonged engagement, triangulation, purposive sampling, persistent observation, and referential adequacy, etc., (Megheirkouni and Moir, 2023). This research integrated the following aspects to enhance the credibility of this research. Member checking was carried out in this research as transcripts were sent to participants for review to confirm if the interviewee responses had been accurately interpreted and to provide additional information. The research also used multiple sources and methods simultaneously for data collection i.e., interviews and documents. In addition, the research used a purposive sample technique for case organization and interviewee selection.

c. Transferability

Transferable suppose the extent to which the findings of a research inquiry can be applied to another context. transferable is perceived to be equivalent to the generalisability of the research

(Meheirkouni and Moir, 2023). Transferability can be achieved by researchers providing a detailed description of the respondent in the inquiry and the process observed when performing the inquiry so the reader can decide whether to use the study or not as per the setting. Enough information must be gathered by the researcher for the inquiry such as time, location, and respondents to the reader whether the same results can be obtained with other respondents if the inquiry is repeated in other settings. The transferability of a research study can be improved by the researcher providing complete information on the evidential data collection methods and analysis (Yin, 2013). This research provides an extensive description of data collection instruments and techniques, respondents, and the results.

d. Confirmability

Confirmability is the extent of the acceptability of a research result and confirmed by other results. According to Tobin and Begley (2004), confirmability is “concerned with establishing that data and interpretation of the findings are not figments of the inquirer’s imagination but are derived from the data” (Meheirkouni and Moir, 2023). Confirmability asserts the accuracy and authenticity of the processes and results of the inquiry. A common aspect of confirmability is to mitigate issues of bias related to the research (Lyons et al., 2018). Qualitative researchers have used different strategies to enhance the confirmability of their research studies including interview debriefing, member checking, ethical approval, and data representativeness. This has been achieved and implemented in this research. Yin (2018) suggested inquirers should consistently document methodological procedures with the help of a well-structured research protocol and database to enhance confirmability to enable others to follow similar procedures. Inquirers should look for theories, data, or disagreeing information that run counter to themes or analyses developed in the research (Rose and Johnson, 2020). In demonstrating evidential information and proof that confirms and contests general assumptions of a theme, inquirers

enhance the validity of the claims made by their inquiries (Rose and Johnson, 2020). Detailed documentation of research processes and procedures is a means of improving the confirmability of the research results. This research thoroughly documented all the research processes and procedures, including data gathering, data analysis, and interpretation to maintain an audit trail as a means of ensuring confirmability.

Researchers have also attributed the validity of qualitative inquiries to the data richness of the selected case organizations. The research used semi-structured interviews and documents to gather evidential information from five carefully selected and discrete organisations with varying sustainability characteristics for the information richness of the case organisation. The number of cases chosen reflects an accepted range for multi-case study research and facilitates cross-analysis among cases (Yin, 2013). This is essential to ensure the replication of results across the carefully selected case organizations and to analyse theoretical and empirical variables across case organisations. The use of multiple sources of data gathering provided for methodological triangulation to establish a convergence of evidence while strengthening validity and reliability. The necessary publicly available and supporting case organisation documents were reviewed in this study including website data, case publications, and other information posted on the Internet to triangulate the interview data. Reviewing case documents is a means for researchers to confirm or refute evidential information collected from respondents during interviews to improve reliability and validity.

Table 3.5 Case study tactics, four design tests.

Test	Aim	Phase of research	Case study tactic	Implementation (in this research)
External validity	Defining the domain to which a study's findings can be generalized	Research design	Replication logic in multiple case studies	Both literal and theoretical replication were included in the case selection
Construct validity	Identifying correct operational measures for the concepts being studied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Data collection . Data collection . Data collection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Use multiple sources of evidence. . have key informants review draft case reports. 	Interviews and documents were used. Yes
Reliability	Demonstrating that the operation of a study can be repeated with the same results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Data collection . Data collection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . develop a case study database. . Use case study protocol 	A protocol was developed. A formal case database was developed.
Internal validity	Seeking to establish a causal relationship, whereby certain conditions are believed to lead to other conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Data analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Pattern matching . Explanation building . Rival explanations . Logic models 	Cross-case synthesis

Source: (Ellram (1996), Flint et al. (2002), Voss et al. (2002) and Yin (2008).

3.9 Ethical Consideration

3.9.1 Informed Consent

Before conducting the interviews, informed consent was sent through e-mail to the potential interviewees. According to Ritchie et al. (2013) informed consent must meet and satisfy these requirements: 1) the research purpose and scope, 2) introduce the investigator, 3) method for gathering empirical evidence, and 4) how the participants will participate, the length of the interview. The aspects of confidentiality and wilful participation should be spelled out in the

consent form. Interviews were carried out only after consent was obtained. Informants were also informed of the right to quit the research at any time if they wished to do so.

3.9.2 Anonymity and Confidentiality

Ensuring anonymity refers to protecting the identity of the participating parties outside the research team, and confidentiality that is avoiding the use of direct or indirect attribution of comments in reports or when presenting the findings in any way that can identify the participants (Ritchie et al., 2013). Anonymity and confidentiality are used at the organisational level and interviewee level. To ensure the anonymity of participants and the confidentiality of research data without impacting the research findings. The names of participating organisations and interviewees are anonymised in the data storage and case writing. For indirect attributes, special care needs to be taken. Ritchie et al., (2013) considered indirect attributes to characteristics collected that might be used to identify the participating parties.

The need for anonymity and confidentiality are also evident for data storage. Ritchie et al. (2013) suggest the use of codes to label record interviews and transcripts instead of using real names to ensure anonymity. Also, the identifying information (secondary data and interview list) is kept separately from the interview data.

3.10 Summary

In this chapter the philosophical background relative to the researched phenomenon has been discussed, the chosen research methodology, process, and procedures described relative to the research purpose, and the sampling method has been explained. I explained the case organization's participants' eligibility criteria, research method and design, population sampling, and ethical considerations. Further to this section is the description and usage of the

data collection instruments and techniques, data analysis procedures, and how reliability and validity were achieved. The following chapter discusses the research findings.

Chapter Four – Findings

4.1 Introduction

This qualitative multiple case study aimed to explore the strategic implementation of social sustainability in improving supply chain management in the agricultural sector of an LMIC and to develop and validate a framework for implementing improvement on social sustainability in supply chain management. I conducted semi-structured interviews in person from five carefully selected agribusiness case organisation differing in characteristics on supply chain sustainability with managers, directors, and departmental heads. Other data sources used for gathering evidential information comprised the relevant company sustainability and CSR policy, supply chain procurement policy, and documents from the case organisations. In addition to the review of the relevant literature.

4.2 Presentation of the findings

The findings are grouped and matched together were applicable to answer the study questions.

Table 9 Demographic Data of Respondents

Case Organisation Code	Participant Code	Function in the Organisation	Experience in years	Experience in Sustainable SCM (yes/no)
CO1	A1	Supply Chain Manager	16	Yes
	A2	CRS Manager	13	Yes
	A3	Director of the Quality, Health, and Safety Standards	Over 20	Yes
	A4	Operations Manager	8	Yes
CO2	B1	Supply Chain Manager	11	Yes
	B2	Head of Projects	10	Yes
	B3	Procurement Manager	12	Yes
	B4	Head of Community Support	16	Yes
	B5	Head of crop production	13	Yes
	B6	Sustainability Adviser	14	Yes
CO3	C1	Supply Chain Innovation & Partnerships	17	Yes

	C2	Communications Manager	7	Yes
	C3	Head of Environmental Management	8	Yes
	C4	Regional Child Labour Analyst	14	Yes
CO4	D1	Procurement Manager	9	Yes
	D2	Assistant Quality Control Manager	10	Yes
	D3	Quality Control Manager	15	Yes
	D4	Health and Safety Supervisor	8	Yes
CO5	E1	Operations Manager	18	Yes
	E2	Head of Smallholder Department	12	Yes
	E3	Sustainability Supervisor	17	Yes
	E4	Assistant Operations Manager	8	Yes
	E5	Logistics Manager	7	Yes

4.3 Research question 1 – What is the current trend of social sustainability in supply chain management in developing countries?

To capture the existing trends, table 2.1 developed from different studies conducted in developing countries on social sustainability in supply chain management where they are placed under the different aspects addressed as highlighted in Figure 9 below.

Figure 9 existing trends of social sustainability

With regards to the social dimensions, the analysis reveals aspects of labour conditions (LC) and decent work, society (S), product responsibility (PR), and human rights (HR) are the focus of social aspects in supply chains. Further analysis shows that there have been more focus LCs compared to the others. This might suggest firms are under pressure to consider issues of health

and safety and their impacts in reports. Aspects of human rights are still to be fully integrated as this continues to be a major issue, particularly in distant supply chains operating in poorer countries where most of the suppliers are foreign-based (Huq et al., 2014). It should be noted that most of these studies analysed social sustainability related to CSR indicating the need to identify the key aspect that should be explored to incorporate the four main social pillars.

In terms of the supply chain entities, studies have mostly considered individual entities. Research has mostly focused on upstream supply chain partners. Studies considering a holistic view of all supply chain tiers from the extraction of raw materials to return are very limited. The analysis shows that external stakeholders are missing when considering supply chain entities, especially the society aspect. This might lead to limited social sustainability integrations in the supply chain.

The analysis reveals most of the methodologies used to investigate social sustainability are exploratory suggesting a focus towards defining social sustainability and its integration in sustainability supply chain management activities. Building on this, a mix of methodologies has been adopted (qualitative, quantitative, and a combination of both methods) indicating a lack of agreement on the best method to analyse social sustainability.

The analysis of the companies' dimensions indicates that social sustainability practices have mostly been considered by larger and multinational companies with little or no interest in locally based companies both large, small, and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). This might suggest the need to explore social sustainability from the perspective of locally based companies and their collaboration with stakeholders.

Following the activity sector, the results reveal this has mostly followed those sectors that come under external stakeholders' pressure to address social sustainability issues in supply chains. Thus, the current focus is on a limited number of sectors for instance manufacturing.

This might suggest limited work on cross-analysis from different sectors and the need to develop common measures for social sustainability across the different supply chains.

The advancement in information and communication technologies and the growing interest in integrating them into supply chains have significantly improved issues of transparency at all stages in the supply chains. An increasing number of studies highlight the importance of identifying loopholes and addressing them, especially on issues of noncompliance with to code of conduct. However, this is yet to be fully exploited. But there has been emphasises on the need to integrate them as critical resources for information sharing.

The focus on the analysis of risk and uncertainty is a response move from growing stakeholders' interest in social sustainability issues. The literature suggests to best capture aspects of risk and uncertainty all supply chain tiers must be considered. However, the social dimension has not been focused on risk and uncertainty but rather under the umbrella of organizational sustainability particularly on aspects related to codes of conduct. The general view is that risk associated with noncompliance affects both the firms and the society. This calls on the need for the assessment of social impacts and the need to develop frameworks to efficiently assess risk and uncertainty related to social sustainability and evaluate compliance with to code of conduct.

4.4 Research question 2 – What are the drivers, principles, and barriers to social sustainability and how do these contribute to the operational performance of the entire agricultural supply chain in Cameroon?

4.4.1a Social Dimensions

With regards to social dimensions, the results showed that activities of health, safety, and wellbeing were mentioned by all the five researched case organisations and appeared in at least one of the social initiatives launched by the researched organisations. Participants emphasized social sustainability practices like ensuring the health, safety, and hygiene of workers, contractors, and anyone else impacted by the firm's activities, and compliance with safety standards. The companies' responsibility to deliver safe end products is also mentioned. In addition, some suggested that providing health coverage helps improve employee social wellbeing. Despite support from scholars on best practices related to safety, safe movement of products to facilities, and social sustainability, this study's results show that social aspects related to safety and health differ in LMICs. Poverty alleviation was also emphasised as key social aspect by the respondent for the case organisations to achieve their sustainability goals. Poverty alleviation was present in six of the twenty-six social initiatives. Participants mentioned aspects of economic and humanitarian measures to lift people in a community out of poverty, sourcing from poor farmers in local sourcing communities and incorporating the poor as suppliers as a mechanism for supporting poverty alleviation.

Table 10 Dimensions of Social Sustainability

Social Aspects	Measures	Case Organisation
Ethics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usage of non-hazardous material. • Not allowing the use of sub-standard materials in production. • Eliminating all unethical practices (anti-competitive behaviors, bribery, coercion, and pollution). 	CO5, CO4, CO3, CO1, CO2
Equity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity and inclusion. • Gender balance and equal opportunity. • Non-discrimination. 	CO5, CO4, CO3, CO2, CO1
Human rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prohibition of child labour forced labour and modern slavery. • Respect for rights and freedom of association. • Ensuring appropriate labour working conditions. • Protecting labour rights. 	CO5, CO4, CO3, CO2, CO1
Education and training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education and training for skills enhancement and development. 	CO1, CO2, CO3, CO5
Health, safety, and wellbeing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health coverage. • Ensuring the health, safety, and hygiene of workers, contractors, and anyone else impacted by firms' activities. • Provision of safe end products (food safety system). • Compliance with health and safety standards. 	CO5, CO4, CO3, CO2, CO1
Product responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product labelling. • Regulatory compliance. • Safety and health of the customer. • Customer privacy. • Friendly packaging. 	CO5, CO4, CO3, CO2, CO1

Poverty alleviation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We identify economic and humanitarian measures to lift people in a community out of poverty. • A critical aspect of this initiative is to alleviate poverty in the local sourcing community to achieve our sustainability goals. • We incorporate the poor as suppliers as a mechanism for supporting poverty alleviation. 	CO1, CO4, CO5
Community involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extending help to local communities in building educational establishments and training centres. • Training and education for local youth to gain skills and employment. • Local supplier development. • empowering women for entrepreneurship. • Construction of health centres, and hospitals and conducting health campaigns for health and hygiene. • Extending help in sustainable farming. • Construction of potable drinking water. 	CO5, CO4, CO3, CO2, CO1
Philanthropy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offering donations to educational institutions, NGOs, and religious organizations. • Construction and renovation of schools, colleges and educational institutions. 	CO5, CO4, CO3, CO2, CO1

Source: Empirical Data

The results suggest the significance of equitable practices particularly in improving issues of diversity and inclusion involving all communities, cultures, and ages in the workforce.

Participants emphasized these practices seek to leverage the diversity of thinking to drive creativity and innovation. Improving gender balance and providing equality opportunities were also mentioned and considered leading to social sustainability. Other aspects such as eliminating all forms of discriminatory practices denying privileges and rights because of origin, nationality, religion, race, gender, age, physical condition, sexual orientation, or engaging in or permitting any kind of harassment based on any of the above or for any other reason were combined and labelled under equity. These practices were addressed in all five researched case organisations and were present in 12 of the 26 social initiatives.

Participants discussed the significance of managing human rights issues and taking measures in relation to violations of human rights in their production facilities including child labour, forced labour, and modern slavery considered a top priority. In LMICs such as Cameroon, human rights violations i.e., bonded labour is mostly pronounced in smallholder activities. Similarly, issues related to the freedom and rights of association, such as participation in workers' unions and associations were emphasized by all 5 researched case organisations. Our results suggest aspects of human rights were addressed in 13 out of the 26 social initiatives.

When referring to ethical issues, our results show the use of non-hazardous and substandard materials for production and limiting all practices that might subject employees to involved in any unethical activities like anti-competitive behaviours, bribery, and pollution. Ten out of the 26 social initiatives addressed ethical issues. Product responsibility issues that relate to labelling, health, and safety of the consumer during usage, and consumer privacy were emphasized in ten of the social initiatives. Four out of the five researched case organisation appeared to have addressed issues of skill development, education, and training essential for organisation effectiveness in sustainability practices. These practices appeared in only five of the social initiatives.

Regarding community involvement, our results indicate nine of the social initiatives were related to activities such as sourcing directly from local partners or developing local supplies partners through capacity-building programs for sustainability practices, strengthening local communities by improving access to basic social amenities such as education, health and nutrition and breaking down barriers to economic empowerment such as training and supporting female entrepreneurship. Others discussed youth volunteering programs for skills enhancement and the creation of employment opportunities, the construction of hospitals, and conducting health campaigns to better health and access to hospital services in the local communities. Sustainable farming was emphasized to improve issues of malnutrition, and poverty and to diversify sources of income in the local sourcing communities. Improving access to potable drinking water sources in local communities was mentioned by informants because many workers still do not have adequate access to potable drinking water. Although the literature has addressed issues of housing, health, food security, and job creation in LMICs (Laire and Mont, 2010; Mani et al. 2016). Issues supporting sustainable farming to local communities, improving access to potable drinking water and the construction of health centres were particular in LMICs.

Finally, the results showed the enhancement of social issues through engagement in philanthropic activities like the construction and renovation of schools and hospitals in local manufacturing communities, and donating to NGOs, schools, and religious organisation. Six of the social initiatives were designed for social sustainability via philanthropic activities.

4.4.1b Correlation to the literature

The findings about the dimension of social sustainability align with the current literature (Mani et al., 2015; Yawar and Seuring, 2015; Mani et al., 2016b; Denu et al., 2023) and highlighted measures of social sustainability in SCM to include Human rights, equity, health and welfare, safety, ethics, and philanthropy. The results support Golicic et al., (2019) assertion that practices of social sustainability to highly contextual, time-dependent, and dynamic as the results confirm earlier studies conducted in LMICs that identified poverty alleviation and community involvement as major social dimensions to organisations (Denu et al., 2023). Therefore, actions for social sustainability initiatives are contingent upon the situation (Golicic et al., 2019). The results further support the assertion by Hajjar et al. (2019) that organisation have started giving priority to ameliorating rural livelihoods in developing countries. Thus, poverty remains a major global challenge to achieving the sustainable development goals. It has also led to social exclusion and inequality especially in developing countries (Hall et al., 2011).

Table 11 Social Initiatives driver, implementation criteria and the social relationship levels.

#	Case	Drivers		Principle for engagement		Relationship levels			
		Intrinsic	Extrinsic	Formalisation	Collaboration	Supplier	Internal operations	Customer	Society
1	CO1		X	X	X	X	X		
2		X		X			X		
3		X			X				X
4		X			X				X
5			X		X			X	
6		X			X				X
7		X			X				X
8	CO2		X		X	X			
9			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
10			X		X				X
11	CO3		X	X		X	X		
12			X		X	X	X	X	X
13		X			X	X	X	X	X
14			X	X		X	X		
15			X	X	X	X	X	X	
16			X	X				X	
17	CO4	X		X		X	X	X	X
18			X	X		X	X		
19		X			X				X
20		X		X		X	X	X	X
21	CO5	X		X	X	X	X		X
22			X	X		X	X		
23		X		X		X	X	X	
24		X		X		X	X	X	
25		X			X	X			X
26		X			X	X			X

Source: empirical data Mani et al., (2015)'s social relationship level

4.4.2a Drivers for Social Sustainability

It was evident that 14 out of the 26 social initiatives were influenced due to organizational values ethical principles, and top management moral standards (internal drivers). These initiatives involved practices including community involvement programs to break down barriers to economic development like empowering women to become financially autonomous and providing funding for community action plans on projects related to education, health, and nutrition. Addressing social sustainability issues like access to portable drinking water, and donations to hospitals with equipment and accessories to increase access to healthcare needs, especially for little children and pregnant women.

The remaining 12 out of the 26 social initiatives were influenced for risk mitigation and financial gains i.e., externally influenced social initiatives and related to practices such as capacity building for skills enhancement to boost the level of professionalism demanded by market actors and promoting initiatives that fight against human right issues like child labour, diversity, and inclusion. Educating on ethical standards across the supply chain. All 5 case organizations for the study mentioned at least one social initiative influenced by each of the drivers (internal or external driver).

4.4.2b Correlation to the literature

The results on the drivers for social sustainability implementation correspond to the existing literature on drivers in developing countries viewed from an internal-external perspective (Yin, 2017; Morais and Silvestre, 2018). The findings also, confirm the significant role stakeholders play in driving the adoption and implementation of social sustainability practices in this context (Mani et al., 2015; Mani and Gunasekaran, 2018; Fernando et al., 2022). The findings further align with Huq et al. (2014) on the three driving forces of social sustainability adoption and

implementation in SCM in developing countries including normative factors, cultural motivations, and regulatory influences. Studies in developing countries have revealed regulatory factors to be the most significant drivers in the context (Mani and Gunasekaran, 2018; Koksal et al. 2018). However, the results in this study contradict these findings that cultural and normative influence is the most significant influencing drivers of social sustainability initiative adoption and implementation. Thus, this result supports the assertion by Govinda et al. (2021) who argued regulatory drivers might not always be the most significant drivers. This research's reason for this observation to the fact decision decision-makers are starting to realise that instead of seeking temporary opportunities and risk it is better to create a long-term focus for permanent results.

4.4.3a Social Relationship Levels

On the social relationship level (Mani et al., 2015), from the results various levels of social relationships ranging from single to multi relationship were observed. The result showed one social initiative is related to suppliers only, one to internal operation, six to society, and two are related to consumers. Interestingly, we observed initiatives that engage simultaneously at different social levels. That is five social initiatives were engaged with internal operations and suppliers, two involved suppliers and society, one initiative engaged with internal operation, suppliers, and society, and three were related to supplier, internal operation, and customers. Finally, five social initiatives were linked to the four social levels i.e., internal operation, supplier, society, and consumer (see tab 11). The results suggest social sustainability initiatives across the supply chain tend to engage multiple stakeholders no matter the driver of the social initiatives (i.e., internal, or external) or the implementation criteria used (i.e., formalization or collaboration).

4.4.3b Correlation to the literature

The result on the social-relational level aligns with the work of Mani et al. (2015) and Morais and Silvestre (2018) who found that addressing social issues should consider entities beyond the focal firm boundary to include suppliers, consumers, and the community. But fail to consider other entities such as reverse logistics (Govindan et al., 2020; Bubicz et al., 2019). The findings also show that the current focus on the social entities of social sustainability initiatives is mainly on the forward supply chain. The literature argues that social initiatives targeting suppliers and buyers can be considered a risk transfer strategy by the focal firms aiming to avoid being held responsible for poor social issues in the supply chain (Klassen and Vereecke, 2012). Another possible assumption for this forward focus supply chain entities might be that the concept is still to be fully understood and integrated in the sector not alone mention the complexity associated with the social dimension of sustainability.

4.4.4a Principles for Engaging the Social Sustainability Initiatives

Regarding the principles for engaging the social initiatives, 11 of the 26 social initiatives are engaged based on collaborative mechanisms only (see table 11) that is partnering with stakeholders in developing monitoring programs to tackle child and forced labour; training and educating suppliers on compliance to social standards; safe working practices, supply diversity, and gender equality. Another 11 of 26 social initiatives were engaged through formalised mechanisms such as standard contractual agreements, business codes of conduct, and codes of ethics; dissemination of sustainability policies, sectoral or national or regional, or international pacts; creation of online platforms for managing social issues. Surprisingly 4 of the 26 social initiatives were engaged using both collaborative and formalised mechanisms which is evident at the upstream or downstream supply chain. It is important to note all case organisations

conducted at least one social initiative that is either governed by collaborative, formalised, or both mechanisms.

4.4.4b Correlation with the Literature

The findings noted about the principle for engaging social initiatives in supply chain management align with findings in the existing literature. Sancha et al. (2016) reported that “while assessment of suppliers improves the focal firms’ social performance, collaboration with suppliers enhances the supplier’s social performance”. The case organization (CO1) launched a social initiative that closely monitored and assessed its logistic partners to improve its social performance while at the same time collaborating with them to enhance knowledge and understanding to manage social issues in their operations. The research findings also align with Porteous et al. (2015) who revealed that supplier incentives through training and increased business opportunities compared to sanctions improve supplier violation and reduce focal operating costs. Many social initiatives were engaged through education, training, coaching, and incentive actions for improvement achieved through best-in-class theoretical methods translated through best practices, to assessment standards and monitoring (CO2, CO3, CO5) in response to stakeholders' demand for improved professionalism on social sustainability practices.

4.4.5 Challenge/Barriers to Social Sustainability Adoption

This section covers the challenges of social sustainability mentioned by the respondents. For this study, this can be described as those aspects acting as a hindrance to the adoption and implementation of social sustainability SCM practices in the manufacturing sector.

4.4.5.1 Inadequate Resources and Adaptive Capabilities

This is a major challenge in the sector according to respondents, particularly in the upstream supply chain. Participants emphasize most of their partners engaged in the food production system have little or no capacity to adapt and are unable to withstand external shocks (i.e., market prices, weather conditions infrastructure, etc). Our results argued the lack of access to adequate resources such as phytosanitary and quality treatment in plantations as well as access to quality seeds only leads to lower yield which makes it difficult to earn a living income in the upstream,

“a vast majority of farmers and people engaged in the Agri, and food production system cannot earn a decent income and are not resilient to external shocks. That is the vagaries of weather, infrastructure, and global market pricing, many of them operate on a fine line between success and failure with little capacity to adapt, let alone grow”.

“...around 20% of school-aged children in Cameroon do not attend school. The reasons for this are complex. The majority of smallholder cocoa farmers have small plots with low yields, which makes it difficult to earn a living income. When parents cannot afford to pay for labour to help on their farms, they may keep children at home to work the land rather than attend school”.

“At the individual supplier level, the unsustainability practices are mostly due to financial constrain.... Making it difficult for the individual farmers to access inputs such as fertilizers as well as use efficiently and responsibly.”

4.4.5.2 Inadequate Understanding and Knowledge of the Importance of Social Sustainability

There is inadequate understanding and the absence of training on social sustainability issues. Social sustainability is recent and still starting to gain ground in the Cameroonian manufacturing companies. Organisation with foreign partners or those that extend their operations to external markets are more aware and knowledgeable about the concept and demonstrate a good understanding of its applicability. However, supply chain management is well established in the processes and operations of the companies in the sector.

4.4.5.3 Inadequate Basic Infrastructures and Amenities

The absence of infrastructure and inadequate basic amenities were mentioned by informants as a principal challenge in adopting social sustainability. The effect is multi-dimensional as it covers a part of the problem with stakeholders, depending solely on agribusiness companies,

“... In Cameroon, the provision of basic utilities is still a problem and what are these basic utilities: water supply, primary hospitals, roads, and electricity supply? Now these are the things that raise concerns for manufacturing in-country”.

“...To have a high-performance SSCM system, we need very good internet and intranet system...we are not there yet...the government needs to put in place necessary developmental infrastructures in place”.

4.4.5.4 Intermediaries and Third Parties

This was mentioned by respondents as a key challenge to the adoption of social practices. Our results show that the scale and complexity of the supply change attract intermediaries and third-party agents as alternatives to the purchase of smallholders producing mostly those in highly rural areas and challenging to address social issues.

“The scale and complexity of our supply chain present an increased risk of human rights abuses”.

“Our major challenge to implementing our sustainability practices is that many of our supply chains are in highly rural areas... Can involve intermediaries and other third parties, which makes eradicating aspects such as labor-related issues much more complex”.

4.5.5 Culture

cultural issues are a major challenge and cut across the whole value chain which invariable influence operations and management practices in the agribusiness sector. Respondents emphasized issues of corruption (i.e., illegal payments and behaviors limiting competition) and tribalism (i.e., unequal distribution and poorly managed community support programs). Others mentioned the cultural aspect of the reluctance to embrace changes as one manager argued.

“Our major challenge today and tomorrow will be to always integrate standards and respect for continuous improvement procedures into the management of our various processes... Most times when there are innovations, there is usually this reluctance to change”.

4.5.6 Corporate Social Responsibility Projects Not Effective

Most of the corporate social responsibility (CSR) projects launched by manufacturing organizations are not aimed toward development and are often not designed to directly reflect on societal needs. This has been a major challenge reoccurring over the years, where CSR projects are designed but do not yield long-term developmental effects on stakeholders and end up in conflicting stakeholder relationships with manufacturing companies in local communities.

“They all have programs to ensure that their communities’ interest is met however when you look at the books and what is actually on the ground, there is usually a disconnect. ... Yes, a lot of money is being put into CSR but how sustainable are these programs...because the community needs are not as much as what cannot be provided... if you build a school or provide community centres with equipment and there is no constant electricity supply, how then can they make use of the facilities you have provided”.

4.5.5 Benefits of Social Sustainability Adoption

The benefits achieved because of implementing social sustainability can be found in Table 4.4 presented in terms of social-related levels, indicators, and frequencies demonstrating to some extent the significance of social sustainability initiatives to business performance.

Table 12 Benefits of social sustainability initiatives.

Level	Outcome and related measures	Initiatives
Supplier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase stakeholder trust: hassle-free operations, compliant, organised, and confident. 	CO1, CO2, CO3, CO4, CO5
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved level playing field: bargain for better prices for their produce, attract finance and access to bigger markets. 	CO2, CO5

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic opportunity: socio-economic resilience on product and diversification, business management skills 	CO2, CO3, CO4, CO5
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supply chain performance: increase customer service, more reliable chain partner, increase productivity. 	CO2, CO3, CO4, CO5
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizational learning: corporation between suppliers and buyers. 	CO1, CO2, CO3, CO4, CO5
Focal firm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational excellence: efficiency, increased productivity, reliability, quality, and safety assurance in production. 	CO1, CO2, CO3, CO4, CO5
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Productivity: improved facility. 	CO1, CO2, CO3, CO4
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corporate social performance: community impacts, responsibility suppliers and productivity. 	CO1, CO2, CO3, CO4, CO5
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovative capabilities 	CO1, CO2, CO3, CO4, CO5
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focal relationship and commitment: increase cooperation in the relationship. 	CO2, CO3, CO4, CO5
Customer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumer confidence: transparency, traceability, reliable consumer communication, and reporting systems. 	CO1, CO2, CO3, CO4, CO5
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer performance: increase sales, increase loyalty, and increment in customer perception. 	CO1, CO2, CO3, CO4, CO5
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corporate image: good perception among stakeholders, positive impression by employees and society. 	CO1, CO2, CO3, CO4, CO5

Source: empirical data

It can be observed from the results that the extension of social sustainability initiatives by the focal firm to the supplier location led to supplier performance assessed in terms of productivity, quality, and error reduction in operations. Thereby creating trust and hassle-free operations

“We are already seeing improvements in cooperatives we work with whose leaders have undergone the training. Not only are they more organized, but their improved professionalism is also inspiring new confidence from farmers who used to distrust cooperatives”.

This inspired new confidence at the supplier not only making them more organised and compliant but also improving the level playing field, as a CO2 manager remarked:

“There are various advantages of farmers coming together. Working together in a group offers them the benefits of bargaining for better prices on their produce, attracting financing, access to markets and you can expect an increase in the quantity of products they produce. Thus, giving them access to bigger markets. The results so far have been encouraging”.

This in effect has made them become better and more reliable supply chain partners, increase productivity, and offer better services.

Our data further suggest addressing social issues led to economic opportunity achieved through socio-economic resilience on products and income diversification, and the development of business management skills. As some managers remarked:

“a vast majority of farmers and people engaged in the Agri, and food production system can't earn a decent income and are not resilient to external shocks. That is the vagaries of weather, infrastructure, and global market pricing, many of them operate on a fine line between success and failure with little capacity to adapt, let alone grow. In this direction, we provide farmers with training on good agricultural practices, access to finance, Agri-inputs, climate-resilient seeds and labour-saving tools and equipment, and other aspects such as business management training and support for farmer collectives and cooperatives, as well as digital inclusion”.

“We enable the smallholders we source from to maximize the profitability of their farms through better productivity per hectare and income diversification. This is achieved by offering products, services, training, and coaching to all smallholders we source from”.

From the focal firm perspective, the results show the implementation of social sustainability initiatives led to operational excellence utilizing efficiency, quality, reliability, and safety assurance in production with improved facilities that have increased productivity. As one manager described corporate social Performance (CO1) as:

“a continual construction of efficiency which involves each of us as well as the entire organization in its processes, its choices, and its relations with its partners, as an invitation to action in its productivity, competitiveness, quality of people, products, equipment, facilities, and leadership. Social activities facilitated the creation of value to remain the preferred choice of the market by being more profitable, more competitive, and more qualitative”.

Also, we observed from the data those social initiatives not only bring about increased corporate relationships and commitment to enhance corporate social performance, but such engagements trigger the development of innovative capabilities essential for transformational changes.

“We use the power of partnerships to accelerate and magnify our efforts to achieve a level of sector transformation that cannot be accomplished alone. our partnerships focus on driving transformational changes in the areas of market demand, accountability, public sector governance, and farmer organizations. As a data-driven thought leader in the industry, we use our knowledge and scale, together with our partners to help raise sustainability norms industry-wide to address significant sustainability issues in the sector, together”.

Our result further showed that managing social issues via the introduction of social initiatives leads to improved corporate image which results in building a good stakeholder’s perception

and positive impression by workers and local communities. By adopting social sustainability initiatives, reliable consumer communication and reporting systems are developed to ensure transparency and traceability of corporate activities which significantly boost consumer confidence for sustainable products.

“Our commitments help consumers around the world choose sustainable cocoa and chocolate products with confidence. We make traceability the standard in our directly sourced cocoa supply chain. The certification boosts consumer confidence that products have been sustainably sourced from farm-to-shop shelves. This requires our suppliers to follow our code of conduct which offers expert guidance on better farming methods – Sustainable cocoa production requires environmentally friendly farming techniques that limit the use of fertilizers and pesticides. Beans must be fermented for six days and left to dry in the sun over the same period, working conditions and care for nature this in turn leads to a better production, a better environment, and a better life for everyone”.

“Transparency is also critical for our stakeholders, both at a local and international level. Recognizing that transparency and traceability can help boost consumer confidence and minimize social and environmental risks”.

4.4.6 Way forward

Landscape approach: Our results show that adopting a landscape approach to managing social sustainability helps to re-imagine the management of social issues. This approach identifies the many individuals, groups, and interests that are taken into consideration from which to generate well-informed opinions and gives them a voice in establishing a balance amongst competing demands for social sustainability issues (i.e., water and sanitation, income, health, safety, and wellbeing, and schools),

“It is important to remember; many issues cannot be tackled in silos. In a smallholder landscape, climate change may impact water availability and farmer livelihoods. In a processing facility, labor standards can impact food safety. That is why ... takes ‘a landscape’ approach to understand the potential risks and opportunities that an action can have in several others”.

“We listen to the opinions of stakeholders who include customers, communities, NGOs, Development Finance Institutions and banks, foundations, shareholders, and employees. ...this leads to collaborations and partner programs that enable us to scale positive impact more quickly and with greater reach than we could achieve alone”.

4.5 Research question 3 – How are the social sustainability initiatives implemented and managed in the agricultural supply chain with respect to Cameroon?

* operations *Society *supplier *customers

Figure 10 Social Sustainability Initiatives

With regards to the extrinsically driven social initiatives (6 out of 12) had engagement principles based on formalised mechanisms while (5 out of 14) of the intrinsically driven social initiatives had engagement principles based on formalised mechanisms. On the other hand, the extrinsically driven social initiatives (4 of 12) were based on collaborative mechanisms and (7

of 14) of the intrinsically driven social initiatives were based on collaborative mechanisms. It is also observed that some social initiatives in both intrinsically (three initiatives) and extrinsically (two initiatives) driven followed collaborative and formalised mechanisms in at least one social initiative in both drivers (i.e., internal, and external drivers). Thus, the drivers of social initiatives appear to have some considerable influence on the principle used for introducing the social initiative (the two most populated quadrants in Fig. 10 – Top left and right quadrant). Notwithstanding this significant observation from the results, it can be suggested that organisational drivers to social initiatives do not limit the principle of engaging with their supply chains in any form.

Another interesting observation is that in the quadrant “extrinsic driver/formalized mechanism” (5 out of 8) the social initiatives involve internal operation and supplier relationships. This result supposes that when extrinsically driven, lead firms had their suppliers and internal operations as the focus of formalised mechanisms. Even though the quadrant “extrinsic driver/collaborative mechanism” looks like more of a supplier and society relationship, this may indicate that extrinsically driven social initiatives are developed at the expense of some direct stakeholders (i.e., consumers) notwithstanding the formalised or collaborative approach adopted for its development (see fig 10).

When the lead firm is intrinsically driven and adopts a collaborative approach, initiatives engage with a series of multiple relationships (that is internal operation, supplier, consumer, and society), the other (i.e., supplier, and society relationship), and a couple of society only relationship. More specifically, intrinsically driven social initiatives develop via formalised mechanism turn to develop more diverse relationships between a lead’s firms direct and indirect stakeholders (i.e., internal operations, supplier, consumer, and society) as indicated in the quadrant “intrinsically driven/formalised mechanism” (most populated quadrant).

This observation suggests that when extrinsically motivated (notwithstanding the principle for engaging the social initiative), the focus relationship with upstream partners is the route lead firms pursue (10 out of 12 initiatives involved suppliers). There is further observation that when they are intrinsically driven (notwithstanding the engaging principle), the lead firm pursues a no-dominant pattern of multi-stakeholder relationship. Also, when adopting collaborating mechanisms (notwithstanding the driver), the relationship between the supplier and society appears to dominate (fig 10). When adopting a formalized mechanism (notwithstanding the driver), the relationship between the internal operations and supplier seems to dominate (i.e., 6-internal operations and supplier, 1 -supplier, 1 internal operation, 6 – internal operations, supplier, and customer, 1 society, customer and internal operation and finally 1-internal operation, supplier, consumer, and society relationship).

It should be noted that (fig 10) out of the 17 social initiatives including a relationship with upstream partners or suppliers (i.e., involving single or multiple relationships with suppliers), 9 social initiatives were linked to external drivers. Out of the 16 social initiatives (i.e., involving a multiple relationship), 12 of all social initiatives with a multi-relationship of three or four supply chain partners (i.e., upstream, and downstream partners) are associated with internal drivers. Thus, it can be said from the results that when the social sustainability initiatives are involved in some kind of relationship with it upstream partners (suppliers) while engaging with their society, the social sustainability initiatives might be strongly connected to external drivers. Also, when the social sustainability initiatives involve a relationship with both upstream and downstream partners, then these initiatives are more strongly connected to internal drivers.

4.6 Findings Relative to the Adopted Theories

Through the lens of the stakeholders' theory, the results showed how different stakeholders influence the drivers of social sustainability implementation in supply chains. Pressure from market actors significantly influences social sustainability adoption in the supply chain. This might be because most local-based companies are seeking to enhance their profiles to access bigger markets. This aligns with assertions of stakeholder theory that stakeholders and the community need to develop sustained relationships for success and survival (Stieb, 2009). This research finding aligns with Mani and Gunasekaran (2018) research in emerging economies on customer pressure and the adoption of social sustainability in the forward supply chain. Similar results were achieved by Carter and Jennings (2004). This result also confirms Ehr Gott et al. (2011), through the stakeholders' perspective, demonstrated how customer pressure enabled the disclosure of social sustainability adoption. The findings also confirm Sancha et al. (2015) results achieved on normative pressure to act as a strong enabler for firms to develop sustainability capabilities and sustainability adoption. Internal pressure from top management and sustainability culture are found to also influence social sustainability adoption. This finding confirms Carter and Jennings (2004) who found a relationship between purchasing social responsibility (PSR) and the adoption of social sustainability in the forward supply chain. This further confirms Marshall et al. (2015) who found organisation sustainability culture advances social sustainability adoption practices and regulatory pressure to basic practices. Thus, this finding contradicts Mani and Gunasekaran (2018) and Nguyen et al. (2023) who find regulatory pressures to be most significant in developing countries but aligns with Tran and Jeppesen (2016) who found moral-based motives are the most significant. This research's reason for this observation is the fact decision-makers are starting to realise that instead of seeking temporary opportunities and risk it is better to create a long-term focus for permanent results.

From the resource base view lens, this research confirms the outcome of organizational learning through social sustainability practices and reward for acquiring and controlling social resources in the forward supply chain led to lead firm gain competitive advantage, supplier performance, operating cost reduction relationship management (Klassen and Vereecke, 2012). These research findings show that acquiring and controlling social resources enabled agribusiness companies to gain access to bigger markets. This aligns with earlier works of Carter and Euston (2011) who found that organizations learning about sustainability practices give them a significant competitive advantage in the international market. The findings also support Sancha et al. (2016) whose results suggest that organisational learning through assessing suppliers contributes to improving the buying firm's social performance and collaborating with them enhances the suppliers' social performance. These findings further agree with Rodriguez et al. (2016) who argue collaborating with third parties without creating a trade between economic and social performance leads to the development of resources that enhance the social sustainability of the supply chain.

With regard to the strategic contingency theory, this research supports this theory. This study argues that supply chain social sustainability and its implementation must vary depending on the environment in which the organizations operate. The variation exists due to the different stakeholder resource needs in each community. The typology developed allows for this variation in the environment as well as distinct social supply chain practices contingent upon the needs that are present. Other studies have confirmed this perspective (Walker and Jones, 2012; Golicic et al. 2021). This research findings advance research on social sustainability in SCM by being more sensitive to the organisation and business situation and specifically offer a better understanding of the implementation of social sustainability SCM practices in this context (Cameroon).

4.7 Summary

From the results of the study, it can be established that social sustainability is only been recently introduced in the agricultural sector. In all 5-case organisations were familiar with sustainability and supply chain management. However, socially sustainable supply chain management (SSSCM) was not very well known to all 5 case organizations. Social sustainability measures practiced were concealed under the HSE, QMS, ISO, SDGs, ILO, and UN Global Compact and not essentially for the goal of sustainability but rather to satisfy stakeholder demands and interests.

Table 13 summarising the findings.

Social Dimensions		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health, safety, and wellbeing • Human rights • Equity • Product responsibility • Education and training • Ethics • Community involvement • Philanthropy
Drivers	Internal drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethics and values
	External drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market demand • Competition • Regulation • Reputation and competitive advantage • Secondary stakeholders
Social relationships levels		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supplier relationship • Customer relationship • Internal operations relationship • Society relationship
Implementation criteria	Formalised criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standard contractual agreements • Business codes of conduct and ethics • Sustainability policies • Pacts (sectoral/national/international) • Online platforms
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education, training, and incentive actions • Platforms to Forster local development

	Collaborative criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing monitoring programs
Performance	Supplier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase stakeholder trust. • Improved level playing field. • Economic opportunity • Supply chain performance • Organisational learning
	Focal firm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational performance • Productivity • Corporate social performance • Innovative capabilities • Focal relationship and commitment
	Consumer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumer confidence • Customer performance • Corporate image
Challenges		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of understanding and knowledge of the importance of social sustainability. • Lack of resources and adaptive capabilities • Intermediaries and third parties • Culture (corruption, tribalism, and resistance to change) • Lack of basic infrastructures and social amenities • CSR projects are not effective. • The country's level of development
Recommendations		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Landscape approach • Awareness and training on social SCM • Education on the core part of CSR

Source: empirical data

Chapter Five - Discussion and Framework Development

5.1 Introduction

This chapter coins the findings to address the objectives of the study. Also, a framework for enhancing social sustainability in SCM is developed and validated for the Cameroon Manufacturing sector (CMS). This supposes necessary improvement for the manufacturing companies to enhance their supply chain through social sustainability and metrics for assessing their improvement.

5.2 Objective 1

To critically examine the existing trends of social sustainability in supply chain management in developing countries.

See section 4.3. for analysis of the existing trends

5.3 Objective 2

Identifying the drivers, principles, and barriers to social sustainability in supply chain management practices in the agricultural sector in Cameroon.

For the drivers see section 4.4.2 a & b.

For the principles see section 4.4.4 a & b.

For the barriers see section 4.4.5 and 5.6.1.1.

5.4 Objective 3

To critically examine the implementation and management of social sustainability initiatives in the agricultural supply chain with respect to Cameroon.

To achieve objective 3 of this study, i.e., to critically examine the implementation and management of social sustainability initiatives in the agricultural supply chain in Cameroon, the research argued that social sustainability initiatives can be analysed with the driver and the principle used for engaging the social initiative. Building on these two aspects, a typology of social sustainability initiatives was developed to gain insight into the phenomenon (Fig 4.1). Based on the empirical data gathered in Cameroon, 26 social initiatives from the 5 case organisations under investigation were organised into one of the 6 types: 1) Intrinsically driven/formalisation, 2) Intrinsically driven/collaboration, 3) Extrinsically driven/formalisation, 4) Extrinsically driven/collaboration, 5) Extrinsically driven/formalisation and collaboration, and 6) Intrinsically driven/formalisation and collaboration.

These social initiatives are argued to differ from each other with some distinctive characteristics linked to the driver/motivation and the approach/principle used to engage with other stakeholders. Following Mani et al. (2015) and Morais and Silvestre (2018), a third aspect is considered the social relationship levels to assess the extent to which these initiatives are implemented. This guides the analysis to identify and understand how social sustainability initiatives are implemented and managed (i.e., the dimension, the driver, the extent of operationalising social initiatives, and the principle for engaging the initiative).

Early studies on social responsibility identified and distinguished various levels of operationalising social responsibility (Carroll, 1991). Other studies like the work of Du et al., (2010) grouped corporate social orientation into three levels (i.e., prosocial, individualistic, and competitive): corporations at the prosocial orientation level seek to equally maximize outcomes

for both themselves and other stakeholders. The Individualist corporations seek to maximize only their outcomes, while competitor corporations seek to maximize their outcomes relative to other stakeholders' outcomes. Converging with this literature, the typology presented here (Figs. 4.1 and Table 4.3) is promising as it provides new insights and perspectives on social sustainability. Each quadrant is discussed below to the literature.

Table 14 Quotes from each type of social sustainability initiative.

Initiation type	Quotes from interview
Extrinsically driven supply chain collaboration	<i>“Many cooperative leaders still lack business management skills and because they are struggling to find the minimum level of professionalism demanded by market actors, many cooperatives in [...] are looking for support to improve their profile as reliable supply chain partners. To acquire enough high-quality cocoa beans to satisfy our customers’ global market demand, sourcing directly from individual smallholder farmers is simply not an option. We have chosen instead to work with farmer organisations and cooperatives to help them raise their level of professionalism”.</i>
Intrinsically driven supply chain collaboration	<i>“Poverty, lack of health infrastructure, and access to clean water and sanitation contribute to lowered life expectancies in most of the areas we rely for core crops, which also correlates with farm productivity. Those with specific health issues, whether suffering from a disease or exposed to episodic risks, such as pregnant women, are particularly vulnerable. It is an important initiative to reach communities with campaigns on health and nutrition, supporting the manufacturing and retailing of fortified foods for consumers with reduced salt, fat, and sugar through ingredients solutions”.</i>
Extrinsically driven supply chain formalisation	<i>“At [...], we cannot tolerate school-aged children being taken to work. We are committed not to employing or making use of any individual below the minimum employment age set by the local laws or the International Labour Convention. [...] teams take adequate measures to prevent child labour. [...] verify the age of all employees, using documents such as birth certificates, school records, IDs, and driving licenses. [...] does not make any exception to this policy. Our teams are regularly audited by their line managers or local labour inspectors. Each violation of this commitment will lead to severe punishment. Regarding the supply chain, we have developed an audit system to verify whether all</i>

	<i>commodity suppliers and subcontractors correctly adhere to this policy. As part of the [...] project, with [...] participation, checklists were developed and tested to identify different social risks in the supply chains, including child labour”.</i>
Intrinsically driven supply chain formalisation	<i>“With the [...], [...] focussed efforts on supporting the farmers it believes can be the backbone of a sustainable cocoa supply chain while continuing to provide holistic support to all cocoa farmers in our sustainability programs”.</i>
Extrinsically driven supply chain formalisation and collaboration	<i>“With the significant buy-in and demand from our customers for certified products our long-term goal is to contribute to a thriving sector for smallholders and their communities. To make this happen, we have set up the right support, tools, and training to help smallholders and their communities improve their livelihoods and contribute to professionalizing the smallholder organizations. By empowering these organizations, supporting training in business skills, and strengthening their business operations, we can help progress this sector for the future”.</i>
Intrinsically driven supply chain formalisation and collaboration	<i>“Ever since, we have always strived for both ethical and sound performance to ensure the group’s long-term success while improving living standards and natural resource management. The [...] is opted by a management approach that is responsible and transformative, and cuts across our operations including plantations and extends to our subcontractors and suppliers”.</i>

Source: Empirical data

5.4.1 Extrinsically Driven social initiatives/collaboration.

From the empirical data, 5 social sustainability initiatives are identified under this group (i.e., lower left quadrant fig 10 and table 11). These social initiatives were based on collaborative mechanisms. A good example is Initiative Eight launched by CO2 (see Table 11 and Appendix C), a capacity-building program developed in partnership with its mainstream institutional investors to boost the level of professionalism demanded by market actors in the CO2 supply chain. It involved providing training to cooperative leaders and their organisations for business management skills to run their organisation in an efficient, membered-centred, and profitable

manner. It employs collaborative mechanisms with cooperatives to improve their profile as reliable supply chain partners.

In the same way, Initiative Ten launched by CO2 (see Fig 10 and Table 11) aimed to help strengthen local sourcing communities by providing access to basic educational and health services, improving access to nutritional requirements, and breaking down barriers to economic empowerment. CO2 in this initiative partners with its main customers to give opportunities to impoverished vulnerable women aimed at empowering them, especially in becoming financially autonomous. The focus is on addressing social issues in local sourcing communities (i.e., responding to external pressure) and employs collaboration at the relationship level of the society (i.e., women entrepreneurs) by offering them equipment, training, and support on entrepreneurship, crop diversification, and financial management techniques. This initiative helped CO2 improve its corporate social performance.

These initiatives engaged at different social levels along the supply chain as highlighted by the literature (Schliephake et al., 2009; Cantor et al., 2012) and consistent with the work of Dyck and Silvestre (2018), who suggested in LMICs sustainability must necessarily engage different stakeholder groups in the society. Moreover, collaborations between firms and stakeholders in this context turn to increase their social acceptance which leads to building strong synergies for social improvements such as on issues of diversity and inclusion (Hall and Matos, 2010; Gold, 2011).

Table 15 Model for implementing social sustainability into supply chains.

	Intrinsic	Extrinsic
Formalisation	Social initiatives that are initiated by a supply chain lead firm are primarily based on intrinsic drivers (e.g., values and ethical considerations, satisfaction because this was the right thing to do, etc). Lead firms' engagements with the rest of its supply chain are based on formalisation because the organisation can achieve the desirable goal with existing internal resources	Social initiatives that are initiated by a supply chain lead firm primarily based on Extrinsic drivers (e.g., gain competitive advantage, improve reputation, increase market share, etc). Lead firms' engagements with the rest of its supply chain are based on formalisation, because the organisation can achieve the desirable goal with existing internal resources
Collaboration	Social initiatives that are initiated by a supply chain lead firm are primarily based on intrinsic drivers (e.g., values and ethical considerations, satisfaction because this was the right thing to do, etc). Lead firms' engagements with the rest of its supply chain are based on collaboration to achieve the desired goal (i.e., internal resources to the organisation are not enough)	Social initiatives that are initiated by a supply chain lead firm are primarily based on extrinsic drivers (e.g., gain competitive advantage, improve reputation, increase market share, etc). Lead firms' engagements with the rest of its supply chain are based on collaboration to achieve the desired goal (i.e., internal resources to the organisation are not enough)
Collaboration and formalisation	Social initiatives that are initiated by a supply chain lead firm are primarily based on intrinsic drivers (e.g., values and ethical considerations, satisfaction because this was the right thing to do, etc). Lead firms' engagements with the rest of their supply chain are based on formalisation and collaboration. Because both internal and external resources the organisation are needed to achieve the desirable goal.	Social initiatives that are initiated by a supply chain lead firm are primarily based on extrinsic drivers (e.g., gain competitive advantage, improve reputation, increase market share, etc). Lead firms' engagements with the rest of their supply chain are based on formalisation and collaboration. Because both internal and external resources to the organisation are needed to achieve the desirable goal

5.4.2 Intrinsically driven social initiatives/collaboration.

From the results of the analysed data, seven social initiatives were identified under this category (i.e., lower right fig 10 and table 11) for example CO3 launched initiative thirteen (see appendix C) a campaign to reach out to local sourcing communities on health and nutrition to address

social issues of poverty, access to health infrastructures and portable drinking water (i.e., ensuring employee access to an adequate food source, clean drinking water and sanitation during working hours, promoting crop diversification in local sourcing communities to improve nutrition and food security needs, mobile medical screenings to fight against diseases, and supporting food manufacturing to customers that reduce salt, fat, and sugar through ingredients solutions). This initiative shows an intrinsic driver to address social issues through collaborative mechanisms at a relationship level of society, operations, suppliers, and customers.

Similarly, Initiative Three by CO1 (see Fig 10 and table 11) was launched in partnership with public institutions, to support local communities with basic infrastructures, empowering women, and access to clean water and sanitation. This initiative focussed on ethical principles and organizational values since the organisation was not aiming for financial returns but rather to enhance its corporate ethical performance. CO1 engages with a collaborative approach at the relationship level on issues of diversity, health, and safety in the local communities.

Both initiatives emphasised aspects of diversity, social inclusion, health and safety, health, and well-being at the forefront. Showing higher levels of transformation in design. This is aligned with sustainable innovation 2.0 perspectives (Dyck and Silvestre, 2018b), where the economic/financial dimension is subservient, especially on complex social issues within their supply chains (Hall et al., 2012a, 2012b).

5.4.3 Extrinsically driven social initiatives/formalisation.

From the empirical data, six social initiatives were identified and grouped under this category (i.e., upper right quadrant fig 10 and table 11). The main formalised mechanisms used when engaging were the use of codes of conduct, or ethics; commitment to social standards via

contractual information; the development of web-based mobile applications to assess social practices of supply chain partners, and the dissemination of sustainability policies. A good example is Social Initiative Twenty-one launched by CO5 (see Table 11 and appendix C) developed by its main buyer under a multi-stakeholder initiative to continuously improve CSR performance in the industry by helping to mitigate human rights violations, including modern slavery and aspects of child labour, within the sourcing community being particularly exposed to social risk.

Social initiative fourteen launched by CO3 (see table 11 and appendix C) formally commits suppliers to the lead firm's sustainability policy by defining minimum requirements on quality, safety, and governance mechanisms.

Similarly, social initiative eleven by CO3 (see Table 11 and Appendix C) proactively partnered with an NGO to map out issues of child labour in its smallholder supply chain by introducing a new app that digitally registered nearly 7000 smallholder suppliers that directly feeds into CO3's "Atsource" an online platform that provides its customers and other stakeholders unparalleled information on the supply chain of their products. The initiative is an outcome of multi-stakeholder development designed to introduce rigorous traceability and reporting systems to enhance reputation, increase supply chain transparency, gain market share, and strengthen its competitive position (i.e., extrinsically driven) works by disseminating information to its stakeholders (customers, civil society organizations, etc).

It can be viewed from the description that the nature of these initiatives supposes a formalised approach like easily enforced contracts and online content that can easily be shared and promoted. These formalised mechanisms are adopted to reduce stakeholders' pressure on the lead firms to address their social supply chain performance (Huq et al., 2016; Zeng et al., 2017; Morais and Silvestre, 2018). These formalizations targeting suppliers and buyers through

contracts can also work as a risk-mitigation mechanism for the focal companies (Klassen and Vereecke, 2012). Thus, from these formalized mechanisms, lead firms are aiming to avoid being held responsible for poorly managed social issues in the supply chain. However, Pedersen and Andersen (2006) argued that these mechanisms are not always effective because the incentives to comply are not the same for all the partners. Thus, active commitment from all the actors in the supply chain is needed.

5.4.4 Intrinsically driven social initiatives/formalisation.

Based on our empirical data, seven social initiatives were identified and grouped under this category (i.e., upper left quadrant fig 10 and table 11). the initiatives involve both primary and secondary stakeholders (i.e., internal operations, suppliers, consumers, and society). For example, social initiative Twelve launched by CO3 (see table 11 and appendix C) to extend its sustainability progress partnered with customers, NGOs, and local communities to improve the livelihood of its direct cocoa supply chain (i.e., to achieve a defined living income to conquer poverty), eliminate child labour and ensure children in the local sourcing community access to education and at the same time mitigate environmental impact.

Initiative seventeen launched by CO4 (see table 11 and appendix C) aimed to identify and mitigate social and environmental risks (e.g., safety and health at work, and reduction of carbon gas emission, diversity, and social inclusion,) in its direct supply chain. CO5 in partnership with NGOs (e.g., ProForest i.e., “supporting the transition to agricultural commodity production and sourcing that delivers positive social and environmental outcomes for people and the planet” and Earthworm Foundation i.e., “working with businesses committed to change the present in some of Earth’s most critical ecosystems”). CO5 disseminates information to its

stakeholders to mitigate these risks via its sustainability policies, business code of conduct, reporting systems, and online platforms.

Although these social initiatives were intrinsically driven, the nature of these initiatives requires formalised mechanisms rather than collaborative ones (Lee and Whang, 2000). The purpose is to disseminate information to the public by using standard methods and online platforms. Coupled with that, focal collaborations with secondary stakeholders e.g., NGOs, can provide the basis for significant value-building synergies (Perez-Aleman and Sandilands, 2008) and assist in reaching out information to the desired audience (Brockhaus et al., 2013).

5.4.5 Extrinsically driven social initiatives/ formalisation and collaboration.

The empirical data suggest two social initiatives fall under the category (i.e., upper, and lower right quadrants Fig 10 and Table 11). These initiatives adopt various implementation criteria ranging from education, training, coaching, and incentive actions for improvement achieved through best-in-class theoretical methods translated through best practices, to assessment standards and monitoring. Initiative nine (see table 11 and appendix C) for instance launched by CO2 to satisfy the growing appetite of customers for certified products aimed towards its long-term commitment to upstream partners and their local communities enabling them to achieve better incomes and improved living standards while growing and delivering a sustainable supply of cocoa and chocolate products from bean to end-product. To achieve this, case B provides certified training programs to these organizations while developing their local communities e.g., between 2011 to 2019, more than 30,000 farmers were trained in about 900 farmer fields' schools and dug 32 boreholes in communities to increase access to potable and clean drinking water. They are further incentivized through premium payment for professionalized practices and achieved certification.

Similarly, Initiative One (see Table 11 and Appendix C) was launched by CO1 to enhance its competitive position by putting customer interest at the centre of all its operations. CO1 adopted a quality management system for continuous improvement in and across the organisational operations that work with national and ISO norms to interact with its partners ensuring the quality and safety of products, people, and the environment. For instance, to address issues of work safety with its partners in charge of logistics, CO1 closely monitors and continuously assesses them for rewards and penalties, which partners who fail to meet those standards. This is done through contract renewal to those who meet work and road safety standards.

Although these initiatives are extrinsically driven, they require both assessments and collaborative mechanisms. Several authors support this relationship (Klassen and Vereecke, 2012; Gimenez and Sierra, 2013; Sancha et al., 2016). For instance, Foerstl et al. (2010) suggested that assessing suppliers about sustainability issues leads to the development of supplier development initiatives. Similarly, Gimenez and Sierra (2013) argued before aiding upstream partners in sustainability issues focal firms should evaluate them to identify areas that require development. To others, suppliers' assessment of social issues is considered a risk mitigation strategy (Klassen and Vereecke, 2012)

5.4.6 Intrinsically driven social initiatives/formalisation and collaboration.

Based on the empirical data, the social initiative under this category involves a multiple stakeholder relationship (i.e., primary, and secondary stakeholders). Initiative twenty-two (i.e., upper, and lower right quadrant fig 10 and table 11), also (see appendix C) launched by CO5 to produce palm oil and natural rubber in a way that benefits all (i.e., allows for long-term socio-economic development, social well-being, better health conditions, security, and

efficient management of natural resources. For instance, CO5 provides an adapted response to economic development, food security needs, and child labour mitigation with its smallholders in a win-win partnership. To achieve this, CO5 formalized its commitments to better structure its actions, and more specifically, collaborate with smallholder organizations (i.e., provide technical assistance and procurement of their produce) and at the same integrate its “Rubberway” program to identify and address issues of child labour. This in return positively impacts smallholders’ productivity and allows them to have a stable income while improving issues of child labour which aligns with the goal of the initiative (responsible management policy).

It can be viewed from the description that, this initiative generates both private and social value (i.e., by improving smallholder’s well-being, and issues of child labour while also improving its reputation among stakeholders and the sustainable supply of palm oil and natural rubber). This is consistent with the literature on initiatives that reimagine a relationship between organizational performance and society, seeking win-win situations, and remaining profitable by resolving social issues (Porter and Kramer, 2019; Ollivier de Leth and Ros-Tonen, 2021). Most recently, the literature on business and management studies advocates for businesses to adopt a paradox perspective in their business strategies (T. Hahn et al. 2018; Ollivier de Leth and Ros-Tonen, 2021).

5.5 Objective 4

To analyse the benefits of social sustainability on the entire supply chain.

From the empirical data, social sustainability initiatives resulted in numerous benefits across the supply chain including suppliers, focal firms, and customers.

5.5.1 Supplier

At the supplier level, this research findings align with (Carter and Jennings, 2004; Mani et al., 2016) who found supplier sustainability to have a mediating role in organizational learning and trust, and further highlighted the benefits of social sustainability including productivity, lead firm trust, learning, and supply chain performance. Many scholars have reached similar results (Anisul Huq et al., 2014; Lee, 2016; Mani et al., 2018a, b, 2020) establishing a relationship between social sustainability and supplier performance. Despite prior studies had demonstrated supplier performance in a more general manner (Vachon and Klassen, 2006; Sancha et al., 2015), studies investigating supplier's social performance and supply chain performance are scant with respect to agribusiness firms in sub-Saharan Africa (Cameroon). These findings support the assertion that "suppliers are part of the upstream supply chain and are highly influenced by supply chain social sustainability practices, which directly reflects on their performance outcomes" (Anisul Huq et al., 2014).

Our research acknowledges the impact of sustainability and ethical behaviour displayed by suppliers on corporate performance (Mani et al., 2020). The findings support Mani et al. (2016) assertion that "ethical issues are important to social supply chain sustainability in developing countries" contrary to Carter and Jennings (2004). These findings suggest suppliers played a significant role in improving the entire performance of the supply chain and support the

assertion on environmental sustainability practices and their relationship with suppliers and the overall supply chain performance (Akamp and Müller, 2013; Seuring and Müller, 2008).

The research findings also suggest implementing social sustainability practices led to new products and processes that benefited suppliers (i.e., smallholders) in becoming socio-economic resilient which directly reflected on their performance. Marshall et al (2016) achieved similar results in demonstrating how different social sustainability practices (market-based i.e., innovation in products and processes that reimagine the supply chain) impact supplier performance, suggesting how significant the mediating role played by supplier's performance is. Furthermore, Lalwani et al. (2018) and León-Bravo et al. (2021) showed how sustainable supply management (SSM) benefits were achieved in trying to affect buy requirements while recognizing suppliers' needs. This aligns with our finding that suggests social sustainability practices designed to improve supplier profiles unlocked suppliers' access to bigger markets, attracted access to finance, and bargained for better prices for their produce.

5.5.2 Focal firm

With regards to lead firms, the research findings show implementing social sustainability initiatives led to the focal firm's operational benefits being significantly influenced by the supplier's social performance. These research findings align with those achieved by (Mani et al., 2018, 2020; Gimenez and Sierra, 2013; Sancha et al. 2016). Carter and Jennings (2004) demonstrated how the adoption of social responsibility in purchasing (purchasing social responsibility (PSR) led to operational benefits of the focal company mediated by an increased corporation which facilitates knowledge exchange and learning. The research findings are also consistent with those achieved by Gimenez and Sierra (2013) which demonstrated how sustainability supplier collaborative initiatives resulted in the environmental performance of

the firm. This is an indication that sustainability collaborative initiatives are critical strategies for risk mitigation and enhancing supplier performance which in return benefits the operational performance of lead firms. Sustainability initiatives in the upstream supply chain reduce lead time and increase quality and supply will become reliable thereby ensuring the supplier's performance. As supplier performance increases, the focal firm will also benefit from quality products, on-time delivery, minimization of supply risk, and reduced total cost (Mani et al., 2020; Klassen and Vereecke, 2012). Contrary to Hollos et al. (2012) who found no benefits in social sustainability practices to performance in LMICs this research findings established a relationship and confirmed similar results by Mani et al. (2018) and (2020) in LMICs who found that social sustainability adoption in SCM in LMICs helps improving focal firms' operational performance.

The findings also give evidence that the majority of the initiatives are predominantly linked to companies' corporate social responsibility activities towards its stakeholders (i.e., community impacts, responsible suppliers and productivity, and customer relationships) and how this contributes to productivity and corporate social performance (Hutchins and Sutherland, 2008). This approach allows the integration of these perspectives (i.e., stakeholders' interest) to favour the improvement of the organisation's footprint (Ehrgott et al., 2011; Gimenez and Tachizawa, 2012; Ali and Kaur, 2021). These results align with Toussaint et al. (2020) who found that "gaining of social conformity through transparency, market awareness and consistency of responsible practices can favour the legitimacy of companies but also, the integration of external pressure from different stakeholders benefit these practices that can be replicated once demonstrated its market effectiveness".

Furthermore, this research finding aligns with Klassen and Vereecke, (2012) who established a relationship between the management of social issues and innovative capabilities. Mann et

al. (2017) and Nath and Agrawal (2020) asserted that “companies have begun to proactively create a sustainability orientation in response to stakeholder demand, and agility is required to sense opportunities, seize opportunities, and reconfigure business processes according to market needs”. Thus, the development of social sustainability requires new behaviors and ideas (Marshall et al. 2015). Several companies were actively building new skills and capabilities as they developed new production processes and digitalized their quality management system (QMS) to meet customer requirements and ensure the safety of goods and people (initiative one CO1), delivered more compelling supplier education related to issues of lowered life expectancy which also correlates to supplier productivity (health and nutrition, poverty, inadequate health infrastructure, access to potable water source) (initiative nine CO3), and developed a digital platform with its main customer to address social issues relating to human rights (initiative twenty-two CO£). Overall, these case organizations demonstrated that producing safer goods, increasing supplier education on health issues to ensure stability in productivity, and increasing transparency to mitigate risk were perceived to bring huge returns, although the benefits were difficult to quantify. These initiatives had relatively little incremental cost, yet significantly increased productivity, customer value, transparency, and reduced firm risk.

5.5.3 Customer

With regards to customers, the results show that acknowledging customers as key partners linked social sustainability initiatives to customer benefits. These results align with Toussaint et al. (2021) who found a relationship between companies’ social responsibility practices and customers’ conception strongly influenced by reliable product communication, transparency, and aspect of brand reputation. Companies are constantly being careful when reporting best

practices to customers to strengthen ties with stakeholders that inevitably impact their business performance (De Brito et al., 2008). Notwithstanding certain debates on the credibility of sustainability reporting, most reports are strategic follow-ups to improve corporate communication to gain an enhanced perception by stakeholders. This research results align with Mani et al.(2018b) findings on supply chain social sustainability in Portuguese manufacturing which not only found the significance of responsible practices but also that enhanced stakeholder communication helps to strengthen extended stakeholders' relationships.

Our results also show that social operational practices correlate with increasing customer loyalty and sales. These findings correspond to Longoni and Cagliano (2016) who showed that “social operations practices can provide a work environment for employee safety and well-being that allows employee motivation and retention, and through these, increases customer loyalty and sales”. Toussaint et al. (2021) achieved similar results and found employee outcome mediates social sustainability orientations and customer outcomes in corporate SCM. Carter (2005) shows that sustainable practices have a significant indirect relationship with a firm's financial performance through HR benefits (i.e., increasing organizational learning). Previous research has shown mixed findings from empirical results when the expected outcome of the chain is profit (Homburg et al., 2009). In this research (i.e., which uses social sustainability) the expected outcome of the chain found a significant relationship. Hence, this research emphasizes the importance of linking strategic planning with sustainability on a long-term scale. Companies need to avoid falling into the short-term survival and profitability trap, as this can be a main limitation to embracing long-term business performance.

5.6 Objective 5

The development and validation of a framework to evaluate and enhance the agricultural sectors' social sustainability SCM efforts in Cameroon.

5.6.1 Developing a Framework for Integrating social Sustainability into Cameroon Agricultural supply chain.

In sustainability supply chain management (SSCM) discussion, the incorporation of social sustainability in SCM has become prominent and described as the formal and informal processes purposefully designed to improve the well-being of people and society via the management of social resources. When communities become equitable, diverse, healthy, and democratic for a sustained period created via these processes, i.e., social sustainability is assumed to have occurred (Khan, et al., 2021; Huq, Chowdhury, and Klassen 2016; Khan and Zhang 2020).

Firms seeking to be sustainable and managed in a socially sustainable manner must go in for sustainability-oriented opportunities. These opportunities provide a framework to address sustainability-related challenges and properly managing such opportunities is reliant on the voluntary efforts of companies directed towards such improvements (Schaltegger and Burrit 2014).

Thus, for agribusiness companies to effectively manage social sustainability in their supply chains, is important to develop a roadmap with the needed strategies and indicators tailored to suit these companies. To propose a social sustainability-enhancing framework for agribusiness companies, it is necessary to understand the challenges of adopting social sustainability. These challenges were discussed in Chapter 4 and are necessary for developing the framework. The research findings show a mix of challenges (i.e., some aspects are already captured in the

literature and others are specific to the research context (Cameroon). Thus, this supports the assertion that social sustainability issues in LMICs are “contextual, time-dependent, dynamic, and emergent” (Yawar and Seuring, 2015). Identifying social sustainability challenges for agribusiness companies in LMIC in sub-Saharan Africa in transition of becoming emergent by 2035 like Cameroon is novel as limited research has been carried out in this direction.

Sustainability today has become nearly a do-without phenomenon by many companies seeking to stay competitive and aiming for long-term gains and remain in business, are continuously defining new business strategic goals and as well as developing techniques to manage the necessary changes towards achieving these goals (Delai and Takahashi, 2013; Morais and Silvestre, 2018). One major problem with managing change in an organization is that some or most of the change policies are often executed as “quick fixes” mostly focused on a single or limited developmental aspect without careful consideration of possible unwanted effects on other aspects. Consequently, triggering unwanted and unpredictable disruptions in the change process (Gill 2003). Change management is considered the renewal of a firm’s structure and capabilities to satisfy emerging stakeholder demands. Thus, change is a critical aspect of the development and implementation of innovative strategies for companies and this at times is dependent on organisations values, leadership style, and communication to achieve the desired results (Gill, 2003).

Corporate culture and sustainability are closely related. An organisation seeking adherence to sustainability standards and assimilating reactive sustainability measures needs as an initial move to incorporate sustainability into its corporate culture (Carter and Rogers, 2008). This can be done by accepting the need for deliberate change management emphasised through planning, monitoring, controlling, and the incorporation of strategies that motivate and inspire those involved in the change process (Gill 2003).

Notwithstanding the apparent necessity of change management, change management by itself does not suffice to achieve a successful transition to corporate sustainability. Thus, a system that recognizes a company's sustainability vision, the needed resources and procedures as well as considering personal management and their performance evaluation.

To successfully incorporate a corporate sustainability vision and measures across the entire corporate functions, it is important to consider personnel training and development as an essential part of the entire process. Inadequate personnel development on knowledge, skills, and competencies to incorporate sustainability is a major barrier in SSCM which may lead to inconsistency in the daily applicability of sustainability practices. Thus, for there to be effective integration of corporate sustainability, it is necessary to adequately train personnel to bring them up to date on the required skills and knowledge needed for the procedures and its implementation (Sarkis et al., 2010).

As mentioned in the previous paragraph, organisation seeking to pursue the sustainability path, usually encounter challenges like change management and cultural limitations. These challenges are often addressed through effective training programs, workshops, and other personnel knowledge acquisition initiatives (Sarkis et al., 2010). For the agricultural companies in this study, it is evident from the case organizations that various training programs and schemes are ongoing to manage social issues. However, further analysis shows that these training and schemes are directed towards ISO, FSSC 22000, and QMS. These systems can drive sustainability and training in this direction will be beneficial to the management of social sustainability in SCM to an extent.

However, committing all social sustainability measures on aspects of ISO or FSSC2200 standards will be insufficient as these standards by themselves do not competently address social issues and the adoption of sustainable SCM. To be precise, these are tools for defining

motions or suggesting techniques for promoting measures to enhance business processes and can be considered as sustainability enhancement such as product quality. These standards are not inclusive but rather suggested as support for continuous improvements. Because of this, they are perceived as fuzzy (MacDonald, 2005). Coupled with that, it is argued that most companies only adopt ISOs to build their reputation and image (Rondinelli and Vastag, 2000). Therefore, it is not enough to ascertain the incorporation of ISO standards by themselves will result in social improvements and eventually business sustainability (Krut and Gleckman 2009). In this regard, skills and competence building based on ISO standards as the main road to improving social sustainability in SCM is incomplete and not enough to acquire the needed capabilities, skills, and expertise to effectively move these manufacturing companies towards responsive socially sustainable SCM. Instead, all-inclusive training based on skill and knowledge acquisition on the incorporation and management of social issues on the entire supply chain activities is needed for the adoption, execution, and continuing improvement of social aspects in the manufacturing sector.

5.6.1.1 Challenges/Barriers

As discussed in section 4.5 on the challenges, our results show most of the challenges are interrelated. Not effective CRS projects and the challenge of intermediaries and third parties. The former can be described as the outcomes of the latter. The reason for this conclusion can be attributed to interview responses where respondents claimed that the disconnect between programs to ensure communities' interests are met and what is on the books. Such misalignment is an obstacle to proper communication on social issues (Sodhi and Tang 2018). This often results in to lack of confidence and engagement which triggers third-party influence making it difficult to tackle social issues. Hussain et al. (2018) and Mani et al. (2016) support this view

and argue the lack of communication between companies and the local communities may alter public perception of the social initiative. To others (Khan et al.,2021), the lack of community involvement in social initiatives may hinder their advancement.

With regard to the challenges related to inadequate resources and adaptive capabilities, our findings established that this is a major challenge for managing social sustainability in the upstream agricultural supply chain. Our findings show that most of the partners operating in the upstream (smallholders) cannot earn decent income and operate in a narrow line of margin between success and failure. This is attributed to the lack of financial and material resources, lower yields, lack of diversification, and inability to respond to external shocks (i.e., change in market prices, vagaries of weather and infrastructure) due to little or no capacity to adapt, let alone grow as the research case respondents claimed. Thus, tackling social issues becomes a big problem.

Other challenges such as inadequate social amenities and the country's lower level of development are not yet explored in the literature as challenges to social sustainability. This could be that the literature gives more attention to direct organizational challenges and often at times generalise observations without taking into consideration where the company operates i.e., with context and the nature of the context of operation.

Another possible explanation that could be obvious to the researcher is that these can be specific challenges to the agricultural sectors of LMICs – Cameroon where many factors such as cultural issues (i.e., higher levels of corruption and tribalism), low level of technological advancement, slow and inconsistent developmental structures are a continuing issue.

Figure 11 Current State of Challenges in the Cameroonian Manufacturing Industry

Challenges to Social Sustainability Adoption
1. Inadequate resources and adaptive capabilities
2. Inadequate understanding and knowledge of the importance of social sustainability
3. Intermediaries and third parties
4. Culture (corruption, tribalism and resistant to change)
5. Inadequate basic infrastructures and social amenities
6. country's lower level of development
7. CSR projects are not effective

source: empirical data

5.6.1.2 Propose Social Sustainability Framework Measures for the Agricultural Supply Chain

For agribusiness companies to fully incorporate social sustainability into their supply chains, it is essential to first identify the relevant challenges before adopting the necessary measures (Yarwar and Seuring, 2015). This may lead to certain changes in the already existing business procedures and the eventual development of new products and processes (Khan et al. 2021).

5.6.1.2.1 Stakeholder Engagement

Engaging stakeholders is an important measure of social sustainability. Social sustainability in supply chains encompasses the safety and wellness of people, it also involves primary stakeholders; employees, suppliers, and customers, and secondary stakeholders (communities

and NGOs) (Mani et al. 2016; Davies et al. 2019) in SCM. It has become a common route for engaging with stakeholders to ensure they get involved in every stage of the supply chain even at the decision-making phase (Huq et al., 2014).

To achieve this goal, agribusiness companies need to give stakeholder precedence by creating an environment that facilitates firm-stakeholder dialogue addressing their common interest to ensure strong and sustained relationships. As a necessary step, companies should engage stakeholders on issues related to “sustainability, their concerns, planned actions, decision-making, and performance updates” (Rinaldi et al., 2014).

In addition to the incorporation of stakeholder management as an important social improvement measure, agribusiness companies will also be in a better position to mitigate supply chain-related risks, reputational risks, and a better picture of their business surrounding and the resistant challenges. This could be an approach used by agribusiness companies to learn and at the same time involve stakeholders for the best interest of the concern. This could lead to trust building and confidence, and promoting transparency (Rinaldi et al., 2014).

5.6.1.2.2 Integration of Sustainability into Corporate Policy

Socially sustainable supply chains are often focused on sustainable SCM and are more likely to incorporate societal needs and expectations into their business strategies. The purpose of this is not just a responsive stance toward increasing stakeholder demands to address social issues but to also gain a competitive advantage (Mani et al., 2020). However, a starting point to reflect adherence to effective sustainability practices significantly linked to corporate policy starts with the commitment of top management (Huq et al., 2014).

The commitment of top management is an important aspect of the incorporation of continually beneficial socially sustainable SCM practices. Redesigning supply chains with a social focus necessitates the commitment of top management and higher levels of decision-making. Also,

it requires creating awareness and formalizing the corporate sustainability vision to reflect corporate culture and values solely reliant on the commitment of top management embodied in the corporate policy (Huq et al. 2014; Khan et al. 2021).

Currently, agricultural companies are more into ISO and QMS standards, which are aspects captured under the sustainability phenomena and are crucial in achieving social sustainability in SCM. Incorporating social sustainability into supply chain processes will require developing innovative ideas and techniques, educating, and creating awareness among the various stakeholder groups about the corporate sustainability policy (Davies, Haugh, and Chambers, 2019; Morais and Silvestre; 2018).

The incorporation of social sustainability in SCM into corporate policy by agribusiness companies will be a major significant move towards enhancing social sustainability. This will enable top-to-bottom communication of goals and expectations regarding social sustainability. For this to be achieved, it will entail significant clarification as to the meaning, perception, and plans to incorporate social sustainability, and the need for educational programs designed for the promotion and benefits of sustainability to both internal and external stakeholders (Davies, Haugh, and Chambers, 2019; Morais and Silvestre; 2018).

5.6.1.2.3 Collaboration with Host Communities

Focal collaboration with host communities is an essential aspect of addressing social issues (Vurro et al., 2009; Gimenez and Sierra, 2013), No matter the context, collaboration and the active participation of communities have been considered to significantly advance the sustainability prospects (Koontz, 2006). The supply chain's social sustainability mostly involves stakeholder engagement (Hutchins and Sutherland 2008). These engagements might involve sponsoring or aiding in developmental programs in local sourcing communities or

engaging to jointly develop partnerships or collaborative schemes for the host community (Rondinelli and Berry 2000).

Collaborative initiatives are known for achieving enhanced social sustainability (Gimenez and Sierra, 2013). Even effective collaboration helps improve corporate perception by the communities (Hutchins and Sutherland 2008; Mani, Agrawal, and Sharma, 2016). Thus, with the evolving nature of challenges linked to social issues, companies must engage in collaborative ways with their host communities. This is a necessary way to avoid conflicting stakeholders' interests paving the way for constructive and improved relationships where members reach mutual agreements beneficial for either party.

As social sustainability measures bring about transformational partnerships with communities, companies should consider integrating this as a major aspect of their sustainability agenda. While collaboration with stakeholders can be viewed from different directions (i.e., from philanthropic engagements to standard forms of stakeholder engagement), it is imperative to achieve societal and SDGs.

Figure 12 Social Sustainability Framework for the Cameroonian Agribusiness Companies (VI)

5.6.1.2.4 Education and Awareness Programme

With regards to social sustainability enhancing initiatives, in most cases, no visible outcome exists between action and impact on social sustainability. This is attributed to the complex

process through which social actions often follow making it challenging even for those responsible for the action to trace its effectiveness (Azapagic 2000). Thus, at times there is a disconnect between action and impact on social issues in communities. This inadequate awareness and understanding of the implications of social issues signifies a knowledge gap on social sustainability that can be addressed via education on social sustainability.

Also, in LMICs focal firms often go beyond corporate limits for sustainability in supply chains to create stakeholders' awareness of safe practices with the primary objective of enhancing social sustainability (Silvestre 2015). As a key influence for social sustainability, creating awareness and designing programs to educate and encourage communities on the relevance of social sustainability practices will not only benefit these communities but these companies as well.

5.6.1.2.5 Lean and Agile Social Supply Chain Measures

Lean practice is supposed to identify and eliminate all forms of waste in the production system for improvement (Shah and Ward, 2007), and agility is the ability to respond to changing market dynamics (Parera et al., 2014).

The lean 4P model by TOYOTA emphasis “people, process, philosophy (purpose), and problem-solving” (Alves et al., 2012). The people element emphasizes developing people. People are central to lean thinking, and without their commitment, and workplace knowledge, it will be difficult to achieve benefits in the long run. Thus, it seems logical to say lean management supposes “customer-centric thinking i.e., delivering the highest quality product, at the lowest cost, with the shortest lead time, in the safest manner, all while respecting people. This aspect of delivering value most safely and respecting people suggests moving toward the social aspects (health, safety and wellbeing, labour practices, equitable wages) of lean management. The problem-solving aspect is the ability to identify problems in advance.

Sustainability is a key issue nowadays and recognizing the need to incorporate it into business processes is becoming crucial due to pressures from stakeholders (Mani et al., 2016). Therefore, the problem-solving aspect can be considered as developing sustainable processes that are in line with stakeholders' demands and regulatory authorities. Finally, the processes part of the 4P model emphasises standardizing processes in case of diversion that can easily be tracked and adjusted. The standardization of processes is necessary for health and safety certifications such as OHSAS18000, which will lead to better working conditions for the employees and thus make the organization socially sustainable”.

Teece (2007) defined agility based on three dynamic capabilities including sense, seize, and reconfiguration. “That is “sense” means the ability to search for opportunities and threats, “seizing” means identifying potential market changes and tuning the current product portfolio or developing new products, and “reconfiguration” capability refers to modifying production routines and configuring suppliers. Agility enables a firm to develop a relationship with buyers and suppliers and helps in spotting market changes using collaborative efforts and reconfiguration of resources to address the change. Such a process helps the firms to identify and capitalize on market opportunities, which in turn enhances a firm’s adaptive capability (Wang and Ahmed, 2007; Parera et al., 2014). Furthermore, Teece et al. (1997); Wang and Ahmed (2007); Barreto (2009); Parera et al. (2014) argued information exchange improves learning at the firm and supply chain level. Wang and Ahmed (2007) argued that learning enhances an organisation's absorptive capability by enabling them to recognize, assimilate and utilize new knowledge. Knowledge is required to be innovative, and agile firms possess innovation capability as they synthesize innovative solutions to respond to the changing market conditions (Agarwal and Tiwari, 2007), and such new knowledge ultimately influences the social sustainability of the firm. Thus, agility helps a firm to sense social sustainability needs,

and sensing the need for social sustainability leads to the development of social sustainability initiatives” (Marshall et al., 2015).

The adoption of both lean and agile social sustainability strategies by agribusiness companies will be useful for enhancing social sustainability performance via the mitigation, quick, and dynamic responses to social sustainability issues.

5.6.1.2.6 Transparency

Cameroon ranks high relative to the most corrupt countries in the world. Corruption is a widespread practice and a well-known issue recognized in the country. Most often attributed to one of the factors responsible for the country’s current lower level of development notwithstanding the country’s endowment with natural resources.

Transparency in business necessitates openness prohibits all hidden agendas and conditions and supports the accessibility to accurate data to affect a joint and informed decision-making process. Transparency supposes the accessibility of product and process aspects which allows stakeholders to access accurate and important data (Mani et al. 2018b; Toussaint et al. (2020). Nowadays, supply chain transparency is often triggered either by regulatory requirements or pressure from stakeholders to be well-informed on corporate practices. Companies in LMICs integrating aspects of transparency in the supply chain are likely to adhere to their sustainability commitment (Toussaint et al., 2020). Transparency of corporate operations and processes in the agricultural sector will help improve corporate stakeholders’ relationships as well as ensure their adherence to sustainability enactments.

5.6.1.2.7 Wealth Creation Programmes

Reducing poverty is considered critical to attaining sustainable development at a global scale, particularly in LMICs like Cameroon where poverty, unemployment, and inadequate basic amenities are a major cause for concern (World Bank, 2018).

Corporate philanthropic initiatives are relevant to supporting government efforts to provide social amenities and, in this case, individual developmental schemes that can empower community members, especially women for a better life (Hutchins and Sutherland 2008). As a social sustainability measure, the company's commitment to wealth creation programs designed to ameliorate living conditions and community empowerment, will help fight against poverty, reduce unemployment in these communities as well as enhance corporate-community relationships.

5.6.2 Framework Validation

Validation shows the extent to the applicability of an instrument. The instrument is the framework designed to enhance social sustainability in SCM in the Cameroonian agricultural sector. Validating entails assessing the content of the framework relative to the purpose of its measures. This involved the applicability of the proposed framework alongside the measures for improving social sustainability for the sector. Special care was given to its content validity. Content validity supposes the extent to which an item in a measure reflects the content it assesses (Rubio et al. 2003). It can be achieved through face validity which supposes the relevance of a measure "at face value" and logical validity entailing experts' assessing the validity of the measures (Rubio et al. 2003). Content validity also allowed improvement via feedback from subject experts' evaluation.

Taking into consideration the purpose of this research and the expected outcome: improving SCM via social sustainability, the proposed framework was open for corrections and improvements following sector opinion. This supposes that the framework was not limited to academic purposes only, but also portrays its usefulness in the agricultural supply chain. The validation process was iterative involving academic and corporate experts' judgement. This

ensured the framework was precise and easily understandable. This resulted in the development of two more versions of the framework following expert feedback.

To commence with the evaluation, expert opinion and judgment were sought after. Two experts on SCM were consulted for the first proposed framework (version 1(V1)). Their comments and opinions informed the second proposed framework (version 2 (V2)).

Feedback received from proposed V1 was attached to a worksheet explaining the framework and proposed measures for easy understanding; To expatiate the links shown by the arrows in the framework to clearly explain to managers and their role in incorporating social sustainability. An improved version (V2) was returned to experts to ensure the feedback was correctly integrated (Pati et al., 2016; Richardson, 2005). Version two was then forwarded to corporate executives to find out its relevance and necessary feedback on proposed measures.

Figure 13 Social Sustainability Framework for the Cameroonian Manufacturing Sector (V2).

Figure 5.3 captures the improved framework following subject experts' feedback. The framework depicts the social sustainability enhancement area alongside measures for this improvement.

Sending the proposed framework to the companies was a major element in the validation process particularly important to ensure the relevance of the framework for the agribusiness companies (Schwartz et al., 2008). Since the framework is considered a tool that can guide practitioners in improving supply chains via social sustainability improvement it was important for deliberation to centre around the relevance and applicability of the framework to agribusiness companies. To achieve this goal i.e., to obtain feedback on the relevance and applicability of the framework to agribusiness companies, eight executives were contacted (four supply chain managers, two operations managers, one CSR manager, one Quality, health, and safety manager) from the case organizations who can take strategic decisions that can influence sustainable supply chain practices. Phone consultation meetings were initiated, and the research purpose and framework were discussed. Ensuring an understanding of the validation exercise. Subsequently, the improved version 2 framework was emailed to them with an attached worksheet detailing a description of the framework and measures and feedback questions related to the framework. The purpose of the questions was to assess the “accuracy, completeness, feasibility, and acceptability” of the framework on yes or no options. A deadline was fixed to conduct feedback interviews on the framework and the return of the framework feedback responses. Seven out of eight feedback questions were returned completed. The completed response showed the degree of acceptability of the framework as shown in table 5.2. Comments were made on the framework, and these were further deliberated at the interview stage of the validation process. Afterward, telephone interviews were conducted with each of the selected respondents. The focus of the interview questions was on the responses from the feedback question on the applicability of the framework in the sector as well as the willingness of the agribusiness companies to adopt the framework was a major point of the discussion.

Table 16 Feedback Showing the Perception of Practitioners on the Proposed Framework

	Agreeability of Proposed Framework				
Improving the supply chain via social sustainability	Accurate	Complete	Feasibility	Cost Acceptability	Appropriateness of measures
	Yes	Yes	Yes	no	Yes

5.6.2.1 Validation of the Framework

Responses from interviews demonstrated the accuracy of the proposed measures based on responses of yes, yes, yes, no, and yes for social sustainability improvement as presented in Table 5.1. suppose the framework is accurate and addresses most of the social sustainability challenges in the agricultural sector.

The interview response also suggests the proposed measures are feasible following a “yes” response indicating respondent agrees to that. This demonstrated a unanimity in the preparedness of the agribusiness moving towards a socially sustainable SCM in the agricultural sector.

Also, respondents agreed on the need for realizable performance indicators to evaluate progress. Although the incorporation of social sustainability is important, it is also imperative to have a scale of indicators for social sustainability in supply to monitor progress against impacting social sustainability initiatives across the supply chain.

Regarding the implementation cost, the response from informants was “no”. The argument raised by respondents was that most initiatives may require multi-stakeholder participation especially when such initiatives extend beyond corporate limits, considering most organizations do not even have the resources to sustain their proper operations. Furthermore,

emphasis was made on the fact that Cameroon is an LMIC which will require plenty of support from external actors.

Regarding the completeness of the framework, some recommendations were proposed, and minor corrections to the framework were made which further improves Figure 5.3 and eventually figure 5.4. This recommendation and changes were received and emphasized during the interviews. Some of the major points raised are.

- Emphasis was made on the fact that for there to be more impact in the local communities regarding social improvements, the government needs to be actively involved. As well as support from other developmental organisations for social improvement to be effectively achieved.
- Repositioning the Cameroonian government in the framework in a middle position between focal firms and local communities for social sustainability improvement in the agricultural supply chain.

Generally, the informant restated that looking at the potential benefits that accompany socially sustainable SCM from the agribusiness company (s) and its stakeholders, incorporating the proposed framework is important as it assists agribusiness companies to re-strategize their operations to be more competing and socially performing supply chains.

Figure 5.4 Social Sustainability framework for the Cameroonian Agricultural Sector (Version 3 Validated).

5.7 Performance Indicators for Social Sustainability

To ascertain the enhancement of social sustainability in SCM by agribusiness companies, it is important to produce a tool that will enable a frame to assess progress. Integrating such a framework will ensure there are visible improvements in process and product aspects of companies for social sustainability which can be traced, assessed, and modified for improvement (Varèse et al., 2014).

Indicators give updates on the current position on the dimensions of social sustainability. Indicators are tools that can be observed or assessed. As a usual procedure in benchmarking, it will be necessary for indicators adopted to be gathered and analyzed continually for a certain period to achieve the complete benefits of incorporating social sustainability SCM practices (Ahi and Searcy, 2015).

Table 17 Metrics for Social Sustainability Framework in the Agricultural Sector

Areas for Social Sustainability Improvement	Metrics	Information provided by the metric	Unit
<p>Stakeholder Engagement</p> <p><i>Short Term Improvement</i></p> <p><i>Impact Area; Significant impact in the assessment, planning, and reduction/mitigation of negative effects on surrounding communities (GRI, 2016)</i></p> <p><i>Targets based on avoiding or decreasing the negative effects of supply chain activities on stakeholders (local communities) with the overall objective of fostering a cordial relationship with stakeholders and ensuring a safe environment and socio-economic atmosphere (GRI 2016)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of meetings/consultations with stakeholders. • Number of stakeholder complaints received. • Several stakeholder grievances were addressed. 	<p>Total number of meetings with local communities regarding company activities and operations</p> <p>Several complaints and issues were raised by local communities regarding company operations.</p> <p>Total number of local community grievances addressed successfully and satisfactorily</p>	<p>Number/Year</p> <p>Number/Year</p> <p>Number/year</p>
<p>Sustainability Integration into Corporate Policy</p> <p><i>Short Term Improvement</i></p> <p><i>Impact Area: Significant impact in the redesigning of Cameroon agribusiness companies to reflect a sustainability-focused value-adding process and products</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several sustainability strategies were implemented. • Type and scope of organizational policy towards sustainable social sustainability. 	<p>Several strategies were implemented to enhance social sustainability across the supply chain.</p> <p>Management approach and policies enacted towards the achievement of a socially sustainable supply chain.</p>	<p>Number/year</p> <p>Descriptive</p>

<p><i>facilitated by corporate sustainability policy.</i></p> <p><i>Targets based on the integration of sustainability goals into company policy to ensure the effective adoption and practice of SSCM via a trickle-down process from top management down to lower cadre employees. (GRI 2016, Huq et., 2014)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage of revamped supply chain activities to enhance social sustainability. • Percentage of budget earmarked for sustainability improvement 	<p>Percentage and type of supply chain processes and activities that have been revamped for the achievement of a socially sustainable supply chain.</p> <p>Percentage of budget allocated for improving sustainability across the supply chain</p>	<p>Percentage Descriptive</p> <p>Monetary unit/year</p>
<p>Collaborations with Host communities</p> <p><i>Short Term Improvement</i></p> <p><i>Impact Area: Significant impact on relationships with communities and establishing communication and collaboration pathways between agribusiness firms and key interest groups in the surrounding communities.</i></p> <p><i>Targets based on increasing the number of development programs and partnership schemes between agribusiness companies and surrounding communities with the overall benefit of improved engagement with communities and socio-economic development (GRI 2016, Khan et al., 2020)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several development programs focused on communities' needs and interests. • Collaborations with communities • Community involvement in the decision-making process 	<p>Several corporate-sponsored initiatives aimed at improving the quality of life in surrounding communities.</p> <p>Type and scope of collaborative initiatives with surrounding communities aimed at improving corporate-community relationships.</p> <p>Commitment to surrounding community involvement in the decision-making process</p>	<p>Number/year</p> <p>Descriptive</p> <p>Descriptive</p>
<p>Education Awareness Programs</p> <p><i>Long Term Improvement</i></p> <p><i>Impact Area; Significant impact on mitigating issues of child and bonded labour, gender issues, and ethical practices on local sourcing</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investment in educating local communities on social sustainability practices. 	<p>Total investment in creating awareness and a learning platform for local communities on the importance of social sustainability practices.</p>	<p>Monetary unit /year</p> <p>Number/year</p>

<p><i>partners via improved social sustainability awareness and knowledge across local communities</i></p> <p><i>Targets are based on increasing resources towards, several education awareness programs and active stakeholder engagement processes focused on sustainability awareness, impacts, and improvement (GRI 2016, Silvestre 2015).</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of awareness programs undertaken. • Feedback from local sourcing communities on awareness programs. 	<p>Total number of awareness and educational programs undertaken.</p> <p>Feedback and comments from stakeholders indicating the effectiveness of the program.</p>	<p>Descriptive</p>
<p>Wealth Creation Programs</p> <p><i>Long Term Improvement</i></p> <p><i>Impact Area; Significant impact in socio-economic empowerment via human-capital development; job creation, skill development, scholarships, and community empowerment programmes</i></p> <p><i>Targets based on improving skills, and socio-economic development of local communities with the overall benefit of reducing poverty, unemployment, and entrepreneurship (GRI 2016)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indirect benefit accrued by local communities per unit value added. • Direct benefits to local communities per unit value added. • Total investment in entrepreneurial programs 	<p>Indirect benefits accrued by local communities because of the company's operations.</p> <p>Direct benefits accrued by local communities because of the company's operations.</p> <p>Investment in wealth creation, entrepreneurial, and empowering programs in local communities</p>	<p>Monetary unit /value added.</p> <p>Monetary unit /value added.</p> <p>Monetary unit /year</p>
<p>Transparency</p> <p><i>Short Term Improvement</i></p> <p><i>Impact Area; Significant impact on development and supply chain efficiency through improved communication and information sharing, resource availability, and management</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The company's policy on openness and transparency • Number of trainings given on company's anti-corruption policy Number of prosecutions for corrupt practices. 	<p>Policy on information dissemination to suppliers and local communities</p> <p>Total number of trainings given to employees (all cadre) on company's anticorruption policies and standards</p>	<p>Descriptive</p> <p>Number/year</p> <p>Number/year</p>

<p><i>Targets based on increased openness and anticorruption policies with the overall objective of supplier and stakeholder engagement, in fairness and eliminating misappropriation of resources (GRI 2016; Zorzini et al. (2015))</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number and nature of discipline for incidents of corruption in the organization. • Several contracts with suppliers were terminated for corruption. • The number of corruption-related legal cases against the organisation and its employees. 	<p>A total number of prosecutions conducted by organisations internally and externally for corrupt practices.</p> <p>Total number of confirmed corruption incidents in the organisation in the recording period and actions taken</p> <p>A total number of contracts with suppliers terminated or discontinued by organisation due to violations related to openness and corruption.</p> <p>Total number of corruption-related legal cases brought against the organisation or its employees by the public and its outcome</p>	<p>Number/year Descriptive</p> <p>Number/year Descriptive</p> <p>Number/year Descriptive</p>
<p>Adopting Lean and Agile Supply Chain</p> <p><i>Long Term Improvement</i></p> <p><i>Impact Area; Significant impact on products and processes improving social sustainability performance through mitigation of social issues and supply chain responsiveness.</i></p> <p><i>Targets are based on engaging/involving people, standardizing procedures, and developing and possessing dynamic and innovative capabilities in response to changing market conditions (Nath and Agrawal, 2020; Perera et al. 2019; El-Khalil and Mezher, 2020).</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process management/planning • Acknowledge the significance of employees in the organization by developing their teamwork, training, and educational skills. • Response rate • Competence/efficiency 	<p>Process management/planning incorporates developing a plan that can guide daily decisions. Savings are made by eliminating waste and value-added.</p> <p>Number, type, and scope of programs implemented to develop personal skills and knowledge management.</p> <p>Quick response to stakeholder demands. It is the ability to Respond quickly to changing stakeholder demands.</p>	<p>Descriptive</p> <p>Descriptive number/year</p> <p>Number/year</p> <p>Descriptive”</p>

		This entails how efficient and effective organization's capabilities are used to achieve social sustainability	
--	--	--	--

Sources; developed and adapted from GRI (2016), Silvestre (2015), Nath and Agrawal (2020), Perera et al. (2019), El-Khalil and Mezher (2020) Khan et al. (2020) and Huq et. (2014)

5.8 Summary

The chapter assessed social sustainability in SCM relative to literature with the analyzed data from the 5 case organizations to the study objectives. After which a framework for improving social sustainability in SCM was developed. The next step assessed the applicability of proposed measures for improving socially sustainable practices by the agribusiness companies. Thereafter was the framework validation achieved through deliberations and recommendations from subject experts and corporate managers from the agribusiness companies. At the end of the chapter, a framework validated in the agricultural sector is achieved to enhance socially sustainable supply chain practices and metrics to measure, monitor, and assess progress.

Chapter Six – Conclusion

6.1 introduction

This chapter discusses how the research aim and objectives were achieved, and the implications of this thesis relevant to knowledge and practice. It further identifies the research limitations and proposes recommendations for future research.

6.2 Meeting the Aim and Objectives of this Thesis.

To achieve the aim of this research (i.e., to explore the strategic implementation of social sustainability on improving supply chain management in the agriculture sector of a lower-middle income country and to develop and validate a framework for implementing improvement on social sustainability in supply chain management.), at the introductory chapter, the researcher identified several objectives that were achieved and discussed throughout the thesis. These are summarised in Table 6.1 below and then discussed in the following paragraph.

Table 18 meets the aim and objectives of this research.

Objectives	Section	Key outcome
Objective 1	Section: 1.4, 4.3 and Appendix H	To understand the current trends of social sustainability in SCM in developing countries
Objective 2	Section: 1.4, 2.1.3.1, 2.1.3.2, 2.1.3.3, 4.4.1a&b, 4.4.2a&b, 4.4.4a&b, 4.4.5(1-6) and 5.6.1.1	To identify the drivers, principles, and barriers to social sustainability in supply chain management practices in the Cameroonian agricultural sector.
Objective 3	Section: 1.4, 4.5 and 5.4 (1-6)	To identify typologies for the implementation and management of social sustainability initiatives in the agricultural supply chain for Cameroon.

Objective 4	Section: 1.4, 2.1.3., 4.4.4 and 5.5 (1-3)	To analyse the benefits of social sustainability on the entire supply chain.
Objective 5	Section: 1.4, 4.4.5(1-6), 4.4.6, 5.6.1, 5.6.2 and 5.7	To Develop a framework to evaluate and enhance the Cameroonian agricultural sectors' social sustainability SCM practices.

- **Objective 1: To critically examine the existing trends of social sustainability in SCM in developing countries.**

After the critical analysis of the literature, the research problem identified and highlighted social sustainability in SCM as a rich and potential avenue for research in developing countries attractive many researchers. This research has identified ongoing trends as researchers continue to explore this interesting social phenomenon in developing sections 1.4, 4.3, and Appendix H.

- **Objective 2: To identify the drivers, principles, and barriers to social sustainability in supply chain management practices in the Cameroonian agricultural sector.**

After the critical analysis of the literature, the researcher recognized and identified the lack of knowledge and understanding of social sustainability about drivers, principles, and barriers to social sustainability along the agricultural supply chain (maybe country-specific) as a requirement for agribusiness company executives to improve their business processes. This has been investigated, analyzed, and developed in this research within the agricultural supply chain in sections 2.1.3.1, 2.1.3.2, 2.1.3.3, 4.4.1a&b, 4.4.2a&b, 4.4.4a&b, 4.4.5(1-6) and 5.6.1.1

- *Objective 3: To critically analyze the implementation and management of social sustainability initiatives in the agricultural supply chain for Cameroon.*

Based on the literature review, the implementation and management of social sustainability in supply chains appeared to be business situational which is a combination of organization and business environment. The research problem identified and highlighted research gaps in knowledge on agricultural supply chain implementation and social sustainability in developing countries. This has been investigated and analyzed in this research within the agricultural section in Cameroon sections 2.1.3, 4.5, and 5.4 (1-6)

- *Objective 4: To analyze the benefits of social sustainability on the entire supply chain.*

After the critical analysis of the literature, the researcher recognized and identified that the development of measures for social sustainability benefits along the agricultural supply chain (maybe country-specific) is a requirement for agribusiness company executives to improve their business processes. This has been investigated, analyzed, and developed in this research within the agricultural supply chain in sections 2.1.3., 4.4.4, and 5.5 (1-3)

- *Objective 5: To develop a framework to improve social sustainability in the supply chain of selected companies in the Cameroon manufacturing sector.*

Based on the literature review and critical analysis of the current state of challenges on social sustainability adoption and implementation in the agricultural sector, the researcher identified a gap in the need for a framework to adequately assess how socially sustainable the agricultural supply chain is (maybe country-specific). A framework to estimate agricultural social sustainability is necessary to appraise how the social sustainability efforts of agribusiness

companies are progressing. The framework has been developed in the research within the agricultural sector in sections 4.4.5(1-6), 4.4.6, 5.6.1, 5.6.2 and 5.7.

6.3 Research Implications

6.3.1. Implications to Theory

The continued emphasis on sustainable operations and services globally puts supply chains at the centre of discussion and the agricultural supply chain remains one of the most talked about sectors. Thus, the locally based agricultural sector is also included in the sustainability agenda. This research examines local understanding of the implementation of social sustainability practices in SCM. The aim of the research explore the strategic implementation of social sustainability in improving supply chain management in the agriculture sector of a lower-middle income country and develop and validate a framework for implementing improvement on social sustainability in supply chain management. This represents a new area of work. It is an extension to gain more knowledge on the social dimension of sustainability in the agricultural sector as no work has been done in this specific area at the moment. The research used SRBV and the Contingency theory of strategic management to advance understanding of this phenomenon. The contributions of this research study to the body of knowledge are highlighted below.

The review of the extant literature showed that sustainability practices about the social dimension are still underexplored as well as some companies/managers lack an understanding of how to implement them in the local agricultural supply chain. Notwithstanding the increasing popularity of sustainability in the agricultural sector and growing demand for sustainable production and consumption of agricultural commodities. This research work adds to the body of knowledge on social sustainability in SCM in the agricultural sector as most

research studies on the sector are usually focused on integrating environmental aspects in SCM.

This research extends prior studies towards the development of social sustainability in SCM (Bubicz and Carvalho, 2021; Morais and Barbieri, 2022) by exploring the “why and how” organizations manage and implement social sustainability in developing countries (Mani et al., 2018). While prior studies on social sustainability management in developing countries have mostly focused on large multinational companies in emerging economies with a cross-sectoral perspective (e.g., Morais and Barbieri 2018), others (Mani and Gunaselaran, 2018) are generic and often focus on developed country perspectives. Perspectives in developing countries, especially from LMICs are relevant and needed indicating a more inclusive understanding of social sustainability in LMICs is required. This research focused on LMICs (i.e., Cameroon) sector-specific (agriculture) on the implementation of social sustainability on improving SCM. This research contributes to filling this gap by demonstrating how and why agribusiness companies in Cameroon strategically implement and manage social sustainability in the supply chains.

This research enumerates the drivers, principles, barriers, and benefits of social sustainability SCM practices in the local agricultural supply chain. These aspects are unique to the case study country and are particularly responsible for the motivation, impediments, level of engagement, and the implications to social sustainability SCM practices in the sector. This knowledge is earlier and is essential for implementing social sustainability in SCM as it enables to identification of improvement areas for the attainment of an enhanced socially performing supply chain.

Through the stakeholders theory (instrumental view), this research confirms stakeholders' influence on the implementation of social sustainability in the entire supply chain. The research

confirms the work of Nguyen et al. (2021) who revealed that the drivers vary based on the supply chain tier depending on the different stakeholders' influence and further show that, these different stakeholders not only influence the drivers based on the tier but also the strategic approach used to implement the social sustainability initiatives. Although regulatory pressure appears to be the most common pressure, this study shows that companies seeking to expand market access beyond local boundaries invest more in social responsibility practices than others. This finding aligns with the work of Koksal et al. (2018) but contradicts Hug et al. (2014) who argue that companies that intend to expand their market reach beyond local boundaries only invest in social responsibility practices to compete against rival products abroad. Thus, such investments in social responsibility practices can be argued as a risk transfer method as it does not benefit all the stakeholders involved. With regards to ethical-based drivers, these research findings are contrary to those (Bilowol and Doan 2015; Tran and Jeppesen 2016) as such drivers are the least common. This is because local agribusiness companies are investing in social responsibility practices for financial motives.

With regards to the resource-based view (RBV) theory, the research confirms the benefits of organizational learning regarding social sustainability practices across the supply chain with the implication of significant competitive advantage achieved through social and supply chain performance in the agribusiness sector.

Attention to the contingency theory has recently increased (Walker and Jones; Golicic et al., 2019; Morais and Barbieri, 2022) and argues that each business situation is contextual and requires unique solutions. Firms must vary if they are to effectively survive with different environmental circumstances. This study supports this theory and argues that the implementation of social sustainability initiatives is contingent upon the environment in which the companies operate. These variations exist based on the resource needs of the different stakeholders. Morais and Barbieri (2022) followed a similar approach to examine how

contingency factors influence the extent to which companies implement governance mechanisms to address social issues in supply chains. This research findings align with Walker and Jones (2012) who used internal and external enablers and barriers to develop a typology of approaches to sustainable SCM. The research goes beyond organisational enablers to include principles and relational levels to develop a typology of strategic approaches for the implementation of social sustainability in SCM.

6.3.2 Implication to practice

This research offers significant implications for agribusiness companies as it reinforces the importance of social sustainability in support of the assertion that genuine management actions might lead to significant and permanent sustainability results. It goes beyond the conception that social sustainability is still “a mere philanthropic activity” and not a major sustainability dimension for organizations. This research draws a full picture of social sustainability practice by linking the drivers, barriers, principles, social dimensions, improvement measures, and performance benefits to the entire supply chain. This study is one of the first in the sector as such practitioners will have firsthand information on drivers, impediments and principles for engaging social sustainability practices and a better management of social sustainability initiatives leads to social and operational benefits in the supply chain. For example, social sustainability initiatives proved to enhance the level of professionalism demanded by market actors and boost economic opportunity for the companies. Signifying agribusiness companies and manager should strengthen social sustainability practices in their supply chains. In addition to the knowledge of drivers, barriers, and mechanisms of social sustainability practices, the agricultural sector can be a promoter of good practice and predict opportunities and challenges likely to be faced to improve social sustainability in their supply chains. Other companies may learn from the implications of implementing social sustainability practices in their

organizations and supply chain performance. In this direction, companies could design suitable sustainability strategies to enable their social sustainability initiatives and to improve their supply chain performance. A lead organization may use social sustainability as a collaborative mechanism with suppliers to procure materials free from social-related risk and uncertainty.

These research results have shown that the drivers of social sustainability initiatives have a significant influence on the principle used for engaging the initiatives and the extent of applicability of such initiatives. Gaining knowledge of this influence is particularly important to agribusiness companies and managers in understanding how the implementation of social sustainability initiatives can be reengineered for social sustainability improvement and supply chain performance. The agribusiness companies and managers can adopt the typology developed in this research to understand the drivers of each type of social sustainability initiative and how to engage initiatives for social and performance improvements. For example, to implement social sustainability initiatives designed to address supplier social issues to minimize supply chain-related social risk, agribusiness companies and managers will be required to engage with their suppliers using both collaborative and assessment strategies at the relationship level of the focal firm and supplier. Practically, adapting and evaluating this typology will benefit both managers and academicians as the proposed model can change with time to fit into the constantly evolving business milieu and mindset of decision-makers. Also, being aware of the link between driver, principle, and extent of applicability of social initiative is particularly important to Cameroon. This is because it helps identify the limits of the agricultural sector's capabilities when managing some of its supply chain social sustainability issues. This is also important for improving the image and perception of agribusiness firms by the public.

Finally, a major implication of this study to the agribusiness companies and managers is the social sustainability enhancing framework developed. The developed framework is particularly designed for the agricultural sector. The successful adoption and implementation of this framework with its proposed measures by the agribusiness companies will enable them to develop a social strategy that would help improve social sustainability in SCM and enhance their competitive positions as well as their corporate-stakeholder relationship. I will share a summary of the current research results with the participants, and I intend to publish my research findings in the *International Journal of Production Economy* and the *International Journal of Cleaner Production*.

6.4 Limitations and Recommendations for Further Research

This research explored the strategy of social sustainability in improving the supply chain of selected agribusiness companies. Despite the relevance of this study to the agricultural sector and the additional knowledge in social sustainability, this research has limitations. This study explored exemplary case organisations and from the empirical analysis, the results showed just slightly above the average of all the social initiatives launched in consideration of the ethical/moral principles and values of the organisations. The research argues this could be lower i.e., far below average for non-exemplar organisations, and suggest organisations are presently focusing their social sustainability initiatives for the wrong motives (that is for financial gains). Future research can focus on investigating “why and how non-exemplar organisations implement and manage social sustainability in their supply chains”.

Although data from exemplary case organisation were gathered, the whole dataset was generated in one country (i.e., Cameroon) and a single sector (i.e., agriculture), indicating a limitation for this study. Future research can be done in multiple settings and cross-sectors to

assess the generalizability of this research results. Thus, future studies should expand the scope of the research by comparing the findings in various developing nations.

Another limitation of this qualitative multiple-case study is the small sample size. The small sample size used may not represent the entire agricultural sector in Cameroon. Future research can be conducted with a quantitative or mixed methodology to obtain data from a much larger sample. Future research can also study strategies used by locally based agribusiness companies and multinational agribusiness companies to implement social sustainability in supply chains. Strategies used by local agribusiness companies are likely to be different from strategies used by multinational agribusiness firms.

6.5 Summary

This thesis investigated an overlooked dimension of sustainability in the agricultural supply chain, thus significantly having implications for theory and practice. The study also researched social sustainability in the context of country-specific characteristics. Five case organizations from the agricultural sector of lower medium-income countries were evaluated for this study.

This thesis has contributed to the SSCM field and specifically the agricultural sector by exploring the strategic implementation of social sustainability in improving supply chains and the outcome of a framework for enhancing social sustainability in the Cameroonian agricultural sector.

The thesis designed questions, aim, and objectives have been achieved. The researcher is convinced the effective adoption of the developed framework in the Cameroonian agricultural sector will help deliver social sustainability improvements in supply chain management practices.

References

- Aberdeen, T. (2013) “Yin, R. K. (2009). Case study research: Design and methods (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, ca: Sage.,” *The Canadian Journal of Action Research*, 14(1), pp. 69–71. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.33524/cjar.v14i1.73>.
- Agarwal, A. and Tiwari, M. (2007), “Modelling agility of supply chain”, *Industrial Marketing Management*, Vol. 36, pp. 443-457.
- Agyemang, M. et al. (2020) ‘Determining and evaluating socially sustainable supply chain criteria in agri-sector of Developing Countries: Insights from West Africa cashew industry’, *Production Planning & Control*, 33(11), pp. 1115–1133. doi:10.1080/09537287.2020.1852479.
- Ahmadi, H. B., S. Kusi-Sarpong, and J. Rezaei.2017. “Assessing the Social Sustainability of Supply Chains Using Best Worst Method.” *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*126:99–106.
- Agle, B.R. and Caldwell, C.B. (1999) “Understanding research on values in business,” *Business & Society*, 38(3), pp. 326–387. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/000765039903800305>.
- Ahi, P. and Searcy, C. (2013) “A comparative literature analysis of definitions for Green and Sustainable Supply Chain Management,” *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 52, pp. 329–341. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.02.018>.
- Ali, S. and Kaur, R., 2021. Effectiveness of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in implementation of social sustainability in warehousing of developing countries: A hybrid approach. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 324, p.129154.

- Ahi, P. and Searcy, C., 2015. An analysis of metrics used to measure performance in green and sustainable supply chains. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 86, pp.360-377.
- Alvarez, G., Pilbeam, C. and Wilding, R. (2010). Nestlé Nespresso AAA sustainable quality program: an investigation into the governance dynamics in a multi-stakeholder supply chain network. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 15(2), pp.165-182.
- Akamp, M. and Müller, M., 2013. Supplier management in developing countries. *Journal of cleaner production*, 56, pp.54-62.
- Anderson, R.J., 1994. Representations and requirements: The value of ethnography in system design. *Human-computer interaction*, 9(2), pp.151-182.
- Ansari, Z. and Kant, R., 2017. A state-of-art literature review reflecting 15 years of focus on sustainable supply chain management.
- Ashby, A., Leat, M. and Hudson-Smith, M. (2012). Making connections: a review of supply chain management and sustainability literature. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 17(5), pp.497-516.
- Alwaysheh, A. and Klassen, R.D., 2010. The impact of supply chain structure on the use of supplier socially responsible practices. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 30(12), pp.1246-1268.
- Azapagic, A. and Perdan, S., 2000. Indicators of sustainable development for industry: a general framework. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, 78(4), pp.243-261.

- B. Roxas and D. Chadee, "Environmental sustainability orientation and financial resources of small manufacturing firms in the Philippines," *Social Responsibility Journal*, vol. 8.2, pp. 208-226, 2012.
- Baghersad, M. and Zobel, C.W. (2021) 'Assessing the extended impacts of supply chain disruptions on firms: An empirical study', *International Journal of Production Economics*, 231, p. 107862. doi:10.1016/j.ijpe.2020.107862.
- Barauskaite, G. and Streimikiene, D. (2020) "Corporate Social Responsibility and financial performance of companies: The puzzle of concepts, definitions and assessment methods," *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 28(1), pp. 278–287. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2048>.
- Barreto, I. (2009), "Dynamic capabilities: a review of past research and an agenda for the future", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 36 No. 1, pp. 256-280, doi: 10.1177/0149206309350776.
- Beckmann, M., Hielscher, S. and Pies, I., 2012. Commitment Strategies for Sustainability: How Business Firms Can Transform Trade-Offs into Win-Win Outcomes. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 23(1), pp.18-37.
- Benbasat, I., Goldstein, D.K. and Mead, M. (1987) "The case research strategy in studies of Information Systems," *MIS Quarterly*, 11(3), p. 369. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/248684>.
- Beske-Janssen, P., Johnson, M. and Schaltegger, S., 2015. 20 years of performance measurement in sustainable supply chain management – what has been achieved? *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 20(6), pp.664-680.
- Blaikie, 1993 N. Blaikie *Approaches to social enquiry Polity*, Cambridge (1993)

- Blome, C. and Paulraj, A., 2013. Ethical climate and purchasing social responsibility: A benevolence focus. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 116(3), pp.567-585.
- Bonatto, F., Resende, L.M.M.d. and Pontes, J. (2022), "Supply chain governance: a conceptual model", *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, Vol. 37 No. 2, pp. 309-325. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBIM-09-2019-0418>
- Brandenburg, M. et al. (2014) "Quantitative models for Sustainable Supply Chain Management: Developments and directions," *European Journal of Operational Research*, 233(2), pp. 299–312. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2013.09.032>.
- Barratt, M., Choi, T.Y. and Li, M., 2011. Qualitative case studies in operations management: Trends, research outcomes, and future research implications. *Journal of operations management*, 29(4), pp.329-342.
- Brockhaus, S., Kersten, W. and Knemeyer, A., 2013. Where Do We Go from Here? Progressing Sustainability Implementation Efforts Across Supply Chains. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 34(2), pp.167-182.
- Brundtland (1987) Our common future - UN documents. Available at: <http://www.un-documents.net/our-common-future.pdf>.
- Bryman, A. (2012) *Social Research Methods*. 4th Edition, Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2015). *Business Research Methods* (4th ed.). Oxford: Oxford Univ. Press.

- Bubicz, M.E., Barbosa-Póvoa, A.P. and Carvalho, A. (2019) “Incorporating social aspects in sustainable supply chains: Trends and future directions,” *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 237, p. 117500. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.06.331>.
- Bubicz, M., Dias Barbosa-Póvoa, A. and Carvalho, A., 2021. Social sustainability management in the apparel supply chains. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 280, p.124214.
- Burgess, K., Singh, P.J. and Koroglu, R., 2006. Supply chain management: a structured literature review and implications for future research. *International journal of operations & production Management*.
- Burrell, G. and Morgan, G., 2017. *Sociological paradigms and organisational analysis: Elements of the sociology of corporate life*. Routledge.
- Cantor, D.E., Morrow, P.C. and Montabon, F., 2012. Engagement in environmental behaviors among supply chain management employees: An organizational support theoretical perspective. *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 48(3), pp.33-51.
- Carroll, A.B. (1991) “The Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility: Toward the moral management of organizational stakeholders,” *Business Horizons*, 34(4), pp. 39–48. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0007-6813\(91\)90005-g](https://doi.org/10.1016/0007-6813(91)90005-g).
- Carroll, A.B. (2016) “Carroll’s Pyramid of CSR: Taking another look,” *International Journal of Corporate Social Responsibility*, 1(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40991-016-0004-6>.

- Carter, C.R. and Jennings, M.M. (2004) “Social Responsibility and supply chain relationships,” *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 38(1), pp. 37–52. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1366-5545\(01\)00008-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1366-5545(01)00008-4).
- Carter, C. and Rogers, D. (2008). A framework of sustainable supply chain management: moving toward new theory. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 38(5), pp.360-387.
- Carter, C. and Liane Easton, P. (2011). Sustainable supply chain management: evolution and future directions. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 41(1), pp.46-62.
- Chardine-Baumann, E. and Botta-Genoulaz, V. (2014). A framework for sustainable performance assessment of supply chain management practices. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 76, pp.138-147.
- Chandrasekaran, N. and Raghuram, G., 2014. *Agribusiness supply chain management*. CRC Press.
- Chopra, Sunil, and Peter Meindl, (2015) *Supply Chain*. 6th Edition, Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice-Hall, Inc., Chapter 1.
- Claro, P.B.d.O. and Esteves, N.R. (2021), "Sustainability-oriented strategy and Sustainable Development Goals", *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, Vol. 39 No. 4, pp. 613-630. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MIP-08-2020-036>.
- Cornelissen, J.P., Haslam, S.A. and Balmer, J.M., 2007. Social identity, organizational identity and corporate identity: Towards an integrated understanding of processes, patterning and products. *British journal of management*, 18, pp. S1-S16.

- Crane, A. et al. (2009) 'The Corporate Social Responsibility Agenda', The Oxford Handbook of Corporate Social Responsibility, pp. 3–16. doi:10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199211593.003.0001.
- Crane, A. et al. (2009) 'The Corporate Social Responsibility Agenda', The Oxford Handbook of Corporate Social Responsibility, pp. 3–16. doi:10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199211593.003.0001.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative Inquiry & Research Design: Choosing among Five Approaches* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.
- Croom, S. et al. (2018) "Impact of social sustainability orientation and supply chain practices on operational performance," *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 38(12), pp. 2344–2366. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijopm-03-2017-0180>.
- D. R. Cooper, C. W. Emory, "Business Research Methods," 5th Edition, Irwin, 1995.
- Dahlsrud, A. (2008) "How corporate social responsibility is defined: An analysis of 37 definitions," *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 15(1), pp. 1–13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.132>.
- Davies, I. A., H. Haugh, and L. Chambers. 2019. "Barriers to Social Enterprise Growth." *Journal of Small Business Management* 57 (4): 1616–1636.
- De Brito, M.P., Carbone, V. and Blanquart, C.M., 2008. Towards a sustainable fashion retail supply chain in Europe: Organisation and performance. *International journal of production economics*, 114(2), pp.534-553.

- Denu, M.K., Bentley, Y. and Duan, Y. (2023) ‘Social Sustainability Performance: Developing and validating measures in the context of emerging African economies’, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 412, p. 137391. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137391.
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2005). *The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Research* (3rd ed.). London: Sage Publications.
- Du, S., Bhattacharya, C. and Sen, S., 2010. Maximizing Business Returns to Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR): The Role of CSR Communication. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 12(1), pp.8-19.
- Dubey, R., Gunasekaran, A., Childe, S., Papadopoulos, T. and Fosso Wamba, S. (2017). World class sustainable supply chain management: critical review and further research directions. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 28(2), pp.332-362.
- Dyllick, T. and Hockerts, K. (2002) “Beyond the business case for Corporate Sustainability,” *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 11(2), pp. 130–141. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.323>.
- Dyck, B. and Silvestre, B. (2018a). Enhancing socio-ecological value creation through sustainable innovation 2.0: Moving away from maximizing financial value capture. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 171, pp.1593-1604.
- Dyck, B. and Silvestre, B.S., (2018b). Enhancing socio-ecological value creation through sustainable innovation 2.0: Moving away from maximizing financial value capture. *Journal of cleaner Production*, 171, pp.1593-1604.
- Ehrgott, M., Reimann, F., Kaufmann, L. and Carter, C.R., 2011. Social sustainability in selecting emerging economy suppliers. *Journal of business ethics*, 98(1), pp.99-119.

- Eisenhardt, K.M. and Graebner, M.E. (2008) “Theory building from cases: Opportunities and challenges,” *Academy of Management Journal*, 50(1), pp. 25–32. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2007.24160888>.
- Elkington, J. 1994. Towards the sustainable corporation: Win–win–win business strategies for sustainable development. *California management review* 36 (2): 70–100.
- Elkington, J., 2004. *Cannibals with forks: the triple bottom line of 21st century business*. Capstone, Oxford.
- Elkington, J. 2013. Enter the triple bottom line. In *The triple bottom line*, 23–38. London: Routledge.
- El-Khalil, R. and Mezher, M., 2020. The mediating impact of sustainability on the relationship between agility and operational performance. *Operations Research Perspectives*, 7, p.100171.
- Eisenhardt, K. M. (1989). Building theories from case study research. *Academy of Management Review*, 14, 532-550.
- Fawcett, S.E., Ellram, L.M. and Ogden, J.A. (2014) *Supply Chain Management: Pearson New International Edition: From vision to implementation*. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
- Fernando, Y. et al. (2022) “Sustainable social supply chain practices and firm Social Performance: Framework and empirical evidence,” *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 32, pp. 160–172. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.04.020>.

- Fleetwood, S., 2005. Ontology in organization and management studies: A critical realist perspective. *Organization*, 12(2), pp.197-222.
- Foerstl, K., Reuter, C., Hartmann, E. and Blome, C., 2010. Managing supplier sustainability risks in a dynamically changing environment—Sustainable supplier management in the chemical industry. *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 16(2), pp.118-130.
- Foladori, G. (2005). Advances and Limits of Social Sustainability as an Evolving Concept. *Canadian Journal of Development Studies/Revue canadienne d'études du développement*, 26(3), pp.501-510.
- Font, X., Tapper, R., Schwartz, K. and Kornylak, M. (2008). Sustainable supply chain management in tourism. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 17(4), pp.260-271.
- Formentini, M. and Taticchi, P. (2016). Corporate sustainability approaches and governance mechanisms in sustainable supply chain management. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 112, pp.1920-1933.
- Freeman, R. E. (1984). *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139192675>
- G. Morgan, and L. Smircich, “The Case for Qualitative Research,” *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 5, No. 4, 1980, pp. 491-500.
- Ganeshan, Ram, and Terry P. Harrison, (1995) “An Introduction to Supply Chain Management,” Department of Management Sciences and Information Systems, 303 Beam Business Building, Penn State University, University Park, Pennsylvania).

- Gaur, J., and V. Mani. 2018. “Antecedents of Closed-Loop Supply Chain in Emerging Economies: A Conceptual Framework Using Stakeholder’s Perspective.” *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 139: 219–227. doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.08.023.
- Gibson, B.J., Mentzer, J.T. and Cook, R.L. (2005) ‘Supply Chain Management: The pursuit of a consensus definition’, *Journal of Business Logistics*, 26(2), pp. 17–25. doi:10.1002/j.2158-1592. 2005.tb00203. x.
- Gill, R., 2002. Change management--or change leadership? *Journal of change management*, 3(4), pp.307-318.
- Gimenez, C. and Tachizawa, E. (2012). Extending sustainability to suppliers: a systematic literature review. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 17(5), pp.531-543.
- Gold, S., Seuring, S. and Beske, P. (2009). Sustainable supply chain management and inter-organizational resources: a literature review. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*.
- Gold, S., 2011. Bio-energy supply chains and stakeholders. *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 16(4), pp.439-462.
- Golicic, S. and Davis, D., 2012. Implementing mixed methods research in supply chain management. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 42(8/9), pp.726-741.
- Golicic, S.L., Lenk, M.M. and Hazen, B.T. (2019) “A global meaning of supply chain social sustainability,” *Production Planning & Control*, 31(11-12), pp. 988–1004. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2019.1695911>.

- Gopalakrishnan, K., Yusuf, Y., Musa, A., Abubakar, T. and Ambursa, H. (2012). Sustainable supply chain management: A case study of British Aerospace (BAe) Systems. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 140(1), pp.193-203.
- Gouda, S. and Saranga, H., 2018. Sustainable supply chains for supply chain sustainability: impact of sustainability efforts on supply chain risk. *International Journal of Production Research*, 56(17), pp.5820-5835.
- Govindan, K., Shaw, M. and Majumdar, A. (2021) ‘Social Sustainability Tensions in multi-tier supply chain: A systematic literature review towards Conceptual Framework Development’, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 279, p. 123075. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123075.
- Gunasekaran, A. and Ngai, E.W.T. (2011) ‘Strategic Enterprise Information Systems for Global Supply Chain Competitiveness’, *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 20(3), pp. 215–216. doi: 10.1016/j.jsis.2011.05.004.
- GRI standards 2016 PDF (2016) Scribd. Scribd. Available at: <https://www.scribd.com/document/407901203/GRI-Standards-2016-pdf>.
- Hall, J. and Matos, S., 2010. Incorporating impoverished communities in sustainable supply chains. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*.
- Hall, J., Matos, S. and Silvestre, B. (2012a). Understanding why firms should invest in sustainable supply chains: a complexity approach. *International Journal of Production Research*, 50(5), pp.1332-1348.
- Hall, J., Matos, S., Sheehan, L. and Silvestre, B. (2012b). Entrepreneurship and Innovation at the Base of the Pyramid: A Recipe for Inclusive Growth or Social Exclusion? *Journal of Management Studies*, 49(4), pp.785-812.

- Haleem, F. et al. (2022) “Sustainable management practices and stakeholder pressure: A systematic literature review,” *Sustainability*, 14(4), p. 1967. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14041967>.
- Hannibal, C., and K. Kauppi. 2019. “Third Party Social Sustainability Assessment: Is it a Multi-Tier Supply Chain Solution?” *International Journal of Production Economics* 217: 78–87.
- Hahn, T., Figge, F., Pinkse, J. and Preuss, L., 2018. A paradox perspective on corporate sustainability: Descriptive, instrumental, and normative aspects. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 148(2), pp.235-248.
- Harms, D., Hansen, E. and Schaltegger, S., 2012. Strategies in Sustainable Supply Chain Management: An Empirical Investigation of Large German Companies. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 20(4), pp.205-218.
- Hervani, A.A., Helms, M.M. and Sarkis, J., 2005. Performance measurement for green supply chain management. *Benchmarking: An international journal*, 12(4), pp.330-353.
- Hojmosse, S., Roehrich, J. and Grosvold, J. (2014). Is doing more doing better? The relationship between responsible supply chain management and corporate reputation. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 43(1), pp.77-90.
- Hollweck, T. (2016) “Robert K. Yin. (2014). *Case Study Research Design and methods* (5th ed.). Thousand Oaks, ca: Sage. 282 pages.,” *The Canadian Journal of Program Evaluation* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3138/cjpe.30.1.108>.

- Hollos, D., Blome, C. and Foerstl, K., 2012. Does sustainable supplier co-operation affect performance? Examining implications for the triple bottom line. *International journal of production research*, 50(11), pp.2968-2986.
- Homburg, C., Wieseke, J. and Bornemann, T., 2009. Implementing the marketing concept at the employee-customer interface: the role of customer need knowledge. *Journal of marketing*, 73(4), pp.64-81.
- Hugos, M. (2018) *Essentials of supply chain management*. 4th edn. Hoboken: Wiley.
- Huq, F.A. and Stevenson, M. (2018) ‘Implementing socially sustainable practices in challenging institutional contexts: Building theory from seven developing country supplier cases’, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 161(2), pp. 415–442. doi:10.1007/s10551-018-3951-x.
- Huq, F.A., Chowdhury, I.N. and Klassen, R.D., 2016. Social management capabilities of multinational buying firms and their emerging market suppliers: An exploratory study of the clothing industry. *Journal of Operations Management*, 46, pp.19-37.
- Hutchins, M.J. and Sutherland, J.W. (2009) “The role of the social dimension in life cycle engineering,” *International Journal of Sustainable Manufacturing*, 1(3), p. 238. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijsm.2009.023972>
- Hussain, M., M. M. Ajmal, A. Gunasekaran, and M. Khan.2018. “Exploration of Social Sustainability in Healthcare Supply Chain.” *Journal of Cleaner Production*203: 977–989.
- Isil, O. and Hernke, M. (2017). The Triple Bottom Line: A Critical Review from a Transdisciplinary Perspective. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 26(8), pp.1235-1251.

- Jajja, M.S. et al. (2020) 'The indirect effect of social responsibility standards on organizational performance in apparel supply chains: A developing country perspective', *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 139, p. 101968. doi:10.1016/j.tre.2020.101968.
- Jia, F., Zuluaga-Cardona, L., Bailey, A. and Rueda, X., 2018. Sustainable supply chain management in developing countries: An analysis of the literature. *Journal of cleaner production*, 189, pp.263-278.
- Jeremy Hall, Stelvia Matos, (2010) "Incorporating impoverished communities in sustainable supply chains", *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, Vol. 40 Issue: 1/2, pp.124-147.
- Jorgensen, A., Le Bocq, A., Nazarkina, L. and Hauschild, M. (2007). Methodologies for social life cycle assessment. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 13(2), pp.96-103.
- K. Gopalakrishnan, Y.Y. Yusuf, A. Musa, T. Abubakar, H.M. Ambursa Sustainable supply chain management: a case study of British Aerospace (BAe) systems *Int. J. Prod. Econ.*, 140 (1) (2012), pp. 193-203.
- K.F. Yuen, X. Wang, Y.D. Wong, and Q. Zhou, "Antecedents and outcomes of sustainable shipping practices: The integration of stakeholder and behavioural theories," *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, vol. 108. pp. 18-35, 2017.
- Karjalainen, K. and Moxham, C. (2012) "Focus on fairtrade: Propositions for integrating Fairtrade and Supply Chain Management Research," *Journal of Business Ethics*, 116(2), pp. 267–282. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-012-1469-1>.

- Khan, Syed Abdul Rehman, and Yu Zhang.2020. “Assessing the eco-environmental performance: an PLS-SEM approach with practice-based view.” *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*.
- Khandelwal, C. et al. (2021) ‘Agriculture Supply Chain Management: A review (2010–2020)’, *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 47, pp. 3144–3153. doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2021.06.193.
- Khan, S., Zkik, K., Belhadi, A. and Kamble, S., 2021. Evaluating barriers and solutions for social sustainability adoption in multi-tier supply chains. *International Journal of Production Research*, 59(11), pp.3378-3397.
- Klassen, R.D. and Vereecke, A. (2012) ‘Social issues in supply chains: Capabilities link responsibility, risk (opportunity), and performance’, *International Journal of Production Economics*, 140(1), pp. 103–115. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2012.01.021.
- Kleindorfer, P. and Saad, G. (2009). *Managing Disruption Risks in Supply Chains*. *Production and Operations Management*, 14(1), pp.53-68.
- Köksal, D., Strähle, J., Müller, M. and Freise, M., 2017. Social Sustainable Supply Chain Management in the Textile and Apparel Industry—A Literature Review. *Sustainability*, 9(1), p.100.
- Kolk, A. (2003) “Trends in sustainability reporting by the fortune global 250,” *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 12(5), pp. 279–291. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.370>.
- KRAUSE, D.A.N.I.E.L.R., VACHON, S.T.E.P.H.A.N. and KLASSEN, R.O.B.E.R.T.D. (2009) “Special topic forum on Sustainable Supply Chain Management: Introduction and reflections on the role of Purchasing Management,”

Journal of Supply Chain Management, 45(4), pp. 18–25. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-493x.2009.03173.x>.

- Krut, R. and Gleckman, H., 2013. ISO 14001: A missed opportunity for sustainable global industrial development. Routledge.
- Kumar, D. and Rahman, Z. (2017) ‘Analyzing enablers of sustainable supply chain: ISM and Fuzzy AHP approach’, Journal of Modelling in Management, 12(3), pp. 498–524. doi:10.1108/jm2-02-2016-0013.
- Labuschagne, C., Brent, A., and van Erick, R. (2005). Assessing the sustainability performances of industries. Journal of Cleaner Production, 13(4), pp.373-385
- Lafferty, William M. and Oluf Langhelle. “Towards sustainable development” (1999). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230378797>.
- Lalwani, S., Nunes, B., Chicksand, D. and Boojihawon, D., 2018. Benchmarking self-declared social sustainability initiatives in cocoa sourcing. Benchmarking: An International Journal, 25(9), pp.3986-4008.
- Lambert, Douglas M., James R. Stock, and Lisa M. Ellram, (1998) Fundamentals of Logistics Management, Boston, MA: Irwin/McGraw-Hill, Chapter 14).
- Lambert, D.M. and Enz, M.G. (2017) “Issues in Supply Chain Management: Progress and potential,” Industrial Marketing Management, 62, pp. 1–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2016.12.002>.
- Luring, J. and Thomsen, C., 2009. Collective ideals and practices in sustainable development: managing corporate identity. Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management, 16(1), pp.38-47.

- Lee, K.H., 2011. Integrating carbon footprint into supply chain management: the case of Hyundai Motor Company (HMC) in the automobile industry. *Journal of cleaner production*, 19(11), pp.1216-1223.
- Lee, C., Che-Ha, N. and Syed Alwi, S., 2021. Service customer orientation and social sustainability: The case of small medium enterprises. *Journal of Business Research*, 122, pp.751-760.
- Lehtonen, M. (2004) “The Environmental–Social Interface of Sustainable Development: Capabilities, social capital, institutions,” *Ecological Economics*, 49(2), pp. 199–214. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2004.03.019>.
- Leire, C. and Mont, O., 2010. The implementation of socially responsible purchasing. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*.
- León Bravo, V., Jaramillo Villacrés, M. and Silva, M., 2021. Analysing competing logics towards sustainable supplier management. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*.
- Lewis, M.W., 1998. Iterative triangulation: a theory development process using existing case studies. *Journal of operations Management*, 16(4), pp.455-469.
- Linton, J.D., Klassen, R. and Jayaraman, V. (2007) “Sustainable Supply Chains: An introduction,” *Journal of Operations Management*, 25(6), pp. 1075–1082. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jom.2007.01.012>.
- Listed in the CSCMP Terms and Glossary at www.cscmp.org.
- Locke, L.F., Silverman, S.J. and Spirduso, W.W., 2009. *Reading and understanding research*. Sage Publications.

- Longoni, A. and Cagliano, R., 2016. Human resource and customer benefits through sustainable operations. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 36(12), pp.1719-1740.
- Luo, J. et al. (2018) 'Agri-Food Supply Chain Management: Bibliometric and content analyses', *Sustainability*, 10(5), p. 1573. doi:10.3390/su10051573.
- Lu, R.X.A., Lee, P.K.C. and Cheng, T.C.E. (2012) 'Socially responsible supplier development: Construct development and measurement validation', *International Journal of Production Economics*, 140(1), pp. 160–167. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2012.01.032.
- M.P. Johnson, "Sustainability Management and Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises: Managers' Awareness and Implementation of Innovative Tools," *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, vol. 22.5, pp. 271-285, 2015.
- M., Reimann, F., Kaufmann, L. and Carter, C. (2010). Social Sustainability in Selecting Emerging Economy Suppliers. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 98(1), pp.99-119.
- MacDonald, J.P., 2005. Strategic sustainable development using the ISO 14001 Standard. *Journal of cleaner production*, 13(6), pp.631-643.
- Mani, V., Agarwal, R., Gunasekaran, A., Papadopoulos, T., Dubey, R. and Childe, S. (2016a). Social sustainability in the supply chain: Construct development and measurement validation. *Ecological Indicators*, 71, pp.270-279.
- Mani, V., Gunasekaran, A., Papadopoulos, T., Hazen, B. and Dubey, R. (2016b). Supply chain social sustainability for developing nations: Evidence from India. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 111, pp.42-52.

- Mani, V. et al. (2017) 'Mitigating supply chain risk via sustainability using Big Data Analytics: Evidence from the Manufacturing Supply Chain', *Sustainability*, 9(4), p. 608. doi:10.3390/su9040608.
- Mani, V., Gunasekaran, A. and Delgado, C. (2018a). Enhancing supply chain performance through supplier social sustainability: An emerging economy perspective. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 195, pp.259-272.
- Mani, V., Gunasekaran, A. and Delgado, C. (2018b). Supply chain social sustainability: Standard adoption practices in Portuguese manufacturing firms. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 198, pp.149-164.
- Mani, V., Jabbour, C.J. and Mani, K.T.N. (2020) 'Supply chain social sustainability in small and medium manufacturing enterprises and firms' performance: Empirical evidence from an emerging Asian economy', *International Journal of Production Economics*, 227, p. 107656. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2020.107656.
- Mann, H., Mann, I.J.S. and Gullaiya (2017), "The role of organizational orientation and product attributes in performance for sustainability", *Procedia Computer Science*, Vol. 122, pp. 850-856
- Marshall, C. and Rossman, G.B. (1999) *Designing Qualitative Research*. 3rd Edition, International Educational and Professional Publisher, California, 35.
- Marshall, L. McCarthy, P. McGrath, and M. Claudy, "Going above and beyond: how sustainability culture and entrepreneurial orientation drive social sustainability supply chain practice adoption," *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, vol. 20.4, pp. 434-454, 2015.

- Marshall, D., McCarthy, L., Heavey, C. and McGrath, P., 2016. Environmental and social supply chain management sustainability practices: construct development and measurement. *Production Planning & Control*, 26(8), pp.673-690.
- Martins, C.L. and Pato, M.V. (2019) ‘Supply Chain Sustainability: A tertiary literature review’, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 225, pp. 995–1016. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.03.250.
- Mathiyazhagan, K. et al. (2021) ‘Evaluation of antecedents to social sustainability practices in multi-tier Indian automotive manufacturing firms’, *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(14), pp. 4786–4807. doi:10.1080/00207543.2021.1938276.
- Matos, S. and Silvestre, B. (2013). Managing stakeholder relations when developing sustainable business models: the case of the Brazilian energy sector. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 45, pp.61-73.
- Maxwell, J. A. (2013). *Qualitative Research Design: An Interactive Approach*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Mentzer, J.T. et al. (2002) “Defining Supply Chain Management,” *Journal of Business Logistics*, 22(2), pp. 1–25. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2158-1592.2001.tb00001.x>.
- Mentzer, John T., William DeWitt, James S. Keebler, Soonhong Min, Nancy W. Nix, Carlo D. Smith, and Zach G. Zacharia, (2001) “Defining Supply Chain Management,” *Journal of Business Logistics*, Vol. 22, No. 2, p. 18.
- Miemczyk, J. and Luzzini, D. (2019). Achieving triple bottom line sustainability in supply chains. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 39(2), pp.238-259.

- Migrant worker at Malaysian medical glove manufacturer dies of covid-19 (2020) The Guardian. Guardian News and Media. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/dec/14/worker-in-malaysian-medical-glove-factory-dies-of-covid-19-top-glove>.
- Milne, M. J., & Gray, R. H. (2007). The future of sustainability reporting. In J. Unerman, B. O'Dwyer, & J. Bebbington (Eds.), *Sustainability accounting and accountability*. London: Routledge
- Milne, M.J. and Gray, R. (2013) "W(H)ither ecology? the triple bottom line, the global reporting initiative, and Corporate Sustainability Reporting," *Journal of Business Ethics*, 118(1), pp. 13–29. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-012-1543-8>.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1984). *Qualitative data analysis*. London: Sage.
- Mingers, J., 2000. The contribution of critical realism as an underpinning philosophy for OR/MS and systems. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 51(11), pp.1256-1270.
- Ministry of Economy, Planning and Regional Development (2021) SND30 - National Development Strategy 2020-2030: for the structural transformation of inclusive development, Africa Designs Innovation - Bureau de Design Economique - Cameroun. Available at: http://bibliotheque.pssfp.net/livres/NATIONAL_DEVELOPMENT_STRATEGY_20_2030.pdf.
- MIT Centre for Transportation & Logistics and Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals. *State of Supply Chain Sustainability 2020*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Centre for Transportation & Logistics. 2020.

- Mohd Noor, K.B (2008) Case Study: A Strategic Research Methodology, American Journal of Applied Sciences.
- Monks, R., Minow, N., 2004. Corporate Governance, Blackwell Business, Cambridge
- Montiel, I. (2008) “Corporate Social Responsibility and corporate sustainability,” *Organization & Environment*, 21(3), pp. 245–269. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1086026608321329>.
- Morali, O. and Searcy, C. (2012). A Review of Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices in Canada. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 7(3), pp.635-658.
- Morais, D.O.C. and Silvestre, B.S. (2018) ‘Advancing Social Sustainability in Supply Chain Management: Lessons from multiple case studies in an emerging economy’, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 199, pp. 222–235. Doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.07.097.
- Morais, D.O.C.; Barbieri, J.C. Supply Chain Social Sustainability: Unveiling Focal Firm’s Archetypes under the Lens of Stakeholder and Contingency Theory. *Sustainability* 2022, 14, 1185. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14031185>.
- Movahedipour, M., Zeng, J., Yang, M. and Wu, X., 2017. An ISM approach for the barrier analysis in implementing sustainable supply chain management: An empirical study. *Management Decision*, 55(8), pp.1824-1850.
- Muller, A. and Kolk, A. (2010). Extrinsic and Intrinsic Drivers of Corporate Social Performance: Evidence from Foreign and Domestic Firms in Mexico. *Journal of Management Studies*, 47(1), pp.1-26.
- Naim, M., Disney, S. and Towill, D., 2004, Supply chain dynamics, In *Understanding Supply Chains: Concepts, Critiques, and Futures*, edited by Steve New and Roy Westbrook, Oxford University Press, Oxford

- Nakamba, C., Chan, P. and Sharmina, M. (2017). How does social sustainability feature in studies of supply chain management? A review and research agenda. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 22(6), pp.522-541.
- Naslund, D. (2002), “Logistics needs qualitative research – especially action research”, *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, Vol. 32 No. 5, pp. 321-38
- Nath, V. and Agrawal, R., 2020. Agility and lean practices as antecedents of supply chain social sustainability. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 40(10), pp.1589-1611.
- New, S.J. (1997), “The scope of supply chain management research”, *Supply Chain Management*, Vol. 2 No. 2, pp. 15-22.
- New, S.J. (2004), “The ethical supply chain”, in New, S.J. and Westbrook, R. (Eds), *Understanding Supply Chains: Concepts, Critiques and Futures*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, pp. 253-280.
- Ngoura Ndjidda, Ngo Bilong Adèe Amoa, Mohammadou Nourou. Agricultural Growth in Cameroon: What Effects of Official Development Assistance Financing? *African Scientific Journal*, 2022, 3 (14), 609. [ff10.5281/zenodo.7324075](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7324075)[ff](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7324075). [ffhal-03858915](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7324075).
- Nguyen, G.N. *et al.* (2021a) ‘Supply Chain Social Responsibility in labour- intensive industries: A practitioner’s perspective’, *Production Planning & Control*, 34(4), pp. 371–390. doi:10.1080/09537287.2021.1925172.
- Nichols, B., Stolze, H. and Kirchoff, J., 2019. Spillover effects of supply chain news on consumers' perceptions of product quality: An examination within the triple bottom line. *Journal of Operations Management*, 65(6), pp.536-559.

- Norman, W. and MacDonald, C. (2004) “Getting to the bottom of ‘Triple bottom line,’” *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 14(2), pp. 243–262. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5840/beq200414211>.
- Orlikowski, W. J., & Baroudi, J. (1991). Studying Information Technology in Organisations: Research Approaches and Assumptions. *Information Systems Research*, 2, 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.2.1.1>
- Ollivier de Leth, D. and Ros-Tonen, M., 2021. Creating Shared Value Through an Inclusive Development Lens: A Case Study of a CSV Strategy in Ghana’s Cocoa Sector. *Journal of Business Ethics*.
- PAGELL, M., WU, Z. and WASSERMAN, M. (2009). THINKING DIFFERENTLY ABOUT PURCHASING PORTFOLIOS: AN ASSESSMENT OF SUSTAINABLE SOURCING. *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 46(1), pp.57-73.
- Pagell, M. and Shevchenko, A. (2014) “Why research in Sustainable Supply Chain Management should have no future,” *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 50(1), pp. 44–55. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jscm.12037>.
- Palazzo, M. and Voller, A. (2021) ‘A systematic literature review of Food Sustainable Supply Chain Management (FSSCM): Building blocks and research trends’, *The TQM Journal*, 34(7), pp. 54–72. doi:10.1108/tqm-10-2021-0300.
- Pati, S., Hussain, M.A., Swain, S., Salisbury, C., Metsemakers, J.F., Knottnerus, J.A. and Akker, M.V.D., 2016. Development and validation of a questionnaire to assess multimorbidity in primary care: an Indian experience. *BioMed research international*, 2016.

- Patton, M.Q. (1990). *Qualitative evaluation and research methods* (2nd ed.). Newbury Park, CA: Sage, 532 pp.
- Parera, S., Soosay, C. and Sandhu, S. (2014), "Does Agility foster sustainability: development of a framework from a supply chain perspective", *Proceedings of the 12th ANZAM Operations, Supply Chain and Services Management Symposium*, pp. 1-19
- Peck, H. (2005), "Drivers of supply chain vulnerability: an integrated framework", *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, Vol. 35 No. 4, pp. 210-232. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09600030510599904>
- Pedersen, E.R. and Andersen, M., 2006. Safeguarding corporate social responsibility (CSR) in global supply chains: how codes of conduct are managed in buyer-supplier relationships. *Journal of Public Affairs: An International Journal*, 6(3-4), pp.228-240.
- Perez-Aleman, P. and Sandilands, M., 2008. Building value at the top and the bottom of the global supply chain: MNC-NGO partnerships. *California management review*, 51(1), pp.24-49.
- Pilbeam, C., Alvarez, G. and Wilson, H., 2012. The governance of supply networks: a systematic literature review. *Supply Chain Management: an international journal*.
- Perera, S., Soosay, C. and Sandhu, S., 2019. Investigating the Strategies for Supply Chain Agility and Competitiveness. *Asian Journal of Business and Accounting*, 12(1), pp.279-312.
- Porter, M.E. and Kramer, M.R., 2006. The link between competitive advantage and corporate social responsibility. *Harvard business review*, 84(12), pp.78-92.

- Porter, M.E. and Kramer, M.R., 2011. Creating shared value: Redefining capitalism and the role of the corporation in society. *Harvard Business Review*, 89(1/2), pp.62-77.
- Porteous, A., Rammohan, S. and Lee, H. (2015). Carrots or Sticks? Improving Social and Environmental Compliance at Suppliers Through Incentives and Penalties. *Production and Operations Management*.
- Prasad, P., 2015. Hermeneutics: The interpretation of texts. In *Crafting qualitative research: Working in the postpositivist traditions* (pp. 38-50). Routledge.
- R. Golini, A. Moretto, F. Caniato, M. Caridi, and M. Kalchschmidt, "Developing sustainability in the Italian meat supply chain: an empirical investigation," *International Journal of Production Research*, vol. 55.4, pp. 1183-1209, 2017.
- Remenyi, D., Williams, B., Money, A., and Swartz, E. (1998), *Doing Research in Business and Management*, London, Sage Publications, pp309.
- Report, C., 2022. BTI 2022 Cameroon Country Report. [online] BTI 2022. Available at: <https://bti-project.org/en/reports/country-report/CMR>>.
- Rinaldi, L., Unerman, J. and Tilt, C., 2014. The role of stakeholder engagement and dialogue within the sustainability accounting and reporting process. In *Sustainability accounting and accountability* (pp. 86-107). Routledge.
- Ritchie, J. and Lewis, J. (2013). *Qualitative research practice: A guide for social science students and researcher*. New Delhi: Sage.
- Roca, L.C. and Searcy, C., 2012. An analysis of indicators disclosed in corporate sustainability reports. *Journal of cleaner production*, 20(1), pp.103-118.

- Rondinelli, D. and Vastag, G., 2000. Panacea, common sense, or just a label? The value of ISO 14001 environmental management systems. *European Management Journal*, 18(5), pp.499-510.
- Rubio, D.M., Berg-Weger, M., Tebb, S.S., Lee, E.S. and Rauch, S., 2003. Objectifying content validity: Conducting a content validity study in social work research. *Social work research*, 27(2), pp.94-104.
- Ryciuk, U., 2020. Supply Chain Governance Mechanisms: A Review and Typology. *Eurasian Business Perspectives*, pp.145-159.
- Sancha, C., Gimenez, C., Sierra, V. and Kazeminia, A. (2015). Does implementing social supplier development practices pay off? *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 20(4), pp.389-403.
- Sánchez-Flores, R.B. et al. (2020) “Sustainable Supply Chain Management—a literature review on emerging economies,” *Sustainability*, 12(17), p. 6972. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12176972>.
- Sachin, N. and Rajesh, R. (2021) “An empirical study of supply chain sustainability with financial performances of Indian firms,” *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 24(5), pp. 6577–6601. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-021-01717-1>.
- Sarkis, J., Gonzalez-Torre, P. and Adenso-Diaz, B. (2010) Stakeholder Pressure and the Adoption of Environmental Practices: The Mediating Effect of Training. *Journal of Operations Management*, 28, 163-176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jom.2009.10.001>

- Sarkis, J., Zhu, Q. and Lai, K. (2011). An organizational theoretic review of green supply chain management literature. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 130(1), pp.1-15.
- Sarkis, J. and Dhavale, D.G. (2015) “Supplier selection for Sustainable Operations: A triple-bottom-line approach using a Bayesian framework,” *International Journal of Production Economics*, 166, pp. 177–191. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2014.11.007>.
- Sayer, A., 1999. Realism and social science. *Realism and Social Science*, pp.1-224.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (1997) *Research Methods for Business Students*. Pitman Publishing, London.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P.H.I.L.I.P. and Thornhill, A.D.R.I.A.N., 2007. *Research methods. Business Students 4th edition* Pearson Education Limited, England.
- Saunders, M.N.K., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A., 2019. *Research Methods for Business Students Eight Edition*. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*.
- Schaltegger, S. and Burritt, R., 2014. Measuring and managing sustainability performance of supply chains. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*.
- Schliephake, K., Stevens, G. and Clay, S., 2009. Making resources work more efficiently—the importance of supply chain partnerships. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 17(14), pp.1257-1263.
- Schönborn, G. et al. (2019) “Why Social Sustainability Counts: The impact of Corporate Social Sustainability Culture on financial success,” *Sustainable Production*

and Consumption, 17, pp. 1–10. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2018.08.008>.

- Sector strategies matrices - cameroonembassyusa.org (2010). Available at:
https://www.cameroonembassyusa.org/images/documents_folder/quick_links/Cameroon_DSCE_English_Version_Growth_and_Employment_Strategy_Paper_MONITORING.pdf (Accessed: May 22, 2021).
- Seuring, S. and Müller, M. (2008) “From a literature review to a conceptual framework for Sustainable Supply Chain Management,” *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 16(15), pp. 1699–1710. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2008.04.020>.
- Sendlhofer, T. and Lernborg, C.M. (2018) ‘Labour rights training 2.0: The Digitalisation of knowledge for workers in global supply chains’, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 179, pp. 616–630. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.12.173.
- Shah, R. and Ward, P.T. (2007), “Defining and developing measures of lean production”, *Journal of Operations Management*, Vol. 25 No. 1, pp. 785-805.
- Shalchian, H., Bouslah, K. and M’Zali, B. (2015) “A multi-dimensional analysis of corporate social responsibility: Different signals in different industries,” *Journal of Financial Risk Management*, 04(02), pp. 92–109. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.4236/jfrm.2015.42009>.
- Shafiq, A. et al. (2014) ‘Socially responsible practices: An exploratory study on scale development using stakeholder theory’, *Decision Sciences*, 45(4), pp. 683–716. doi:10.1111/deci.12085.
- Shah, R. and Ward, P.T. (2003), “Lean manufacturing: context, practices bundle, and performance”, *Journal of Operations Management*, Vol. 21 No. 2, pp. 129-149.

- Shalchian, H., Bouslah, K. and M'Zali, B. (2015) "A multi-dimensional analysis of corporate social responsibility: Different signals in different industries," *Journal of Financial Risk Management*, 04(02), pp. 92–109. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4236/jfrm.2015.42009>.
- Sharma, M. et al. (2021) "Industry 4.0 adoption for sustainability in multi-tier manufacturing supply chain in emerging economies," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 281, p. 125013. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125013>.
- Silvestre, B. and Neto, R. (2014). Capability accumulation, innovation, and technology diffusion: Lessons from a Base of the Pyramid cluster. *Technovation*, 34(5-6), pp.270-283.
- Silvestre, B. (2015). Sustainable supply chain management in emerging economies: Environmental turbulence, institutional voids, and sustainability trajectories. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 167, pp.156-169.
- Silvestre, B. (2016) "Sustainable Supply Chain Management: Current debate and future directions," *Gestão & Produção*, 23(2), pp. 235–249. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1590/0104-530x2202-16>.
- Sodhi, M. and Tang, C. (2011). Social enterprises as supply-chain enablers for the poor. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, 45(4), pp.146-153.
- Sodhi, M.M.S. (2015) "Conceptualizing social responsibility in operations via stakeholder resource-based view," *Production and Operations Management* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/poms.12393>.

- Sodhi, M.M.S. and Tang, C.S. (2018) “Corporate Social Sustainability in supply chains: A thematic analysis of the literature,” *International Journal of Production Research*, 56(1-2), pp. 882–901. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2017.1388934>.
- Starks, H., & Trinidad, S. B. (2007). Choose your method: A comparison of phenomenology, discourse analysis and grounded theory. *Qualitative Health Research*, 17(10), 1372-1380.
- Stadtler, H., 2005. Supply chain management and advanced planning—basics, overview and challenges. *European journal of operational research*, 163(3), pp.575-588.
- Stadtler, H., Kilger, C. and Meyr, H. (2015) ‘Supply Chain Management and advanced planning’, *Springer Texts in Business and Economics* [Preprint]. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-55309-7.
- Stuart, I., McCutcheon, D., Handfield, R., McLachlin, R. and Samson, D., 2002. Effective case research in operations management: a process perspective. *Journal of operations management*, 20(5), pp.419-433.
- Suresh, N., Sanders, G.L. and Braunscheidel, M.J. (2020) ‘Business continuity management for supply chains facing catastrophic events’, *IEEE Engineering Management Review*, 48(3), pp. 129–138. doi:10.1109/emr.2020.3005506.
- Symon, G. and Cassell, C. eds., 2012. *Qualitative organizational research: core methods and current challenges*. Sage.
- Teece, D.J. (2007), “Explicating dynamic capabilities: the nature and micro foundations of (sustainable)enterprise performance”, *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 28, pp. 1319-1350, doi:10.1002/smj.640.

- Thiruchelvam, S. and Tookey, J.E., 2011. Evolving trends of supplier selection criteria and methods. *International Journal of Automotive and Mechanical Engineering*, 4(1), pp.437-454.
- Thomsen, C. and Luring, J., 2008. Practicing the business of corporate social responsibility: a process perspective. *International Journal of Business Governance and Ethics*, 4(2), pp.117-131.
- Touboulic, A. and Walker, H. (2015). Theories in sustainable supply chain management: a structured literature review. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 45(1/2), pp.16-42.
- Toussaint, M., Cabanelas, P. and Blanco-González, A., 2020. Social sustainability in the food value chain: An integrative approach beyond corporate social responsibility. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 28(1), pp.103-115.
- Toussaint, M., Cabanelas, P. and González-Alvarado, T., 2021. What about the consumer choice? The influence of social sustainability on consumer's purchasing behavior in the Food Value Chain. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 27(1), p.100134.
- Tsolakis, N.K. et al. (2014) 'Agrifood Supply Chain Management: A comprehensive hierarchical decision-making framework and a critical taxonomy', *Biosystems Engineering*, 120, pp. 47–64. doi:10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2013.10.014.
- Tundys, B. (2020) "Sustainable Supply Chain Management – past, present and future," *Prace Naukowe Uniwersytetu Ekonomicznego we Wrocławiu*, 64(3), pp. 187–207. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15611/pn.2020.3.15>.

- Understanding Sustainable Development Cooperation Framework guidance (2019) United Nations. United Nations. Available at: <https://unsdg.un.org/resources/united-nations-sustainable-development-cooperation-framework-guidance> .
- UN_Global_Compact_Guide_to_Corporate_Sustainability. (2014). Available at: https://www.unglobalcompact.org/docs/publications/UNGlobal_Compact_Guide_to_Corporate_Sustainability.
- Varsei, M., Soosay, C., Fahimnia, B. and Sarkis, J., 2014. Framing sustainability performance of supply chains with multidimensional indicators. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 19(3), pp.242-257.
- Vachon, S. and Klassen, R.D., 2006. Extending green practices across the supply chain: the impact of upstream and downstream integration. *International journal of operations & Production Management*.
- Vereecke, A. and Muylle, S. (2006). Performance improvement through supply chain collaboration in Europe. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 26(11), pp.1176-1198.
- Venkatesh, V.G. et al. (2020) ‘Drivers of sub-supplier social sustainability compliance: An emerging economy perspective’, *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 25(6), pp. 655–677. doi:10.1108/scm-07-2019-0251.
- Vogel, D.J. (2005) “Is there a market for virtue?: The business case for corporate social responsibility,” *California Management Review*, 47(4), pp. 19–45. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/000812560504700401>.

- Voss, C., Tsikriktsis, N. and Frohlich, M. (2002), “Case research in operations management”, *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 22 No. 2, pp. 195-291.
- Vurro, C., Russo, A. and Perrini, F. (2009). *Shaping Sustainable Value Chains: Network Determinants of Supply Chain Governance Models*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 90(S4), pp.607-621.
- Wang, C.L. and Ahmed, P.K. (2007), “Dynamic capabilities: a review and research agenda”, *International Journal of Management Reviews*, Vol. 9 No. 1, pp. 31-51.
- Wang, Z. and Sarkis, J., 2017. Corporate social responsibility governance, outcomes, and financial performance. *Journal of cleaner production*, 162, pp.1607-1616.
- Walker, H. and Jones, N. (2012). Sustainable supply chain management across the UK private sector. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 17(1), pp.15-28.
- Winter, M. and Knemeyer, A.M. (2013), "Exploring the integration of sustainability and supply chain management: Current state and opportunities for future inquiry", *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, Vol. 43 No. 1, pp. 18-38. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09600031311293237>
- Wisker, G. (2001). *The Postgraduate Research Handbooks*. Great Britain: Palgrave.
- Wood, D. (1991) *Corporate Social Performance Revisited*. *Academy of Management Review*, 16, 691-718.
- Wisner, J.D., Tan, K.-C. and Leong, G.K. (2016) *Principles of Supply Chain Management: A balanced approach*. 4th edn. Boston, MA: Cengage Learning.

- Yadav, V.S. et al. (2022) ‘A systematic literature review of the agro-food Supply Chain: Challenges, network design, and Performance Measurement Perspectives’, *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 29, pp. 685–704. doi:10.1016/j.spc.2021.11.019.
- Yawar, S.A., &Searing, S. (2017). Management of social issues in supply chains: A literature review exploring social issues, actions, and performance outcomes. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 141(3), 621–643.
- Yin, J. (2017) ‘Institutional drivers for Corporate Social Responsibility in an emerging economy: A mixed-method study of Chinese Business Executives’, *Business & Society*, 56(5), pp. 672–704. doi:10.1177/0007650315592856.
- Yin, R.K. (2003) *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*. 3rd Edition, Sage, Thousand Oaks.
- Yin, R.K. (2008) *Case study research: Design and methods*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Yin, R.K. (2013) *Case study research: Design and methods*. 5th edn. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Yin, R. (2014). *Case Study Research: Design and Methods* (5th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Yin, R. (2015) *Qualitative Research from Start to Finish*. Guilford Publications, New York.
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case Study Research Design and Methods* (6th Ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publishing.
- Zadek, S. (2004). The Path to Corporate Responsibility. *Corporate Ethics and Corporate Governance*, pp.159-172.

- Zeng, H., Chen, X., Xiao, X. and Zhou, Z. (2017). Institutional pressures, sustainable supply chain management, and circular economy capability: Empirical evidence from Chinese eco-industrial park firms. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 155, pp.54-65.
- Zhu, J. Sarkis, and K.-h. Lai, "Institutional-based antecedents and performance outcomes of internal and external green supply chain management practices," *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, vol. 19.2, pp. 106-117, 2013.
- Zorzini, M. et al. (2015) "Socially responsible sourcing: Reviewing the literature and its use of theory," *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 35(1), pp. 60–109. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijopm-07-2013-0355>.

Appendices

Appendix A – Case Study Protocol

Title: Improving supply chain management through the implementation of social sustainability in the Cameroon Manufacturing industry

Aim: The research investigates the impact of social sustainability on improving supply chain management in selected companies in Cameroon Manufacturing Sector and develops a model to implement supply chain social sustainability.

Case Study Description

“An exploratory multi-case study is used as a research strategy to evaluate and analyse the impact of social sustainability on improving supply chain management and the achievement of high performance socially sustainable manufacturing industry. The case organisations for this research work are manufacturing companies in Cameroon. Case organisations are large due to supply chain power and showing evidence of the research phenomenon (community awareness of sustainability activities) in the Cameroonian manufacturing industry. Cameroon was selected due to its long-term vision for economic growth and social development and the manufacturing industry is considered a key pillar toward achieving the vision this has followed a heavy commitment from developmental partners of roughly 3 billion dollars. Data will be collected from informants with sufficient knowledge and experience on social sustainability and SSCM through interviews. Collectively, the data gathered during this case-study activity will support the delivery of the following four objectives”

Case-Study Objectives

1. To critically examine the existing trends of supply chain social sustainable initiatives in the Cameroonian manufacturing industry
 - a. Dimension of Social sustainability
 - b. motivation for social sustainability initiatives
 - c. criteria for implementing social sustainability initiatives.
 - d. relationship level
2. To analyze the benefits of implementation of social sustainability in the supply chain
3. To analyse the challenges to the implementation of social sustainability in the supply chain
4. To develop a framework to improve supply chain social sustainability in the manufacturing industry in Cameroon

Unit of analysis

The unit of the analysis is any member of the focal firm supply network impacted by the product and process aspect of the case organisations.

Selection Criteria

Case organisation should be large, have considerable supply chain power, be engaged in manufacturing activities, and be based in Cameroon. Also, there must be community awareness of sustainability activities (evidence of the phenomenon under investigation) from the case organisation.

Participant Selection

Using a non-probability purposeful sampling technique, it can be ensured that the necessary informants are chosen. Using this perspective, informants with sufficient knowledge and experience on social sustainability and SSCM will be selected as appropriate for the research. To avoid aspects of elite bias, within each case organisation, multiple interviewees should be chosen from both managerial and operational levels”.

Data collection instruments

Multiple resources to evidence are used to ensure the triangulation of data during case evaluation: semi-structured interviews and documents are used for this research. Semi-structured interviews are the main instruments for data collection and are corroborated with documents. To minimize bias, the researcher uses multiple sources of evidence and interviews people at different levels and functions to reduce the elite bias. The interview questions in Appendix B present guidance to steer the data collection process and to ensure consistency and validity across the cases.

Case Study Procedure and Roles

- **General rules**

The background of the research will be introduced before or at the beginning of the interview. Each interview lasts about an hour or more. All interviews are audio-recorded, and notes are taken during and after each interview. The confidentiality of the interview is ensured. English is the major interview language. Different languages may be used according to the status of the interviewees. For example, French in case the informant is French-speaking.

- **Pre-interview**

Contact prospective case organizations through email or telephone call to or in person to deposit of request for research participation to 1) explain the purpose of the research; 2) assure confidentiality and anonymity. Plan the interview in advance ensuring all the equipment and documents needed for the interview, such as a digital recorder, a notebook, participant information sheets, and interview questions sheets.

- **Post- interview**

Upload the recorded interviews to a computer and make backup copies.

Complete field notes.

Transcribe recording, translate, and make data reduction, and complete a write-up.

If needed, modify, or add propositions and research questions.

- **Data management**

Data will be collected via face-to-face and telephone interviews. All interviews will be recorded, with notes taken during and after the interview. Interviews will be transcribed from interview recordings into textual data. Transcription of recorded interviews will take place as new interviews are being conducted. This is aimed at identifying patterns and themes in participants' responses and modifying the interview questions to address developing themes and overlooked areas in the study. NVIVO 10 for Windows will be used for organizing, managing, and analysing data collected from the interviews. NVIVO is an excellent platform for the management, analysis, and reporting of unstructured or semi-structured data. It is a useful tool in qualitative data analysis for evaluating, interpreting, and explaining social phenomena.

- **Data Storage**

Collected data will be stored with confidentiality considerations. At least three backup copies of all the data will be kept in a computer, removable hard disk, and the university database. The backup data will be updated every day.

- **Analysis**

Identify the criteria for interpreting case study findings and identify which data elements are used to address which research question/sub-question/proposition and how the data elements will be combined to answer the questions.

Consider the range of possible outcomes identify alternative explanations of the outcomes and identify any information that is needed to distinguish between these.

The analysis should take place as the case study task progresses.

- **Plan Validity**

The validity of the case study should be ensured through the following means:

General – verify the plan against checklist items for the design and the data collection plan.

Construct validity - show that the correct operational measures are planned for the concepts being studied. Tactics for ensuring this include using multiple sources of evidence, establishing chains of evidence, and expert reviews of draft protocols and reports.

External validity – identify the domain to which study findings can be generalized. This research uses multiple-case studies to investigate outcomes in different organisations and adopts a five-stage case study research rigor.

Appendix B - Interview Guide for Case Organisations

Sustainability

Sustainability from an organizational context referred to as “corporate sustainability can be defined as meeting the needs of today’s direct and indirect stakeholders (such as shareholders employees, customers, regulatory bodies, and the society at large) without compromising its ability to meet the needs of future stakeholders”.

Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM)

“The creation of coordinated supply chains through the voluntary integration of economic, environmental, and social considerations with key inter-organisational business systems designed to efficiently and effectively manage the material, information, and capital flows associated with the procurement, production, and distribution of products or services to meet stakeholder requirements and improve the profitability, competitiveness, and resilience of the organisation over the short- and long-term” (p.339).

Social Sustainability

“As the products or processes aspect that affects human security, well-being, and community development. At a minimum, a better management/understanding of social sustainability in the supply chain requires exploring three fundamental questions”:

- **who is being targeted?**

concern with stakeholders “points toward spanning at least three levels of interested individuals and groups for social sustainability; the internal level within a firm’s operations, under the direct control of management, captures such aspects as workforce diversity and safety

management, etc. A second inter-firm level captures external interaction where strong economic ties connect firms, i.e., buying firms, suppliers, consumers, and end-users. Collectively, these two levels – internal and inter-firm levels capture the supply chain. Finally, Other external stakeholders, possibly with weak economic ties, such as communities, regulators, and NGOs, are a third level”.

- **which issues are being addressed?**

Initial research explored issues such as “Training, education, and Personal Skills, working conditions, child labour, human rights, ethics, health and safety, health and wellbeing, equity, Disabled/ Marginalized inclusion, development of minority, gender, product liability, Involvement with the Community, philanthropy. Given the wide range of human health and welfare concerns that could be labeled as ‘social variables’, managers are well served, at least initially, to focus on those aspects for which their firm bears responsibility”.

- **And how they are being addressed?**

In many respects, “the third “how” question pushes researchers and managers to translate the “who” and “which issues” questions into tangible management systems and programs. Thus, to characterize management’s approach to social sustainability in their supply chains”.

Sample Questions	Concepts
<p>Once the social initiative was identified: Why did the focal company launch initiative “X”? Could you comment on what factors led the focal company to adopt initiative “X”? As initiative “X” is potentially a source of costs, how do shareholders view it?</p>	<p>“Motivation for SC social sustainability (Gimenez and Tachizawa,2012) is either intrinsic or extrinsic (Ryan and Deci, 2000). Social initiatives that are launched based primarily on extrinsic motivations are focused on gaining direct or indirect financial rewards (e.g., increased profit margins, increased competitive advantage, larger market share), while approaches that are based primarily on intrinsic motivations are focused on ethical considerations</p>

<p>Explain how was the convincing process.</p> <p>Once approved, how was the process of integrating social sustainability initiatives in the supply chain?</p>	<p>and values of the decision maker (i.e., is it the right thing to do?) (Muller and Kolk, 2010). Approaches based on extrinsic motivations are related to the idea that “it pays to be ethical” (Burke and Logsdon, 1996), are associated with risk avoidance and/or opportunity-seeking behaviours (Silvestre, 2016), and can be linked to a multiplicity of drivers. By contrast, social initiatives that are launched based on intrinsic motivation are related to the mindset of decision-makers and organizational culture (instead of temporary opportunities and risks)”</p>
<p>What practices does the focal company use to interact with other players when integrating initiative “X” into the SC? Explain.</p>	<p>“A focal company engages with other supply chain actors to address social issues or launch social initiatives. At one extreme, the simple exchange of information defines the extent of engagement. At the other extreme of structural collaboration, there is a much higher degree of commitment to resolving social issues, and interaction becomes embedded in business practices and oriented toward integration (Vereecke and Muylle, 2006)”.</p>
<p>In terms of the initiative “X”, which stakeholder groups interact with the focal company?</p> <p>How do these interactions take place?</p> <p>How often do these interactions occur?</p>	<p>“Mani et al. (2015) classify social practices in Indian supply chains into four different relationship levels: internal operations; supplier relationship; consumer relationship and society relationship”</p>
<p>How does the focal company classify social sustainability internally?</p> <p>What category has been the target when integrating social initiatives” in the supply chain? Explain</p>	<p>Mani et al. (2016) “developed and validated five key categories of social issues in supply chains in India. They are philanthropy, health, safety and well-being, equity, ethics, and human rights”</p>
<p>What do you think could be the impediments to the adoption of social sustainability practices?</p>	
<p>What are the outcomes of your social sustainability activities?</p>	

What areas do you see for future work in supply chain social sustainability in your organizations?	
--	--

Appendix C - Social Initiatives

case	#	Initiatives	Standards adopted	Types
CO1	1	Reactivated and digitalized its quality management system “to ensure the sustainability of its operations to aligns with the firms drive towards a 100% quality and safety of its products, people, and the planet”	ISO 9001-2008 ISO 9001-2015 FSSC 22000 ANOR Certification	Health, safety, and wellbeing, product responsibility ethics, education and training, equity human right
	2	Developed a health and safety project to unite all teams around the values of the company by giving every member of the big family the feeling of belonging to it		Health safety, and well-being
	3	Launched a sponsored campaign promoting health by education in partnership with civil society organisations, hospitals, and the Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education from 2017 till the present in local communities across 300 educational infrastructures and hospitals to strengthen corporate citizenship		Community involvement, Philanthropy
	4	Lunch is an “initiative to support social entrepreneurs by connecting them with its employees to develop skills, share knowledge, and provide apprenticeship opportunities”.		Philanthropy
	5	Launched a “responsible consumption project with the stimulation of new		Health, safety, and wellbeing

		consumption patterns using products with refills and sustainable packaging”.		
	6	“Created a forum that brings together volunteers for socio-green projects, which has already benefited more than 23,000 people in the areas of health, education, culture, and sports”.		Philanthropy Health, safety, wellbeing
	7	“The company has a Communities Fund, an incubator of its social business that brings finance and skills to local companies aiming to address social problems such as malnutrition and access to clean drinking water”		Human right Health, safety, and wellbeing
CO2	8	Integrated a capacity-building program developed by the International Finance Corporation (IFC). The purpose was to boost the levels of professionalism for sustainable operations and services on its supply chain. An estimated 50,000 farmers, local cooperatives, and farmer organisational leaders benefited from this training	UTZ certification AMEA (Agribusiness Ecosystem Marketing Alliance)	Education and training
	9	The competitors’ program “is an initiative launched by Case B for commitment to its local supply chain and communities, enabling them to achieve better incomes and living standards while growing cocoa sustainably. The purpose is to accelerate progress towards a transparent global cocoa supply chain, to	UN global compact SDGs	Community involvement Health, safety, and wellbeing Product responsibility human rights, equity

		enable local suppliers and their communities to strengthen their socioeconomic resilience, and to deliver a sustainable supply of cocoa and chocolate products from bean to end-product”.		child and forced labour ethics education and training
	10	Community support program known as a community action plan (CAP) developed by Case B in collaboration with civil society organisations “to help strengthen communities around its operations, to improve access to basic services such as education, health, and nutrition and break down barriers to economic empowerment”		Community involvement Philanthropy Health, safety, and wellbeing Equity human rights (diversity issues)
CO3	11	Proactively partnered with the Fair Labour Association “to map the working conditions in its smallholder supply chain. The outcome was the rollout of Child labour monitoring and Remediation (CLMS). A digital platform. The move forms part of case C's commitment to put children first by tackling child labour and helping more children attend school across its entire direct supply chain”.	International Labour Standards (ILS)	Child labour Ethics Product responsibility
	12	The Cocoa Compass “is a sustainability program designed to support the creation of an environmentally positive, professionalised and quality focussed cocoa supply chain in case C comprising	SDGs	Human right child labour health, safety, and wellbeing

		coca farmers earning a living income, tackle child labour and help children access education”		community involvement
13		Launched Health Living campaign to reach its surrounding communities on issues of “health and nutrition, fight against poverty, lack of health infrastructure, access to clean water and sanitation which contribute to lowered life expectancies in the communities the company relies on for its core raw materials, which also correlates with supplier productivity”		Health, safety, and wellbeing community involvement (health and wellbeing and economic empowerment)
14		The quality and food safety program integrated the company's large-scale growers and smallholders to ensure all legal and quality standards were met in case C supply chain operations	FSSC 22000	Ethics Health, safety, and wellbeing Product responsibility
15		Successfully created more than 30 farmers’ cooperatives training over 7000 farmers directly on UTZ Certification – an industry certification standard for sustainable farming		Ethics Product responsibility Health, safety, and wellbeing Child labour Human rights Education and training
16		Created a platform AtSource for its agricultural supply chains “to give consumer insight to evidence social and environmental impact, that drive positive change on farmers, communities, and ecosystems”.		Ethics Product responsibility Community involvement Child labour Human right

CO4	17	Successfully implemented two channels of sourcing to achieve its mandatory responsible sourcing practices through the procurement organisation and farmer connect team working to ensure a transparent, sustainable, and resilient upstream supply chain	UN global compact ILO Declaration	Human rights, child labour Health, safety, and wellbeing Equity Ethics Community involvement (health and wellbeing) Product responsibility
	18	The project was developed to improve the challenge of child labour in case D's entire supply chain		child labour
	19	The Healthy Living Program leads to the training of mothers, teachers, and health workers, contributing to the creation of healthy eating habits, and contributes to access to quality food, at low cost, with the operation. gardens in preschools and hospitals stimulating healthier and balanced lifestyle choices. The program works to support the company's health and wellness strategy to promote preventive health and basic hygiene.		Health, safety, and wellbeing
	20	Developed corporate business principles that set out the actions and behaviour of everyone at the company. They provide a strong ethical framework, ensuring integrity of action and compliance with laws, and regulations and doing business sustainable in a way that creates shared value.	UN Global Compact	Ethics Product responsibility Community involvement

CO5	21	The program aimed at “producing palm oil and natural rubber in a way and with an approach that allows for long-term socio-economic development in the communities where case E operates. The program adopted a code of standards and good practices while strengthening and protecting communities’ rights, improving their quality of life, and protecting the environment”.	ILO UN global compact ISO	Human right Health and Safety Equity Ethics Community involvement (health and wellbeing) Philanthropy Product responsibility
	22	The project was developed to identify and mitigate human rights violations, including modern slavery and child labour, within the local supply communities been particularly exposed to such risk	ILO	Human rights (forced and compulsory labour) Child labour
	23	The company has an “Anti-Corruption policy to guide the conduct of employees and third parties who interact with the company or any of its subsidiaries, where over 600 people have been trained across the entire supply chain strongly regulating and limiting these practices”		Ethics
	24	The “Anti-competitive behaviour program in compliance with the ethical codes and business code, ensures all employees must abstain from practices limiting competition and, in the case of procurement, ensure that all competitors are treated equally during the entire procurement process”		Ethics

25	The “company has collaborated and partnered with development organisations on synergies that bring together complementary expertise in the realisation of its responsible management policy within its subsidiaries”		Health, safety, and wellbeing Product responsibility Human rights Child labour Community involvement
26	Proactively linked its agro-industrial activity and smallholders’ plantations to develop an “efficient and adapted response to economic development and food security needs”.		Health, safety, and wellbeing

Appendix D – Framework Feedback Sheet

Improving supply chain management through the implementation of social sustainability in
Cameroon Manufacturing industry

“Please kindly complete the following questionnaire based on your perception of the framework and explanatory worksheet.

Your feedback is crucial to the development of the final version of the framework as well as to the completion of this DBA research study and subsequent benefit to manufacturing companies.

All responses are treated as anonymous.

Questionnaire

Please assess the framework, and the content of the social sustainability improvement areas listed below, tick as appropriate, and send back to the email address above.

Social improvement area	Yes	No
I consider that:		
The content is accurate		
The content is complete		
The necessary changes are visible		
Implementation cost would be acceptable		
The use of appropriate performance measure is vital		

Key

comment

.....

.....
.....
.....

Your answers are very important, and they will help guide the discussion at the telephone conference meeting”.

Thank you once again for your help.

Molonge Uriel Ndely

Appendix E - Participant's information sheet

Subject: DBA Research on Sustainable Supply Chain Management

Dear Sir/Madam,

“I am a DBA student (Doctor of Business Administration) at the University of the West of Scotland currently doing my doctoral thesis on sustainable supply chain management. In relation to criteria and impacts with an interest in social sustainability.

The incorporation of social sustainability into business strategies improves risk mitigation and creates new opportunities that give businesses an edge over existing and potential competitors. The findings of this research will help the researcher to develop a framework that will help improve progress in the arena of supply chain social sustainability management.

I have read your standards with interest, and I can see that your organisation is active in supply chain management and highly features a sustainability agenda.

I am writing to you personally, to request if you would like the opportunity to participate in an interview regarding focus organisations' progress in the arena of supply chains with sustainability.

I do hope you will be interested in taking part in this piece of academic research. Your participation is voluntary, and you are free to withdraw at any time without reason. To start with, it would be a short conversation taking up no more than 50 minutes of your time. If you think you might then be more seriously interested, we could discuss your involvement in the research more substantially. It would be a good way to showcase your progress as a company, although it could be anonymous if preferred as well as any other information provided.

I do hope you will meet with me at your convenience for a short interview, or even allow me to arrange a short telephone interview if you would prefer. Alternatively, I would be happy to

speak with any of your team in addition to or instead of yourself if you feel you cannot give the time. I am happy to work entirely around you in terms of times and dates. Please let me know if you are happy for this interview to be recorded digitally and safely. I am happy to provide you with the results of this research if you indicate your interest.

Thank you immensely in advance for your cooperation and time.

For any questions about the research or how I intend to conduct the study, please contact me”.

Uriel Ndely Molonge, DBA student

e-mail: [REDACTED]

Phone: [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix F – Drivers for internal and external social sustainability initiatives

Exemplar Quotes**Benefit themes
(1st order)****Key benefits to the companies
(2nd order)****Main Motivation
(3rd order)****Social initiative**

'The happiness experienced by employees working for the ... is considered a major success factor. For this reason, the organization is strongly working to unite all teams around the values of the company by giving every member of the big family the feeling of belong to it.'

'We believe that our company will be successful in the long term only by creating value for our people, communities and shareholders, as well as for the society and for the environment. In line with our purpose and values and the way we do business, the Corporate Business Principles set out the actions and behaviours of everyone at the company and reflect our culture which has developed over the years. They provide a strong ethical framework, ensuring integrity of action and compliance with laws, regulations, and our own commitments.'

'On the foundation of strong business ethics and compliance, we do business sustainably and in a way that creates shared value. We conduct business in an ethical and principles-based manner even in the absence of legal or regulatory frameworks.'

'Our sustainability initiatives are driven by our ambitious corporate purpose to re-imagine global agriculture and food systems within our ethos of growing responsibly. Therefore, sustainability is at the heart of our business, not just because it is the right thing to do, but because there are clear business benefits.'

'Yes. Our values require us to integrate these aspects to ensure quality and consistency in our operations and the communities we operate in are not an exception.'

- Ethics
- Values

Long-term gains

Internal

Appendix G – Literature Review Table

Author	Title	Area of category	Areas covered	Social aspects	Decision level	Method
Ehrgott et al., (2011)	Social Sustainability in Selecting Emerging Economy Suppliers	Driver of social sustainability	Customer pressure, institutional pressures, and employee pressures	LC, HR, PR	Strategic	Survey
		Outcome	Buyer reputation, organisational leaning, and supplier strategic capabilities			
Lu et al. (2012)	Socially responsible supplier development: construct development and measurement validation	metrics	LC, S, HR, PR, investors		strategic	survey
		Supply chain driver	Supplier evaluation, supplier collaboration and information sharing			
		Principles for managing social sustainability	International standards on social responsibility (ISO 26000)			
Shafiq et al. (2014)	Socially responsible practices: An exploratory study on scale development using stakeholder theory	metrics	LC, HR, S, PR		Strategic	Survey
Mani et al., (2016a)	Supply chain social sustainability for developing nations: Evidence from India	Metrics	LC, HR, S, PR		Strategic	Qualitative case study

Mani et al. (2015)	Social sustainability in the supply chain: analysis of enablers	Enablers of social sustainability	Competitive pressure, customer requirements, employee union pressures, stakeholders pressure, skilful policy entrepreneur, awareness on social sustainability, government regulations, social organisational pressure, investor pressure, international certification and financial liquidity	LC, HR	-	Interpre structure: modellin (ISM)
Hug et al., (2014)	Social sustainability in developing country suppliers: an exploratory study in the ready-made garments industry of Bangladesh	Drivers of social sustainability	Skill labour shortage	LC, HR, S	Strategic	Multi-ca study
		Barriers	misalignment between the requirements of western codes of conduct and the cultural and socio-economic context			
		Practices and capabilities	Monitoring capabilities			
		Supply chain driver	Auditing			
Mani et al., (2016b)	Impediments to Social Sustainability Adoption in the Supply Chain: An ISM and MICMAC Analysis in Indian	Barriers	lack employees' unions pressure from the employees' unions, Lack stakeholders pressure, lack of customer requirements, lack	LC, HR, S, PR	-	Structur equation modellin

	Manufacturing Industries		of pressure from social organisations, and lack of zeal on the part of the skilful policy entrepreneurs, Lack of social concern, inadequate competitive pressure, lack of regulatory compliance and lack of awareness of social sustainability.			
(Brix-Asala et al., 2016)	Reverse logistics and informal valorisation at the Base of the Pyramid: A case study on sustainability synergies and trade-offs	Trade-off	Cost vs social performance measures			Case stu
(Mani et al., 2017)	Mitigating Supply Chain Risk via Sustainability Using Big Data Analytics: Evidence from the Manufacturing Supply Chain	Principles for managing social sustainability	Inspection and social reporting	LC	Strategic	Case stu
Hug and Stevenson (2018)	Implementing socially sustainable practices in challenging institutional contexts: Building theory	Driver of social sustainability Principles for managing social sustainability	Institutional pressure Codes and social standards (SA8000, ISO 20400)	LC, HR, S	Strategic	Case stu

	from seven developing country supplier cases					
Mani et al., (2018)	Enhancing supply chain performance through supplier social sustainability: an emerging economy perspective	Metrics	LC, HR, PR, S		Strategic	Mixed r
		outcome	Supply chain performance, supplier performance, operational performance			
Sendlhofer and Lernborg (2018)	Labour rights training 2.0: The digitalisation of knowledge for workers in global supply chains	Supply chain driver	IT- information sharing; stakeholder collaboration, ICT for creating economic and social value	LC	strategic	Cast stu
Morais and Silvestre (2018)	Advancing social sustainability in supply chain management: lessons from multiples case studies in an emerging economy	Driver of social sustainability	External pressures (competition, regulators, customers, secondary stakeholders, reputation and competitive advantage) and ethics and Values.	LC, HR, S, PR	Strategic	Multi-ca study
		Supply chain drivers	Collaboration and information exchange			
Mani and Gunasekaran (2018)	Four forces of supply chain social sustainability adoption in emerging economies	Drivers of social sustainability	Customer pressure, sustainability culture, government, and external stakeholders	LC, HR, S, PR	Strategic	survey

		outcome	Supplier social performance, buyer operational, buying firms social reputation			
Hannibal and Kauppi (2019)	Third party social sustainability assessment: Is it a multi-tier supply chain solution?	Supply chain driver	Assessment	LC, HR, S, PR	strategic	Qualitat
Venkatesh et al. (2020)	Drivers of sub-supplier social sustainability compliance: An emerging economy perspective	Drivers of social sustainability	Influence of institutional pressure on supplier compliance to Codes of conduct	LC	Strategic	Mixed r
Khan et al. (2020)	Evaluating barriers and solutions for social sustainability adoption in multi-tier supply chains	Barriers	Lack of government enforcement and regulation, financial limitations, lack of investor pressure, lack of industrial obligations	LC, HR, S, PR		hybrid multi-co methods based hesitant sets cumulat prospect theory along VIKOR
		Solutions	External social awareness, advanced technologies, human social awareness and supply chain coordination			
Nat et., (2020)	Agility and lean practices as antecedents of supply chain social sustainability.	Driver of social sustainability	Lean and Agility	LC, HR, PR	Strategic	survey
		outcome	Operational and social performance			
		Practice and capabilities	Agile practices			

Jajja et al. (2020)	The indirect effect of social responsibility standards on organizational performance in apparel supply chains: A developing country perspective.	Principles for managing social sustainability Outcome	SA 9000, ISO 26000, ISO 9000, ISO 14000 and BSCI code of conduct. Operational performance Quality performance	LC, S	Strategic	survey
(Mathiyazhagan et al. (2021)	Evaluation of antecedents to social sustainability practices in multi-tier Indian automotive manufacturing firms	Practices and capabilities	Customer management, Information sharing, Corporate sustainability reporting and standardisation, and monitoring practices	LC, HR, S, PR	Strategic	Total Interpretive Structural Modelling (TISM).
Morais and Barbieri (2022)	Supply Chain Social Sustainability: Unveiling Focal Firm's Archetypes under the Lens of Stakeholder and Contingency Theory	Practices and capabilities	Screening and selection, Incentive actions for Improvement, Assessment, Monitoring, Collaboration and Development		Strategic	Multi study
Mani et al. (2020)	Supply chain social sustainability in small and medium manufacturing enterprises and firms' performance: Empirical	Outcome	Supply chain performance Customer performance Supplier performance Operational performance	LC, HR, S, PR	Strategic	Mixed r

	evidence from an emerging Asian economy					
Denu et al. (2023)	Social sustainability performance: development and validation measures in the context of emerging African economies	Metrics		LC, HR, S, PR	Strategic	Mix me